

D3.2 Solution architecture and governance framework for shortlisted Use Cases

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Summary

Begonia Project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of ODPs across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) Use Cases (UCs), meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

Deliverable D3.2 treats the solution architecture, regulatory, Policy and governance aspects of the six shortlisted UCs, that the project has identified in previous phases WP2-D2.2 [2].

The approach followed here, is for each UC to address in detail the technological considerations in terms of reference layered architecture in order to provide the UC-specific solution architecture.

Next, the regulatory and policy specifications of each case are considered and the governance framework is identified and discussed for the first time in the project.

This way, Deliverable D3.2 will allow the project team to proceed with comparing and selecting the three UCs out of the current shortlist, which will lead to the implementation of preparatory activities in WP4.

Disclaimer

BEGONIA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
ANAC	Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil
API	Application Programming Interface
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CBP	Custom and Border Protection
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CF	Carbon Footprint
CL	Controllable Load
CP	Charging Point
CPP	Charging Point Providers
DC	Data Centre
DEA	Danish Energy Agency
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSS	Decision Support System
EAG	European Air Group
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EEDI	Energy Efficiency Design Index
EEXI	Energy Efficiency Existing Index
EFTI	Electronic Freight Transport Information
EEU	Energy End User
eIDAS	electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EMSP	E-Mobility Service Providers
ES	Electricity Supplier
ET	Electric Truck

EU	European Union
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Standards Organisation
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network
LUC	Light UAS Operator Certificate
ML	Machine Learning
MPO	Metering Point Operator
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MS	Milestone
ODP	Operational Digital Platform
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PC	Project Coordinator
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SOC	State Of Charge
SORA	Specific Operations Risk Assessment
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft Systems

UC	Use Case
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

1.1 BEGONIA Project

The aim of the BEGONIA Project is to expedite the European digital transformation by analyzing promising solutions and providing recommendations to the European Commission (EC). Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of ODPs in the energy and transport sectors across various European Union (EU) countries, with the goal of facilitating the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2 Work Package 3

WP3 is exploiting the six shortlisted UCs that were produced by WP2-D2.2 [2], towards fulfilling the following objectives:

- Develop technical criteria for filtering the UCs.
- Conduct a feasibility study for each shortlisted UC.
- Finalise the selection of UCs based on technical feasibility, regulatory compliance, and cost-benefit analysis.
- Design the solution architecture and governance for each selected UC.
- Develop the necessary regulatory and technical frameworks for each UC and ensure that the selected UCs meet the technical requirements and interoperability standards of the digital infrastructure platform.

This way, WP3 will deliver the three final UCs to WP4 for designing specific piloting activities. The structure of WP3 is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Structure of BEGONIA WP3

1.3 Deliverable description

In particular, Deliverable D3.2 “Solution architecture and governance framework for shortlisted cases”, which is issued in March 2025, is serving the needs of Task 3.2 “Solution architecture and governance framework for each shortlisted case”, by providing a detailed solution architecture and governance framework for each shortlisted UC that aligns with EU policies and standards. It is based on the requirements analysis that came out of WP3-D3.3 [3], which was issued in December 2024, with regard to the six shortlisted UCs and the relevant potential technologies for each one of them.

In D3.2, for each of the six shortlisted UCs, the detailed architecture solution is presented and discussed. Policy and Regulatory analysis follows per case, while the governance approach for each case is also analysed in order to encompass and facilitate the work carried out as part of Task 3.4 “Regulatory and technical framework for final UCs”.

The successful release of D3.2 marks Milestone (MS) 7 “Identification of 6 shortlisted UCs” and MS 8 “All shortlisted UCs to have a proposed solution architecture ready”, which are both due in March 2025.

1.4 Relation to other deliverables

Deliverable D3.2 is based on the requirements analysis that came out of [3] , which was issued in December 2024, about the six shortlisted UCs and the relevant potential technologies for each one of them.

Then D3.2 will feed information to D3.3 Feasibility studies and selection of final UCs, due in April 2025 and Deliverable D3.4 - Evaluation framework and governance scheme for the final cases, due in May 2025, which will describe the selection process for the three final UCs and the detailed implementation and governance plan for each one of them.

2. Analysis and methodology for the shortlisted Use Cases

2.1 Selected Use Cases

Following the shortlisting process outlined in Deliverable D2.1, six (6) UCs were selected for further development based on their technological feasibility, impact potential, and alignment with EU policies on digitalisation and sustainability. These UCs address critical challenges in energy, mobility, logistics, and infrastructure, leveraging advanced digital technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), and data spaces to enhance operational efficiency and interoperability. The selected UCs are:

- **UCI: Electricity customer-centric ODP** - A digital platform empowering electricity consumers with automated supplier switching, demand side flexibility, and enhanced market participation.
- **UCII: AI-driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and Grid** - A smart coordination platform optimising the interaction between electric vehicles, renewable energy sources, and the power grid.
- **UCIII: Digitalisation of Data Centres** - An energy efficiency and waste heat reuse framework to improve sustainability in data centre (DC) operations.
- **UCIV: Digital permits for drone-based inspections** - A secure and automated system for managing drone operation permits in linear infrastructure inspections.
- **UCV: Smart port operations** - A data-driven approach to optimising port logistics, traffic flow, and energy use for improved efficiency and sustainability.
- **UCVI: Carbon footprint of port supply chain** - A solution for accurately tracking and managing carbon emissions across multimodal transport in port logistics.

2.2 Proposed solution architecture and role of each layer

This section outlines the proposed solution architecture for the BEGONIA ODPs. Building upon the technology landscape and requirements detailed in D3.1, this architecture is designed to be modular, scalable, and interoperable, catering to the needs of the shortlisted UCs. As visually represented in Figure 2, the architecture is structured into four key layers: Perception, Middleware, Service, and Business. The following subsections describe the role and key functionalities of each layer within the overall ODP framework, highlighting how they facilitate cross-border data exchange and operational efficiency.

Figure 2 Generic BEGONIA ODP Architecture - Layered Model

2.2.1 Perception layer

The Perception Layer forms the foundation of the BEGONIA ODP architecture, acting as the interface with the physical world. Its primary role is to acquire and collect real-time data from diverse sources relevant to each UC. These sources, as detailed in D3.1, include IoT sensors in DCs, Electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure, and drone-mounted sensors for infrastructure inspections. This layer is responsible for ensuring accurate and timely data capture, often utilising technologies like 4G/5G and Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN) for robust connectivity. The Perception Layer in this architecture builds directly upon the technology considerations outlined in D3.1, focusing on deploying reliable sensor networks and communication protocols to provide the raw data necessary for the subsequent layers of the ODP to function effectively.

2.2.2 Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer is critical for enabling seamless interoperability within the BEGONIA ODP architecture and across different stakeholders. Its role is to bridge the gap between diverse systems and data sources, facilitating effective communication and data exchange. As discussed in Deliverable 3.1, this layer employs technologies like FIWARE Context Broker, Apache Camel, and API (Application Programming Interface) Gateways to achieve data integration, routing, and transformation. It also incorporates API Management functionalities to provide secure and controlled access to data and services, essential for cross-border data sharing and collaboration. This layer refines the middleware concepts from D3.1 by specifically emphasising the need for robust API security and integration with data spaces to address the cross-border nature of the BEGONIA UCs.

2.2.3 Service layer

The Service Layer is where the BEGONIA ODP truly delivers value, providing a range of core platform services built upon the data collected and integrated by the lower layers.

This layer is responsible for implementing the key functionalities of the ODP, including real-time energy monitoring, predictive analytics for grid load, and automated permit validation. Leveraging technologies identified in D3.1, such as AI/ML frameworks like TensorFlow or Scikit-learn, and Digital Twin platforms like Azure Digital Twins, the Service Layer processes data to generate actionable insights and optimised solutions for the UCs. While D3.1 discussed Business and Application Layers separately, the Service Layer in this architecture consolidates these functionalities, focusing on delivering a cohesive set of data-driven services that directly address the needs of the BEGONIA stakeholders. The terminology shift to "Service Layer" emphasises the service-oriented nature of the ODP, highlighting its role in providing valuable digital services to users and stakeholders.

2.2.4 Business layer

The Business Layer sits at the top of the BEGONIA ODP architecture, responsible for orchestrating the overall operation of the platform and ensuring it aligns with business goals and regulatory requirements. This layer implements high-level business logic and rules that govern how the ODP services are utilised and managed. Building upon the concepts in D3.1, the Business Layer incorporates functionalities for user-friendly dashboards for visualisation, automated compliance reporting, and governance mechanisms for data sharing. It provides interfaces for various stakeholders to interact with the platform, access insights, and manage operations. Furthermore, this layer is crucial for ensuring governance and policy compliance, aligning the ODP with EU regulations and project objectives. The Business Layer expands upon the Business and Application Layer concepts from D3.1 by placing a greater emphasis on the governance and strategic decision-making aspects of the ODP, ensuring it operates effectively within the broader European digital and policy landscape.

2.3 Overview of policy and regulatory analysis

The regulatory analysis conducted within the BEGONIA project focuses on studying the relevant regulatory implications of each UC, ensuring compliance with both EU and national legal frameworks. By examining potential regulatory barriers and enablers, the analysis had the goal of supporting the selection and refinement of the UCs. Additionally, this section provides a broader perspective on how BEGONIA's UCs align with key EU strategic policies, reinforcing their relevance within the Union's long-term objectives for digitalisation, energy transition, and market integration.

Alignment with European strategic policies

The European Union is accelerating its digital and energy transitions, recognising the importance of market integration, digital sovereignty, and regulatory harmonisation to strengthen competitiveness and sustainability. The Draghi Report and other EU strategic policies highlight the urgency of enhancing economic security, decarbonisation, and investment in advanced infrastructure. BEGONIA aligns with these objectives through its

study and evaluation of ODPs that all facilitate cross-border interoperability, improve energy and transport sector efficiency, and promote digital services across the EU.

Specifically, a fundamental challenge for the EU remains insufficient investment and market fragmentation, limiting innovation and slowing progress in key sectors. BEGONIA directly addresses this by identifying and refining the six UCs that leverage digital technologies to support electrification, optimise transport infrastructure, and enhance data-driven “decision-making”.

Focusing on the energy sector, the presented UCs align with the EU’s clean energy and grid modernisation goals by supporting the diversification of energy sources, enhancing consumer-centric electricity services, and integrating renewables with AI-driven energy management. These priorities reflect key ambitions such as reducing external dependencies and reinforcing grid resilience. In transport and logistics, the related UCs support the EU’s push toward smart mobility, carbon footprint (CF) tracking, and automation, ensuring that digital solutions facilitate more efficient, transparent, and sustainable transport networks.

In its totality, the work directly supports the EC’s Digital Decade strategy, which promotes secure data management, AI-driven infrastructure, and cross-border interoperability.

Regulatory analysis methodology

The specific regulatory analysis presented for each UC has been conducted in close coordination with their development to ensure a comprehensive assessment that both identifies regulatory constraints and provides valuable input for refining the UC implementations. The approach consisted of a two-phase process: an initial high-level regulatory analysis aimed at identifying preliminary barriers that could impact the feasibility -allowing for necessary adjustments to enhance compliance- followed by a detailed regulatory analysis that examined both EU and national regulations in the member states where the UCs were intended to be deployed, evaluating their short- and medium-term impact on the UCs.

Each UC was evaluated following a structured methodology:

- Understanding the UC in detail.
- Identifying key stakeholders and providers, engaging them to gather insights on regulatory barriers and challenges.
- Identifying relevant EU regulations applicable to the UC.
- Identifying national regulatory frameworks in the relevant member states.
- Evaluating the overall regulatory impact, including potential barriers and compliance challenges.

To ensure clarity and usability, the report presents the key findings in a summary table using a 'traffic light' system, which helps identify potential regulatory issues or clear blockers at a glance. A more extensive and detailed analysis is also available for further reference.

In general terms, the UCs did not present a critical regulatory barrier, also due to their generality. A more in-depth analysis with specific outcomes will also be conducted once the UCs are shortlisted to the final three.

2.4 Overview of governance model analysis

The UCs presented in this document offer different visions of how an ODP could provide novel services and benefits to various stakeholder groups. The stakeholder constellation for each UC is different, as is the value provided to them. As such, we need to consider a separate governance model for the ODP to support the successful participation of the stakeholders and ODP platform users.

A governance model for an ODP defines how stakeholders can participate in the ecosystem enabled by the ODP to create and capture value as intended by the ODP UC. It needs to consider the perspective of each stakeholder involved to ensure that there is sufficient trust and incentive for participation in the ODP and the use of its services and ensure that participants are adequately compensated for the provision of resources while creating sufficient benefits for them.

Governance models for digital platforms have multiple facets and can be diverse. A recent analysis of governance models used by modern digital platforms [1] defines three main elements of such governance models: 1) **Governance structure:** who owns and chooses the digital platform ecosystem's use, development, and architecture; 2) **governance mechanisms:** means used to implement the chosen governance structure; 3) **governance scope:** the expansiveness of the governance mechanisms, such as on what relationship and where they act.

A conceptual framework for digital governance has been developed in [2]. Governance is considered to be a mediator of value creation and capture. The Figure 3 shows how governance mechanisms provided by a digital platform control the participation of different actors participating in a digital platform ecosystem.

Figure 3 Governance mechanisms provided by an ODP

Governance defines a set of controls that verify input (e.g., resources that different ecosystem participants contribute) and outputs (e.g., the benefits or value) they obtain.

Process controls ensure the coordination of participants by ensuring tasks are allocated according to the role of the participants. *Relationship control* ensures that adequate trust between participants is adequately established and maintained and that perceived risks of participation are adequately managed. *Outcome control* focuses on how the competing interests of participants can be aligned by creating adequate incentives for them. A suitable governance model for an ODP needs to balance the trade-off between collaboration and competition, enabling value creation and exchange in the overall ecosystem.

There are different types of governance mechanisms [2] that support control, coordination, trust, and incentives. They can be realised by off-platform mechanisms such as contracts, supported by mechanisms on the digital platform, or fully autonomous. Defining each of them in detail or different options can be very complex.

Our initial analysis of the governance model for each UC in this report explores what a viable governance model could look like to allow different stakeholders to participate successfully in the ODP, despite diverging interest and commitment levels, while ensuring ODP operation compliance in the existing regulatory environment.

The goal is not to go deep to define a suitable governance model for each UC with all underlying mechanisms in detail, but rather to provide a reality check that ODP governance for the Use case is indeed feasible.

We, therefore, propose one plausible governance scenario for each UC where possible. This serves as an additional input into the evaluation of the six UCs so that the final three UCs for the last phase of the project can be selected.

To this end, we follow a multi-step approach. The first step is to understand better how the different ODP services benefit (outputs, incentives) the various stakeholders and what resources (inputs) they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles (coordination) the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating (trust). Based on this analysis, we then propose what a possible ownership model for the ODP looks like, what legal form an entity operating the ODP should take, and how it should be governed to reflect the interests of all critical stakeholders best. Finally, we examine how the regulatory environment in which the UC operates may have a direct impact on governance to ensure compliance and avoid regulatory complications.

3. Specification and solution architecture overview of the shortlisted Use Cases

3.1 Use case I: Electricity customer-centric ODP

3.1.1 Use case identification and scope

The Electricity Customers Centric ODP is designed to place consumers at the centre of the energy ecosystem by enabling smarter energy management, market participation, and seamless integration with Renewable Energy Sources (RESs). The platform provides real-time insights into energy consumption, allowing users to optimise their electricity usage, receive personalised recommendations, and actively participate in demand response programs. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as IoT, AI, and secure data sharing frameworks, the ODP facilitates automated energy supplier switching, supports engagement in virtual energy communities, and enables customers to contribute to grid stability by offering flexibility services. The platform ensures compliance with key EU regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS), while fostering interoperability through standardised data sharing mechanisms like Data Spaces.

The ODP enables two modes of interaction: automated control, where controllable devices such as smart thermostats and batteries respond dynamically to grid conditions while maintaining user-defined comfort levels, and manual control, where users receive notifications and recommendations via mobile apps. Consumers benefit from secure and fast verification processes, transparent billing, and the ability to charge EVs with green energy at competitive prices. Additionally, the platform creates or connects to a local energy market where users can trade power and flexibility services, enhancing the overall efficiency of the electricity grid. AI-driven forecasting tools analyze grid vulnerabilities and help mitigate power instability by leveraging demand-side flexibility. Through these functionalities, the ODP not only enhances consumer engagement but also reduces energy waste, lowers CFs, and promotes sustainable energy practices across the European energy market.

3.1.2 Actors of the Use Case

The actors involved in the conceptualisation of the ODP can be stakeholders, devices, or systems that trigger an action. The following Table 1 analyses the main actors and their actions in the UC.

Table 1 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case 1

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Electricity customer	Role	Residential, commercial, or industrial energy consumers who use the platform to monitor and manage energy usage	Monitor real-time energy consumption, receive personalised recommendations, participate in demand response programs.	GDPR, DLMS/COSEM, Green Button, Zigbee Smart Energy, ISO/IEC 14543-3
Energy provider	Role	Companies or utilities that supply electricity to customers and interact with the ODP	Provide billing information, dynamic pricing models, and integrate renewable energy generation data into the platform	MID, DLMS/COSEM, Green Button, GDPR, IEEE 1547-2018
Grid operator	Role	Manages distribution grid, ensuring stability and efficiency in energy delivery	Share grid status data, enable demand response events, and provide grid capacity insights to the ODP	IEC 61970/61968 (CIM), IEC 61850
RES producers	Role	Operators of renewable energy systems, such as solar or wind farms, that supply energy to the grid or directly to customers	Feed RES data into the ODP, provide flexibility options, and collaborate on integrating RES into the grid	IEC 61400-25 (for wind), IEC 61724 (for solar)
Platform operator	Role	Entity responsible for managing and maintaining the ODP infrastructure and services	Manage platform operations, ensure data security, provide system updates, and handle interoperability with other platforms	ISO/IEC 27001, GDPR
Third-party service providers	Role	Companies offering value-added services such as energy management tools, analytics, or IoT device integration	Integrate additional services into the platform, such as advanced analytics or smart home automation solutions	ISO 50001,ASHRAE 135 (BACnet), MQTT, ISO/IEC 30141, OpenADR, ISO/IEC 42001, ISO/IEC 20547
Regulatory body	Role	Government or EU-level organisations that define policies and ensure compliance with energy and data regulations	Monitor compliance with GDPR, energy policies, and market rules. Provide guidelines for data sharing and privacy	No

3.1.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of UCI is presented in Figure 4. Use case scenarios are explained in Table 2.

Figure 4 Diagram of Use Case I

Table 2 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case I

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.I.S1	IoT device integration	Customer installs a new IoT-enabled smart meter or device in the ODP	The ODP integrates the device, enabling real-time data collection and enhancing energy management capabilities	Electricity customer
BEG.I.S2	Real-time energy monitoring	Customer logs into the ODP platform	The platform provides real-time energy consumption data, visualising usage patterns and offering insights for optimisation	Electricity customer
BEG.I.S3	Demand response event	The grid operator sends a flexibility request to the ODP	The ODP receives the flexibility request and disaggregates it among controllable devices based on the agreements within the platform.	Grid operator
BEG.I.S4	RES integration	A new energy system is connected in the ODP	The ODP manages flexible resources in the virtual community to make the best use of RESs and prevent RES power cuts	RES producers
BEG.I.S5	Billing and transparency	Customer requests billing information	The platform generates itemised bills with energy usage	Electricity customer

			breakdowns, grid services, and cost-saving suggestions	
BEG.I.S6	Automatic switching of the supplier	Customer requests for changing the supplier	The ODP provides a fast and secure way to change the energy supplier	Energy supplier
BEG.I.S7	Recommender service	A potential grid stability issue is identified	The ODP identifies potential grid vulnerability and sends notifications to customers to react voluntarily.	Electricity customer
BEG.I.S8	Green mobility	EV owner decides to charge the EV with green electricity	The ODP helps EV owners to find charging points (CPs) supplied by RESs	EV owners

3.1.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCI are illustrated in Table 3:

Table 3 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case I

Challenges	Mitigation measures
Integrating data from diverse stakeholders (e.g., energy providers, IoT devices, DER operators) with varying standards, protocols, and legacy systems.	Use standardised data models and frameworks such as GAIA-X and International Data Spaces. Implement a middleware layer with APIs to harmonise data exchange and ensure compatibility across platforms.
Data privacy and GDPR compliance to ensure that customer data is collected, processed, and shared in compliance with GDPR and other EU regulations while maintaining data sovereignty.	Implement end-to-end encryption, anonymisation techniques, and role-based access controls. Provide clear consent mechanisms and perform regular audits to ensure compliance with data protection policies
Balancing intermittent RES generation with customer demand and grid stability	Use AI-based forecasting to predict RES availability and align it with demand response schedules. Implement energy storage solutions to store surplus renewable energy for later use
Platform scalability and manage increase data volumes and users as the platform expands across regions and integrates more stakeholders.	Leverage cloud and edge computing for scalable storage and processing. Design modular architectures to allow incremental scalability while maintaining performance
Encouraging customers to actively participate in demand response programs and adopt energy-saving behaviours.	Develop user-friendly interfaces with personalised recommendations and gamified incentives. Offer financial rewards or cost savings for participation in energy flexibility programs.
High implementation costs as the initial costs of deploying the ODP, including IoT devices, cloud infrastructure, and advanced technologies, can be prohibitive.	Leverage public-private partnerships, EU funding programs, and scalable technology solutions to distribute costs and ensure affordability. Pilot the platform in smaller regions before scaling up

3.1.5 Modular architecture specification

The architecture for UCI is designed to integrate data from diverse energy stakeholders, empower electricity customers, and support sustainable energy practices. It is structured into four layers, each with specific roles and functionalities to ensure seamless interoperability, security, and scalability.

Perception layer

The Perception Layer serves as the foundational component for collecting real-time data necessary for the platform's advanced functionalities. This layer integrates various devices and systems, including **IoT sensors, smart meters, distributed energy resources (DERs), EV chargers, and controllable loads (CLs)**. IoT sensors and smart meters are deployed across residential, commercial, and industrial settings to measure energy consumption, power quality, and operational parameters. These devices provide granular data that supports services such as energy monitoring, demand-side flexibility procurement, and energy efficiency optimisation.

DERs, including solar panels, wind turbines, and energy storage systems, contribute to production and storage data to enable aggregation and optimisation of renewable energy. This integration is particularly critical for the Virtual Energy Community Service, which relies on accurate DER data to manage green energy contributions effectively. EV chargers and smart appliances generate real-time data used by services such as green CP identification and flexibility procurement. The communication infrastructure relies on standardised protocols like Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) to ensure secure, reliable, and efficient data transmission between devices and the middleware layer, enabling seamless support for services such as automated supplier switching and recommender systems.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer acts as the processing and communication backbone of the platform, managing data flow between the Perception and Application Layers. This layer ingests data from a wide range of sources, including IoT devices, DERs, and external systems such as data spaces. Data ingestion ensures compatibility and facilitates the integration of high-frequency data streams required for real-time operations, such as flexibility capacity forecasting and local market mechanisms. To address the complexity of integrating diverse data formats and sources, this layer performs data normalisation, converting raw data into standardised models for consistent processing and analysis. Real-time communication is supported by a messaging broker that ensures scalability and reliability, enabling dynamic operations. The API Gateway provides secure access for stakeholders to interact with the platform's services while enforcing permissions and privacy policies. Data sovereignty and compliance mechanisms align with GDPR, ensuring that sensitive customer data and energy market information are managed securely. A Data Space Adapter/Connector enhances interoperability by connecting the platform

with external data spaces, such as Gaia-X, allowing for seamless integration of cross-border and sector-specific energy data. This layer is critical for creating a secure, scalable, and interoperable data environment.

Service layer

The service layer delivers an array of services to empower electricity customers, optimise grid operations, and facilitate the green transition. By integrating data-driven tools and AI-driven processes, the layer ensures seamless operation and dynamic interaction between stakeholders and the platform. Each service is tailored to address specific challenges in energy management, customer engagement, and regulatory compliance.

Automated switching of the energy supplier

The service addresses the complexities of changing energy providers in EU member states, emphasising differences in energy market structures and data regulations. Switching providers typically involves multiple stages, requiring manual intervention, which makes the process slow and costly. Efforts to automate this process face challenges such as the need to synchronise contract creation and termination across different stakeholders, including Transmission System Operators (TSOs), Distribution System Operators (DSOs), Metering Point Operators (MPOs), and Energy Suppliers.

A proposed solution aims to create a unified, automated system that enables consumers to switch energy providers within 24 hours, benefiting all parties involved while adhering to EU regulations. The platform will ensure secure, fast data exchange and comply with privacy rules. Key design questions include supplier participation, handling of electricity consumption data, and privacy regulations. Once these issues are resolved, the platform will automate documentation updates, with provisions for manual conflict resolution when needed.

Virtual energy community service

This service allows joining RESs and controllable devices to act as a single entity in the electricity markets. There can be different virtual communities at the national level or cross-border (if the regulations allow) that the end users can join. Joining this service ensures the end users that their electricity is from green sources and engages them in the green transition. The unpredictable changes in the RESs can be covered by the flexibility of controllable devices, considering the comfort of end users as the main factor to be considered. The whole virtual community can participate in the electricity market as a single market player and excess power production or demand of the community is traded in the day-ahead and intraday electricity markets. The transactions in the service can be done based on the bilateral contract between involved stakeholders or market mechanisms. In both cases necessary tools and algorithms should be developed for the communities.

Implementing this service requires some functionalities as below:

- Forecasting: to predict the output power of RESs and demand of CLs using advanced methods,
- Local market mechanism: for trading power in the community. This would require an AI-driven automated bidding tool for stakeholders and a market clearing tool,
- Bidding in the day-ahead and intraday market: for the excess power production of demand in the community,
- Settlement tool: for calculating the bills of the involved stakeholders,
- Green CPs identification: this service will help EV owners to find the CPs that are supplied by green energy and use them if interested. This would also increase the awareness of green mobility.

Recommender service

The consequences of the investment in RESs and electrification of heat and mobility sectors is the increasing grid vulnerability and the risk of cutting RESs' power or loss of load. The proposed service uses the historical data of the RESs and energy consumption in different member states and predicts the vulnerability of grids in specific member states or areas and sends recommendations to the customers that can have a positive role in reducing the risks. Forecasts and target customer identifications are performed using AI-driven approaches. The recommendations can be sent to the customers via mobile apps, or directly to the CLs via energy management systems (EMS).

Demand-side flexibility procurement service

This service is used to procure demand side flexibility of solving grid issues at both transmission (balancing) and distribution (congestion management) levels. The controllable devices that are connected to the service allow receiving flexibility requests from the ODP and react accordingly. This service needs some functionalities as follows:

- Forecasting the available flexibility capacity: Based on the responses received from CLs, AI-driven methods are used to calculate the aggregated flexibility capacity of all connected devices that should be submitted to the ancillary service markets.
- Classification of available flexibility capacity: Since distribution grid-level services are usually location-dependent, the existing flexibility capacity at different areas is assessed for use when needed. The regulations of member states regarding the collecting and sharing the geographical information of customers at the national or cross-border level should be considered.
- Flexibility procurement mechanism: This service disaggregates flexibility requests from TSOs and DSOs among controllable devices.
- Assessment tool: This tool assesses whether the connected device responded to the flexibility request or not.
- Settlement: This service settles the flexibility provision of controllable devices financially and includes them in customers' electricity bills.

Financial settlement service

Involvement in different services imposes costs and provides revenues for customers. A financial settlement tool is used to collect all the related information from different services and calculate the final electricity bill of the customers.

AI services

Since the ODP is highly dependent on AI-driven approaches, a service is defined for developing the algorithms for different services and improving them over time with the support of a data science team.

Data management service

Access to data is critical for the platform. A service is defined to manage all activities around determining the required data, data collection, communication, processing, and storage, receiving data from external data providers, and interacting with data spaces.

Business layer

The Business layer provides user-centric interfaces, operational insights, and compliance tools for all stakeholders, organised into functional categories.

Visualisation and customer dashboards: Interactive dashboards display energy consumption, costs, and renewable usage, empowering customers to make informed decisions.

Billing and settlement services: Offer transparent, itemised billing based on dynamic pricing models and track financial settlements with energy providers.

Reporting and compliance: Generates detailed automated reports to demonstrate compliance with GDPR, energy market rules, and renewable energy mandates.

User interaction services: Enable customers to interact with the platform through a user-friendly interface, accessing tools for monitoring, optimisation, and participation in demand response programs.

Holistic view and interactions

A critical interaction occurs between the Service Layer and the Business Layer, where technical outputs are translated into user-friendly dashboards, automated reports, billing information, and regulatory compliance tools. The Business Layer ensures that energy customers, market operators, and regulators can access relevant data in an intuitive manner, facilitating informed decision-making and seamless energy transactions. The User Profiling Component in the Business Layer customises platform interactions based on customer energy usage patterns, market behaviour, and flexibility potential, while the Identity and Access Management (IAM) component ensures secure authentication and role-based access to platform services. Through these interactions, showcased in Figure

5 as well, the ODP fosters transparency, automation, and efficiency in the electricity market, ensuring that customers can optimise their energy usage, participate in flexibility markets, and make informed decisions with minimal manual intervention.

Figure 5 Holistic interactions between the layers of Use Case 1

3.1.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 6:

Figure 6 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case I

3.1.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case I are illustrated in Table 4 below:

Table 4 Regulatory aspects of Use Case I

Regulation/standard	Article/section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Regulation (EU) 2016/679	Art. 5, 6, 25 & 32	Ensures that personal data collected from energy consumers is processed lawfully, transparently, and securely, obtaining user consent, implementing privacy-by-design, and complying	●

		with strict security and data minimisation requirements to avoid legal risks.	
Data Governance Act (DGA) - Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 5 & 11	Establishes the framework for trustworthy data sharing, ensuring neutrality in data intermediation services.	●
Data Act - Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 4, 5, 11 & 27	Governs fair access and sharing of energy-related data, particularly IoT data from smart meters and connected devices. The platform must ensure consumer rights to access their data, facilitate secure third-party data sharing, and comply with fair compensation rules for energy market participants.	●
Interoperable Europe Act - Regulation (EU) 2024/903	Art. 6 & 9	Focuses on cross-border data exchange and interoperability, complying with European Data Spaces standards, such as GAIA-X.	●
Artificial Intelligence Act	Art. 6, 8 & 10	The ODP falls under the High-Risk System. It requires the establishment of a comprehensive risk management system to identify and mitigate potential risks associated with the AI system, and it is mandatory to a robust data governance practices to ensure the quality, accuracy, and integrity of data used by AI systems.	●
	Art. 13 & 14	Transparency and Provision of information and human oversight. The ODP must implement the following measures: Document the design and operational processes of the AI components within the ODP and incorporate mechanisms that allow human operators to oversee AI-driven decisions, particularly those affecting grid stability and consumer energy management.	●
Electricity Market Directive 944/2019	Art. 12 & 13	Right to switch and rules on switching related fees; The ODP offers tariffs comparison and switch in a fully digital and paperless manner, but must ensure compliance with the 24-hour switching requirement.	●
	Art. 23	Integration with Smart meters and Energy Data access: The ODP can connect with smart metering systems to analyze individual energy consumption patterns and recommend optimal tariffs, helping consumers save on electricity bills. Through secure APIs, consumers can authorise the platform to access their consumption data, enabling precise switching decisions in line with Article 23 (Consumer Data Access Rights).	●
	Art. 15 & 17	Demand response and consumer participation: the platform, as an aggregator, allows consumers to participate in flexibility markets and respond to price signals. The ODP connects smart meters, home energy management systems (HEMS), and industrial control systems to optimise energy usage.	●

	Art. 32	Grid Stability & Congestion management: TSOs and DSOs can use an ODP to request flexibility services from market participants. The platform facilitates price-based incentives for consumers and prosumers to adjust energy consumption.	●
	Art. 16	Citizen Energy Communities: Establishes that CECs must have non-discriminatory access to energy markets. The platform allows EC to participate in all the electricity markets but also allows the sharing of electricity that is produced by the generators owned by the community, subject to other requirements laid down in this Article and subject to the community members retaining their rights and obligations as final customers.	●
Electricity Market Regulation 943/2019	Art. 16	Real-Time Trading & Peer-to-Peer Transactions: The platform allows households, businesses, and energy communities to trade electricity dynamically. Smart contracts can automate energy exchanges based on grid conditions and price signals.	●
Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001	Art. 22	Renewable Energy communities: The platform as an Energy Community facilitator complies with this article, enabling collective ownership and energy sharing through the ODP among others	●

Legend:

- Relevant, full compliance ●
- Compliant with potential risks ●
- Barrier to implementation ●

Conclusions

The evolution of the European electricity market has necessitated digital transformation to ensure efficiency, transparency, and consumer empowerment. The ODP presented in this UC as described is positioned at the centre of this transformation, facilitating consumer participation, energy sharing, and supplier switching while ensuring strict adherence to EU data protection and market participation regulations. The ODP aligns with key legislative frameworks, including the GDPR, Data Governance Act (DGA), Data Act, Electricity Market Directive (2019/944), Electricity Market Regulation (2019/943), and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II). These regulations collectively establish a legal foundation for secure data processing, consumer rights, market integration, and cross-border energy trading.

The ODP operates within a digital ecosystem where personal and market data are central to its functionalities. Compliance with GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) is crucial for protecting consumer data. Article 5 mandates lawful and transparent processing, necessitating clear communication about data collection. Furthermore, Article 6 requires

lawful data processing, ensuring explicit consumer consent before personal information is used. To enhance security, Article 25 (Data Protection by Design) and Article 32 (Security of Processing) impose obligations for encryption, pseudonymisation, and risk mitigation strategies, which the ODP must integrate into its infrastructure.

The Data Governance Act (DGA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/868) strengthens data sharing frameworks, ensuring interoperability and neutrality in managing consumer data. Article 5 imposes conditions for reuse by data intermediaries, requiring the ODP to implement transparency in data transactions. Additionally, Article 11 supports data altruism, allowing consumers to voluntarily contribute data for grid stability initiatives.

The Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854) further strengthens consumer rights regarding energy consumption data. Article 4 guarantees consumer access to their own energy data, ensuring transparency in billing and consumption insights. Additionally, Article 5 enables consumers to share their data with third-party service providers, fostering competition and personalised energy solutions. Moreover, the ODP must comply with Article 27, which sets legal requirements for smart contracts, ensuring that any automated transactions, such as energy-sharing agreements, remain legally enforceable.

Aligning the ODP with the EU AI Act requires a multifaceted approach that addresses risk management, data governance, transparency, human oversight, and cybersecurity, as it is considered a High-Risk AI system by the regulation. By adhering to these regulatory requirements, the ODP can operate effectively within the European energy sector, ensuring ethical AI deployment and enhancing consumer trust.

For this regulatory analysis, the ODP has been considered as an aggregator for what concerns the flexibility services, and as an energy community management platform and facilitator, so all its functionalities can be deployed with no regulatory barriers or restrictions.

The Electricity Market Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/944) lays the groundwork for consumer participation in the energy market. Article 12 guarantees that supplier switching must occur within 24 hours by 2026, a functionality that the ODP facilitates through automated, real-time digital switching. The platform ensures compliance by providing transparent price comparisons, contract details, and seamless transactions. Additionally, Article 23 mandates the integration of smart meters for personalised energy management. By connecting with smart meters, the ODP allows users to analyse consumption patterns, optimise energy costs, and participate in demand-side response programs.

The Electricity Market Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/943) extends consumer participation to cross-border electricity trading. Article 16 supports real-time transactions and peer-to-peer (P2P) energy exchanges, allowing households and businesses to dynamically trade electricity. The ODP enables automated energy contracts, ensuring

compliance through secure blockchain-based transactions. Moreover, Article 32 allows TSOs and DSOs to request flexibility services, which the ODP supports by aggregating consumer participation in demand-side response programs.

The transition to Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) is a cornerstone of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) (Directive (EU) 2018/2001). Article 22 empowers RECs to manage energy generation, storage, and consumption collectively. The ODP serves as an energy community facilitator, allowing members to trade renewable electricity, share grid resources, and optimise local energy flows. Similarly, Article 16 of Directive 2019/944 ensures that CECs have non-discriminatory access to energy markets, a principle embedded within the ODP's energy-sharing mechanisms and community-driven trading models.

Furthermore, the ODP promotes grid stability through demand-side flexibility. Articles 15 and 17 of Directive 2019/944 foster consumer participation in electricity markets with their flexibility, directly or through aggregators, while Article 32 of Regulation 2019/943 ensures that TSOs and DSOs can procure flexibility services. By leveraging AI-driven forecasting, IoT integration, and automated demand response coordination, the ODP aligns with EU regulations and supports the EU's objectives for a decarbonized and consumer-centric electricity market. However, since the flexibility markets, platform users, and the ODP's role as an aggregator have not yet been defined, further refinement will be needed.

The platform will be able to participate in the market as an aggregator following national legislation. The activity is possible and enshrined in EU regulation, but it is noteworthy that the figure of independent aggregators is still not a reality in all Member States. Similarly, the setup of each energy community will have to be done by the promoters of the community itself, following the specific national regulations.

With respect to cross-border energy trading, it is important to clarify that despite cross-border capacity shall be made available to market participants complying with the safety standards of secure network operation, it is traded at the national level by the System Operator and then integrated through the existing platforms Mari & Picasso.

In conclusion, the ODP serves as a catalyst for regulatory compliance and innovation in the EU energy sector. By adhering to GDPR, the DGA, the Data Act, the Electricity Market Directive, and RED II, the platform empowers consumers, enhances transparency, and ensures secure data sharing mechanisms. Additionally, it integrates supplier switching and demand-side flexibility, fostering a competitive and decentralised energy market. As the EU accelerates its green transition, the ODP remains a critical infrastructure for ensuring efficient, secure, and sustainable energy transactions.

With respect to the **national regulation** where this ODP is to be implemented, it is key to mention some of the regulatory aspects with respect to data and also electricity market participation in **Germany, Denmark and Sweden**.

Given the ODP's reliance on real-time energy data and consumer participation, data protection regulations play a critical role in its implementation. The GDPR sets overarching guidelines, while national adaptations introduce country-specific obligations:

- Germany: The Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG) mandates additional safeguards, such as the appointment of a Data Protection Officer under certain conditions [3].
- Denmark: The Danish Data Protection Act imposes stricter rules on processing national identification numbers [4].
- Sweden: The Swedish Data Protection Act aligns with the GDPR but includes provisions on processing personal identity numbers and credit information [1].

Moreover, the Data Governance Act (DGA) and Data Act require the ODP to ensure transparent, fair, and interoperable data sharing mechanisms while monitoring legislative developments in each country for compliance with evolving regulations.

Otherwise, the ODP aligns with national electricity market regulations to support automated supplier switching, demand-side flexibility, and market participation:

- Germany: The Incentive Regulation Ordinance (ARegV) incentivises efficient grid operations, while the Electricity Market Act (Strommarktgesetz) enables the integration of RESs into the balancing market. The Federal Network Agency (BNetzA) ensures non-discriminatory access to market participants and maintains the Core Energy Market Data Register.
- Sweden: The Electricity Act allows aggregation service providers to participate in the market, while the Swedish Energy Markets Inspectorate (Ei) oversees market integrity and regulatory compliance.
- Denmark: The Danish Utility Regulator (DUR) safeguards consumer interests and promotes efficiency, while the Danish Energy Agency (DEA) ensures fair competition and continuous energy supply.

Furthermore, the ODP supports Energy Communities, enabling collective ownership, energy sharing, and decentralised renewable energy production. Each country has tailored regulatory frameworks for these initiatives:

- Germany: Energy communities operate under federal oversight by BNetzA, allowing municipalities and local entities to participate in decentralised energy generation projects.

- Denmark: The Law on Promotion of Renewables and the Law on Electricity Supply provide the legal basis for energy communities, with the DEA and DUR overseeing regulatory compliance.
- Sweden: The Electricity Act governs the formation of energy communities, with the Swedish Energy Agency promoting energy-efficient investments and ensuring alignment with EU directives.

The promotion and deployment of cross-border energy communities to align with the Renewable Energy Directive and the Electricity Market Directive is challenging and faces numerous barriers, however, there is a notable example to mention in this analysis. This is the Bornholm Energy Island project, a cross-border energy community in Denmark and Germany, an initiative that aims to establish an energy island by 2030, capable of supplying green electricity to approximately 3.3 to 4.5 million households in both countries.

3.1.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCI. The UC relies on several advanced digital services that rely on resources provided by different stakeholders to deliver specific benefits to ODP users.

A suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met.

The table below provides a summary of the UC, highlighting its high-level goal, the advanced digital services provided by the ODP, and expected participant groups.

Stakeholder analysis

This section analyses the specific roles that the different stakeholder groups play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating. Starting from the proposed ODP services, the table below examines the relationship between the service and the identified stakeholder groups.

It is assumed that the provider of all ODP services is the ODP operator.

Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, others may not directly participate but still benefit from these. Stakeholders considered in this section include:

- TSO: Transmission network operator
- DSO: Distribution network operators
- RESP: Renewable Energy Sources Provider

- EEU: Electricity End-Users (consumers and prosumers)
- ES: Energy Supplier

The Table 5 below provides an overview of the different ODP services and the service users and beneficiaries.

Table 5 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	Service user	Other Beneficiaries
Virtual community service	ODP operator	EEU, RESP, ECs	TSO, DSO
Flexibility aggregation	ODP operator	EEU, RESP, ECs	TSO, DSO
Recommender service	ODP operator	RESP, EEU	TSO, DSO
Automated switching of supplier	ODP operator	ES, EEU	TSO, DSO
Internal operational services (data, AI, settlement)	ODP operator, EDP, DS	EEU, RESP, ES	TSO, DSO, DS

A more graphical representation of the stakeholder relationship with ODP and the resources they bring or obtain can be shown in the Figure 7 below.

Figure 7 Stakeholder relationship with ODP

Based on this initial analysis, the role of each stakeholder in the ODP can now be determined. Table 6 summarises their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table, and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 6 Stakeholders' role in ODP

Stakeholder group	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
EEU	End user of some ODP services	Requests and data for changing supplier, providing flexibility, and joining communities	To be supplied by green electricity, revenue from grid services

TSO/DSO	End user of some of the ODP services (Beneficiaries of the platform)	Price data, Grid service request data	Avoidance of grid congestion, increasing grid flexibility, procuring balancing services
RESP	End user of some ODP services	RES production data, Request to join the community	Reducing power curtailment, uncertainty in market participation
ES	End user of some ODP services	Request to join, Approval of supplier switching contract	Access to more cross-border customers
DS	Providers of some of the ODP services	Providing the possibility of data exchange with outside of the ODP	Enriching the data space catalogues, more data exchange, more money
EDP	Providers of some of the ODP services	Providing necessary data for the ODP	Benefiting from exchanging data with ODP and DSs

Finally, Table 7 below examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 7 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
EEU	They might be reluctant to share their data with ODP. Additionally, in some cases, there might be a need for installing new hardware, software, meters, and sensors in the buildings that will raise privacy concerns.
TSO/DSO	Complexities of dealing with demand-side flexibility, for instance, baseload estimation and assessment of flexibility provision may affect their willingness to collaborate with the ODP.
RESP	Some RESs have long-term contracts for selling their output power to the grid. For those RESs, there are not many incentives to join the ODP. If a RES is obligated to participate in the electricity market, then it can participate in the day-ahead and intraday market and adjust its bid in the market up to 45 minutes before real-time. Then there will not be much uncertainty to be resolved in the ODP. Additionally, the prices in the ODP should be in the range of market prices, otherwise, it does not make sense for them to join the ODP.
ES	No significant concern was identified for ESs.
DS	No significant concern was identified for DSs.
EDP	No significant concern was identified for EDPs.

Ownership and legal form of the ODP platform operator

The ODP platform operator will act as an alternative market player, addressing the gap between more prominent energy providers and users/providers of renewable energy with flexibility assets. Key service offerings towards them are the ability to set up virtual energy communities and manage their relationship with the energy grid and market, aggregating flexible loads and value-added services towards these end users.

End users encompass residential customers and businesses with whom the ODP platform operator will have a contractual relationship. Likewise, the ODP operator will interact with the TSO/DSOs through existing energy markets.

The operation of the ODP represents a considerable commercial opportunity. As such, it will likely be owned by a private for-profit entity with a commercial operational model. The services offered by the ODP operator are nationally constrained due to regulation; cross-border energy communities are fostered by EU legislation but face several barriers in their implementation. As such, it is likely that an ODP platform needs to be customised towards the national context they operate in. The owners of the platform are likely to operate an ODP per country/market. Over time a single entity could operate ODPs across different markets.

Relationships with the TSO/ODPs are based on exchanges through the respective energy markets in the different countries. ODP will have to comply with the rules and regulations of these markets, however, no additional regulatory oversight will be required. The overall governance model of the entity operating the ODP will follow commonly used ones for commercial entities.

The ODP platform will allow the creation of different virtual energy communities. Each energy community will likely be set up as a not-for-profit entity and follow governance rules agreed by the community. The community will have a commercial relationship with the ODP operator, e.g., pay an annual service fee to the ODP operator who provides the service and underlying infrastructure for the virtual energy community.

Regulatory governance consideration

The UC operates in a strong regulatory environment, cutting across sectors and territories. Therefore, the governance of the ODP needs to have compliance with relevant regulations at its core.

From a market participation perspective, different possibilities can be foreseen. If in the Member State independent aggregators are recognised and regulated as demanded by EU directives, the ODP can take such form to offer the flexibility services in the markets. Otherwise, if this is not possible or if considered convenient, the ODP operator can find an agreement with electricity suppliers of the energy end users that would be the market participants. In any case, the platform can help set up and manage an energy community and be part of it in some capacity. In this case, the energy community itself would be the market participant, following the specifications of the national regulation in terms of market participation.

An in-depth analysis of necessary regulatory challenges and compliance is provided in Section 3.1.7

3.2 Use case II: AI-Driven ODP for integration of EVs, ETs, RES, and grid

3.2.1 Use case identification and scope

The AI-Driven ODP for EV and ET Coordination is designed to address the growing demand for seamless cross-border EV charging and traffic management solutions. With the increasing adoption of EVs and electric trucks (ETs), it is crucial to ensure efficient access to charging infrastructure, optimal route planning, and effective grid integration of RESs. The platform leverages AI-driven analytics, real-time traffic insights, and dynamic pricing models to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of charge point (CP) booking, charging coordination, and grid flexibility services. By integrating historical usage patterns, RES forecasts, and traffic congestion detection, the ODP facilitates data-driven decision-making that benefits commuters, logistics operators, and grid managers. The dynamic pricing mechanism ensures that EVs and ETs are incentivised to charge during periods of high RES production, optimising grid stability while promoting sustainable transport solutions.

The platform supports both private EV users and logistics companies operating large fleets of ETs by offering automated scheduling and fair resource allocation mechanisms. AI-based routing services optimise charging schedules based on real-time grid conditions, availability of renewable energy, and the demand distribution across CPs. The integration with DSOs and TSOs allows the ODP to actively manage grid constraints by leveraging the flexibility of charging stations, mitigating overload risks while ensuring efficient energy distribution. Additionally, the platform ensures cross-border interoperability by aligning with EU sustainability regulations and promoting standardised data sharing practices.

3.2.2 Actors of the Use Case

The actors involved in the conceptualisation of the ODP can be stakeholders, devices, or systems that trigger an action. The following Table 8 analyses the main actors and their actions in the UC.

Table 8 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case II

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Smart meters and sensors	System	Devices that measure and record specific types of data such as energy consumption, voltage, current, and other relevant parameters.	Measure and record data from the grid, charging stations, EVs, and RESs. Communicate collected data to the data storage system.	IEC 62056, DLMS/COSEM
Energy Data Space	System	The data space that shares the energy data between stakeholders (providers, charging stations, RES) controls their access to the real-time and historical data on a day-to-day basis.	With the access hosted by an external FDaaS platform such as Gaia-X or IDSA, the following data is shared continuously:	CIM, OAuth 2.0, OpenID Connect, eIDAS, W3C, ETSI NFV, MEC,

		It handles real-time energy production, grid load, or consumption data to allow real-time balancing or demand response.	Wind and solar production (shared by RES provider), Grid load and pricing data (by energy provider). Requested EV charging SOC and booking periods Weather data	ISO/IEC 27001 and 20000, (EU) 2022/2065, IEEE P2413, NGSII-LD
Mobility Data Space	System	The data space that shares and controls access to the real-time energy data, energy production, grid load, and pricing data, real and projected EV charging SOC, and booking periods	With the access hosted by an external FDaaS platform such as Gaia-X or IDSA, the following data is shared continuously: EV charging station data, vehicle telemetry, traffic patterns, and route data (mobility providers). EV usage data (charging sessions, vehicle movement) and public transport usage (provided by EV owners for behavioural analysis). Real-time traffic data and vehicle fleet management data.	CEN/ISO 14827, ISO/IEC 15118, same as for Energy except CIM
(Public) AI-based Data Space	System	A miniature cross-border cross-sector data space that trades real-time pricing/load data for EV charging (predicted and measured by the platform for its EV parks and those managed by other parties).	The data space (either within the platform or on an FDaaS) manages access to the following data both generated by the platform and by the : 1. Price offered before optimisation. 2. Price paid by the end user. 3. Optimisation problem constraints. 4. Energy forecasts, pricing insights, and consumption recommendations. Data Provenance can be enabled depending on stakeholder willingness to identify within which DSO areas the aggregated load forecast and average pricing originates from, but	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) and ISO/IEC 19941, FIREWARE, IEEE P2413, W3C, OData Regulations (EU) 2022/1925 2022/2065 2018/1807

			without disclosing the data for individual EV parks.	
Charging points	Role/System	Physical equipment consisting of one or more charging station controllers and EV supply equipment managing energy transfer to and from EVs.	Communicate availability data to the ODP, receive control signals for chargers, process bookings, monitor usage and performance, and receive dynamic prices.	ISO 15118, IEC 61851, OCPP
EV/ET users	Role	Owners or drivers of electric EVs or ETs.	Register on the platform, share location data, receive charging offers, manage bookings, and receive invoices for services.	ISO 15118 (for V2G-enabled vehicles)
EMSP (E-mobility Service Provider)	Role	Companies that offer services related to EV charging, including access to charging networks, routing, payment solutions, and customer support.	Manage device registration, calculate charging costs, apply charging coordination methods, calculate flexibility, and offer it to ancillary service markets.	OCPP, OpenADR
CPP (Charging Point Provider)	Role	Operators of charging stations responsible for maintaining and managing the charging infrastructure.	Register CPs in the platform, provide availability data, receive charging coordination services, and process charging transactions.	OCPP, IEC 61851
TSO	Role	Entity responsible for operating, maintaining, and developing the transmission system in a given area.	Receive flexibility bids from EMSP, provide grid status information, and request ancillary services when needed.	IEC 61970/61968 (CIM), IEC 61850
DSO	Role	Entity responsible for operating, maintaining, and developing the distribution system in a given area.	Provide grid status and limitations, receive location-based flexibility offers and services from EMSP, and ensure stable grid operation.	IEC 61970/61968 (CIM), IEC 61850
Data Science Team	Role	Group of data scientists analyzing, implementing, testing, and deploying data-driven solutions.	Define data collection requirements, develop and validate AI-based forecasting algorithms and pricing mechanisms.	IEEE 7000 series (AI ethics and governance)
Renewable Energy Providers	Role	Companies or organisations that generate electricity from sustainable sources such as wind, solar, and hydroelectric.	Provide information about renewable energy production and forecasts.	IEC 61400-25 (for wind), IEC 61724 (for solar)

External Data Providers	Role	Organisations that supply additional data, such as weather forecasts, electricity prices, and traffic information.	Collect and supply necessary additional information to the ODP for use in forecasting and decision-making processes.	Relevant API standards for data exchange
ET Owner Companies	Role	Logistics companies that own and operate fleets of ETs.	Communicate ET data, destinations, and timetables to the ODP. Receive charging schedules and route planning services.	ISO 15118, relevant logistics and fleet management standards
Platform Manager	Role	Entity responsible for operating and maintaining the ODP.	Ensure proper functioning of all ODP services, manage data flows, and coordinate between different actors.	ISO/IEC 27001, GDPR compliance mechanisms, MQTT or Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)

3.2.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of the UCII is presented in Figure 8 and the description of the UC scenarios in Table 9.

Figure 8 Diagram of Use Case II

Table 9 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case II

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.II.S1	Real-time data collection	Vehicle connects to a charging station	The charging station detects the vehicle and begins transmitting charging status, SOC, charging speed, etc. to the IoT Gateway, which 1) adds it to edge training, 2) translates the data and sends it to the Orion Context Broker (OCB).	EV Charging Station, Energy Data Space
BEG.II.S2	Federated model update	Edge data is ready to be used for local update	The new edge data is used in federated model training. The trained edge model specifications are sent from the edge gateways through Gaia-X Federation Services (Gaia-X FS) to the central aggregator for global model update. The updated global model is distributed back to the gateways through Gaia-X FS.	IoT gateway
BEG.II.S3	Enforcing regulatory, security, sovereignty and compliance requirements on the EU- and member state-level	The data is passing between the edge and the cloud (from sensors, actuators, global model updates, etc.)	The data flows from the IoT Gateway through Gaia-X FS to validate the data and enforce data governance and GDPR rules, data minimisation principles, data localisation and federate data sharing policies, etc. After Gaia-X ensures proper access control and secure transmission, the data is then sent to the OCB for real-time context management.	Data Spaces
BEG.II.S4	AI-based energy production and consumption prediction	The algorithms are updated continuously	AI services are continuously validating machine learning models to forecast the production and consumption of renewable energy and EV charging schedules in each member state (Federated Learning). By using these predictions, EV supply equipment providers the platform can speculate on the price of the energy based on the amount produced and expected consumption. Additionally, the AI services aggregate the federated models to update the global AI model used to predict consumption and prices on the EU level to be used by flexibility services.	Data Science Team/Data spaces

BEG.II.S5	Dynamic energy pricing	Continuous, when the power production and consumption forecast is updated	Development of a dynamic energy pricing scheme to balance the supply and demand across different jurisdictions, minimising the impact of renewable energy's intermittency on a larger scale.	Data Team	Science
BEG.II.S6	Real-time analysis	Continuous	The Data Science Team continuously monitors the power balance condition in member states and the performance of the pricing and prediction algorithms to improve them	Data Team	Science
BEG.II.S7	Traffic anomaly detection	Continuous	Development of a monitoring service using AI to detect and predict traffic congestions and unusual patterns.	Data Team	Science
BEG.II.S8	Grid ancillary services	A balancing demand request is received from TSO/DSO by the Grid Ancillary Services	Grid Ancillary Services sends a request to the AI service (edge) to apply the imbalance to the pretrained model and receives the response with the optimal charging schedule and the short-term price for the period in question. The OCB forwards the optimised schedule to EV chargers. The short-term price is forwarded to the dynamic pricing service to be applied in the current booking service workflow.	Energy Space	Data
BEG.II.S9	EV charging network expansion	When optimal placement for a new charging station is needed	Considering the historical data, optimal locations for installing new charging stations are obtained and informed to investors.	Data Team	Science

3.2.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCII are illustrated in Table 10:

Table 10 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case II

Challenges	Mitigation measures
Grid impact and scalability of charging infrastructure: Scaling EV and ET charging networks across borders without overwhelming local grids is difficult, especially during peak usage times.	Leverage AI-driven demand forecasting to predict peak charging periods and optimise CP distribution, thereby reducing grid strain and ensuring a scalable infrastructure. Additionally, integrating RES helps balance peak load demands.

Data integration from diverse sources: Integrating data from multiple, diverse sources, such as EVs, ETs, CPs, and traffic systems, can lead to inconsistencies and data fragmentation, impacting decision-making.	Implement standardised data models and transformation mechanisms to ensure seamless data integration. Using interoperable Data Spaces (e.g., Gaia-X) allows data from various sources to be aggregated and processed consistently, enhancing data quality and usability.
Variability in RES availability: Intermittency in RES generation (e.g., solar and wind) can lead to mismatches between energy supply and charging demand, complicating grid management.	Incorporate RES forecasting into the platform to dynamically adjust charging schedules and incentivise charging during high-RES availability periods through dynamic pricing, promoting sustainable energy use.
Cross-border data compliance and interoperability: Diverse national regulations and standards make cross-border data sharing and regulatory compliance challenging.	Use Gaia-X and other data space frameworks to ensure secure, compliant data exchange, and integrate eIDAS-compliant IAM to enforce data sovereignty and privacy in cross-border transactions.
Traffic congestion and route optimisation: High traffic volumes and uneven CP distribution can lead to congestion, increased waiting times at charging stations, and inefficient routing for EVs and ETs.	Utilise AI-based traffic anomaly detection and route optimisation to manage congestion in real-time, providing dynamic routing options that prioritise charging availability and reduce travel times.
Complexity of dynamic pricing and incentives: Implementing a responsive, fair pricing model that adjusts based on grid.	Leverage AI to continuously analyse grid status, RES forecasts, and demand patterns, providing trustworthy real-time dynamic pricing and incentives to encourage off-peak charging and maximise RES utilisation.
User adoption and accessibility: Achieving vast adoption of the ODP across different user groups (e.g., ET/EV owners/drivers, logistics operators, and energy providers) is challenging.	Design user-friendly interfaces and dashboards that provide real-time insights on charging availability, route options, and pricing. Offering training resources and personalised features increases accessibility and encourages adoption among all stakeholders.

3.2.5 Modular architecture specification

Perception layer

The Perception Layer remains the foundational layer of the architecture, responsible for collecting real-time data from external third-party systems, including the **charging point network backend, user applications backend, vehicle (ET/EV) telemetry systems, traffic infrastructure, and renewable energy systems**. This layer captures critical metrics such as CP availability, charging session data (start/end times), drivers' and vehicles' location and geospatial characteristics, battery status, state of charge (SOC), traffic conditions for route management, and renewable energy production levels. All data collected in this layer is securely transmitted and ingested to the Middleware Layer using standardised or proprietary protocols such as MQTT over TLS, HTTPS, or custom APIs, aligning with EU data security standards like ISO/IEC 27001. The layer ensures seamless communication between physical devices and higher platform components while supporting scalability and adaptability to new data sources or evolving operational

requirements. For interoperability across diverse devices, a certification or onboarding process can help ensure that all data formats and protocols meet platform requirements. This layer provides foundational data essential for higher-layer services, such as routing, charging coordination, and grid balancing.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer is responsible for both data management and interoperability. This layer bridges the Perception Layer with the Service Layer, facilitating secure, normalised, and efficient data exchange. It plays a critical role in harmonising data from diverse sources while ensuring compliance with EU regulations and standards. The functionalities are described as follows:

Data Ingestion: Handles the southbound integration of data from external systems, third-party APIs, and IoT devices. This component ensures reliable data ingestion, supporting both standard and non-standard APIs to integrate seamlessly with external systems.

Data Normalisation: Data are ingested in different unified formats. This component ensures that data from different sources is transformed into a common structure based on unified data models. This harmonisation enables consistent processing and analysis, eliminating discrepancies caused by variations in source data formats or standards.

Messaging Broker: Acts as a scalable communication backbone for real-time data exchange and asynchronous communication. By generalising the previously proposed Kafka cluster, the Messaging Broker is now technology-independent and adaptable to different implementation technologies, supporting robust and high-throughput data streaming.

API Gateway: Implements the northbound interface of the Middleware Layer, enabling the Service Layer to securely access platform functionalities. The API Gateway enforces data sharing policies, manages user permissions, and supports standardised communication with external applications and services.

Data Sovereignty: Provides tools and mechanisms to define and enforce secure data sharing policies in compliance with EU regulations, such as GDPR. This functionality ensures that stakeholders can share sensitive data confidently while maintaining full control over how their data is used and accessed.

Data space adapter/connector: Facilitates interoperability with other data spaces, allowing the platform to ingest external data or share internal data securely. This component aligns with frameworks like GAIA-X, promoting cross-sector and cross-border collaboration through secure and trusted data exchange.

Service layer

The Service (application) Layer hosts the core services that provide operational functionality and ensure seamless EV and ET charging coordination, route optimisation, and resource management across borders. Key services include:

Data management and communication service

Access to data is essential for the success of this ODP. Required data can be from sensors and meters of CPs, EVs, ETs, and RESs, or other resources such as weather and price. If the data from EVs and ETs cannot be achieved directly, EV and ET owners can send the minimum required information to the platform using mobile applications. These data will be used for AI-driven algorithms, financial settlements of transactions, and so on. To ensure security and interoperability, the data exchange mechanisms must be aligned with data space concepts and use protocols such as NGSI-LD for IoT compatibility and OAuth 2.0 for access control. This service also enables communication between different actors using advanced communication technologies and the IoT. These technologies facilitate the real-time exchange of data between EVs, charging stations, renewable energy producers, and grid operators located within the EU.

Pricing Service

The Pricing Service calculates dynamic prices for EV and ET charging based on a combination of real-time and historical data. It uses inputs such as renewable energy availability, grid load, CP demand, and user-specific factors like charging duration and energy consumption. By applying AI algorithms to these inputs, the service determines optimal pricing that balances grid stability, RES utilisation, and user incentives. This computational framework ensures fairness, scalability, and alignment with sustainability goals, making the pricing system responsive to both operational constraints and market conditions.

AI services

AI-driven services can be used for the following purposes:

- Forecasting RES power generation: AI methods use different types of data received from data management services to predict RES power generation, which is used later for generating dynamic prices,
- Dynamic price generation: This service receives RES predictions and generates dynamic prices for pricing services,
- Identify commuter patterns: Analyzing the charging behaviours of commuters gains actionable insights from the processed data. This is done by cutting-edge machine learning-based profiling algorithms. This data supports charging coordination, dynamic price generation, and flexibility capacity calculations. To comply with ethical standards like **IEEE 7000 series**, this service is designed with transparency and data governance protocols.

CP booking service

As mentioned before, the platform can provide the possibility of booking CPs. This will integrate a booking service with the platform, facilitate joining the EV owners to the platform, and address the complexities of the flexibility capacity calculations of the platform for providing grid services. This service will also interact with the routing service to increase the efficiency of the platform and improve end user satisfaction.

Routing service

This service helps EV owners travelling and commuting, considering the access to CPs. Based on the data on the installed CPs, the booked CPs by the booking service, the SOC of the battery of the EV, and commuters' patterns obtained from AI services, it can estimate the availability of CPs and suggest an optimal route for travelling.

This service would also be very useful for companies that own ETs to deliver their goods based on their timetable as much as possible, considering other similar companies and EV owners' demand. Of course, the level of access that companies can provide for the platform would affect the success of providing solutions.

Charging coordination service

Based on the booked CPs, predictions on the RESs, prices, and behaviour of commuters, EV and ET specific requirements (minimum favourite SOC and timetables), and grid limitations received from DSO to TSO, the ODP can use advanced methods to schedule the charging of EVs and ETs in the platform. In case the ODP is going to provide the balancing service for the grid, it should also calculate the flexibility capacity to bid in the balancing market and consider it in the coordination problem. This service provides relevant and effective recommendations to optimise the charging behaviour according to the commuters' travel patterns along domestic and long-distance routes while ensuring consistency of service for EV owners in different member states.

Additionally, together with dynamic pricing service and balancing service, this service helps to ensure the balancing of supply and demand across different jurisdictions, minimising the impact of renewable energy's intermittency on a larger scale. This includes calculating EV charging schedules that ensure efficient utilisation of surplus RES production.

Flexibility service

This service includes three main sub-services as follows:

- Calculating the flexibility capacity: This sub-service calculates the available flexibility capacity considering booked CPs and ETs' and EVs' requirements, e.g., minimum favourite SOC at the end of the charging period and timetables,
- Bidding flexibility: This sub-service takes care of bidding calculated flexibility capacity to the balancing market,
- Control and assessment: This sub-service is responsible for receiving flexibility requests from the grid, sending control signals to CPs with available flexibility

capacity, and assessing the performance of the platform in providing the service and sending the information of devices collaborating in the grid service to the financial settlement service.

Financial settlement service

Facilitates secure, transparent financial transactions related to charging fees, dynamic pricing adjustments, and grid services, ensuring efficient and compliant settlement for cross-border operations by aligning with PSD2 (Payment Service Directive).

Each of these services operates in synergy to provide a comprehensive set of tools for efficient EV and ET operations, from real-time route planning and CP access to dynamic energy pricing and secure financial transactions. The way they are correlated and interconnected is depicted in the architecture scheme of the next section.

Blockchain

The blockchain component ensures secure and immutable recording of transactions related to charging, grid interactions, and financial settlements. It supports mainly services like the Financial Settlement Service, providing transparency and trust for payments, and the Flexibility Service, where blockchain tracks energy usage and resource contributions.

Business layer

The business layer provides stakeholders with intuitive tools for monitoring, decision-making, and regulatory compliance, ensuring they can interact effectively with the platform and access actionable insights. Key Performance Indicator (KPI) dashboards and visualisation displays KPIs relevant to each stakeholder, such as CP usage rates, traffic flow data, and RES integration. These visualisations enable quick assessments of system status and operational efficiency while complying with GDPR and data privacy standards. These visualisations allow for quick assessment of system status and operational efficiency. In addition, the Business Layer includes user profiles and settlement management functions. These features enable customised experiences for different users, including EV drivers, logistics operators, and CP providers, allowing them to manage their profiles, track usage, and monitor financial transactions. To streamline operations further, this layer enforces business rules and logic that automate workflows, such as charging coordination and dynamic pricing adjustments, thereby enhancing operational consistency and efficiency. Data integrity and transparency for cross-border operations are aided by blockchain that logs user transactions, CP usage, and regulatory compliance metrics, enabling stakeholders to verify financial settlements and generate trustworthy reports.

Holistic view and interactions

The Middleware Layer is vital for linking services like the Charging Coordination and Flexibility Services in the Application Layer with external entities such as grid operators

and energy providers, allowing for a dynamic response to charging demand, RES availability, and grid conditions.

Also, there is a dedicated EV/ET interaction microservice that provides users with an intuitive interface to interact with the system. Through this service, EV and ET users can search for available CPs based on their location, route, and charging preferences. The service allows users to view real-time CP availability, pricing, and estimated waiting times, ensuring informed decision-making. Once a suitable CP is identified, users can seamlessly book the CP through the platform, receiving a confirmation along with navigation assistance to the selected location.

Figure 9 showcases the abovementioned interactions:

Figure 9 Holistic view and interactions between the layers of Use Case II

3.2.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 10:

Figure 10 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case II

3.2.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case II are illustrated in Table 11 below:

Table 11 Regulatory aspects of Use Case II

Regulation/ standard	Article/ section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Regulation (EU) 2016/679	Art. 5, 6, 22 & 32	Governs the processing of personal data, such as EV/ET user location, charging behaviour, and payment data. For transparent data sharing, minimising real-time data and proper user consent to take AI-driven decisions.	●

Data Act – Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 3 & 9	Governs access to non-personal IoT data generated by EVs, CPs, and smart grids, ensuring interoperable formats and fair access to all actors.	●
Data Governance Act (DGA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 9 & 14	Facilitates data sharing frameworks, ensuring neutrality and transparency in cross-sectoral exchanges between energy, mobility, and AI-based services, shaping the ODP as a neutral data intermediary.	●
NIS 2 Directive – Directive (EU) 2022/2555	21 & 23	Mandates cybersecurity measures for critical infrastructure and digital platforms, directly applicable to ODPs.	●
Digital Markets Act (DMA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/1925	5	Ensures fair competition in digital markets, particularly where dominant platform operators may control access to critical services or data, ensuring equitable access for smaller stakeholders to data and routing services.	●
Interoperable Europe Act – Regulation (EU) 2024/903	4 & 6	Establishes interoperability standards for digital platforms across the EU, promoting seamless real-time data exchange across multiple sectors between systems of public administrations and private entities.	●
Digital Services Act (DSA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/2065	13	Emphasises transparency and accountability in digital services, including platforms using automated systems like AI-driven pricing and routing mechanisms.	●
eIDAS – Regulation (EU) No 910/2014	24 & 30	Provides the legal framework for secure electronic identification and trust services, necessary for user authentication and secure data sharing.	●
New Network Code on Cybersecurity for the EU Electricity Sector – Regulation (EU) 2024/1366	Arts. 4 & 8	Sets specific cybersecurity requirements for the electricity sector, relevant for integration of smart grids and RES.	●
Artificial Intelligence Act		Classification of High-Risk AI Systems & risk management system. The ODP, which uses AI for dynamic energy pricing and grid flexibility, is subject to high-risk AI requirements. The ODP must implement a risk management framework that continuously monitors AI-driven charging coordination and pricing decisions.	●
	Art. 13 & 14	Human Oversight & Transparency Requirements: The ODP must inform users, charging operators, and energy market participants when AI is making pricing or energy allocation decisions. The ODP must have human-in-the-loop mechanisms allowing manual intervention in AI-driven actions	●

	Art. 51	Registration and Market Compliance: The ODP's AI systems must be registered in the EU AI Database for regulatory oversight. Failure to comply with AI Act requirements may result in fines.	●
Regulation (EU) 2023/1804 on Alternative Fuels Infrastructure (AFI)	Art. 20	Ensures interoperability and real-time data exchange for EV charging infrastructure.	●
Electricity market Regulation 2019/943	Art. 11	Dynamic electricity pricing gives EV users control over charging costs, incentivising consumption during periods of high renewable energy generation or low demand. This flexibility supports grid stability and maximises renewable energy use.	●
	Arts 13, 15 & 17	Aggregators bundle smaller consumers and prosumers (including EVs) to create market-ready flexibility resources. EVs under aggregation can provide balancing services, participate in demand-side response, and supply stored energy back to the grid via V2G technology. Smart charging enables EVs to adjust charging based on real-time price signals or renewable energy availability, reducing grid strain and optimising renewable energy use.	●
	Arts. 31 & 32	Deployment of widespread and accessible charging infrastructure is mandatory to support EV growth and their integration into the grid. DSOs and TSOs must ensure charging infrastructure aligns with grid capabilities and renewable energy generation patterns.	●
Electricity Directive 2019/944	Art. 17, 32 & 35	Integration of renewable energies and demand-side flexibility as promoted in the UC platform: Consumer Participation (art.17): Consumers can participate in all electricity markets by providing flexibility to the system via energy storage (including EVs), demand response, or energy efficiency schemes. Demand Response (Art. 32): Recognised as pivotal for enabling smart charging of EVs, demand response allows for the efficient integration of EVs into the grid, crucial for decarbonising transport. Network Development Plans (Art. 25): DSOs are required to include in their development plans the integration of renewable energy installations, energy storage facilities, and the electrification of the transport sector. This ensures that infrastructure	●

		planning aligns with the anticipated growth in renewable energy and electromobility.	
	Art 33 & 36	<p>Integration of electromobility:</p> <p>Development of Charging Infrastructure (Art.33): Member States must ensure the deployment of publicly accessible and private recharging points for EVs, facilitating efficient integration into the system.</p> <p>Role of DSOs (Art. 36): DSOs are required to cooperate non-discriminatorily with entities owning or managing recharging points, ensuring seamless grid connection. While DSOs are generally restricted from owning or operating recharging points to prevent market distortion, exceptions exist if no other parties can provide these services at reasonable cost and in a timely manner.</p>	●
Renewable Energy Directive	Art.20, 21, 23 & 24	Balancing markets, system operation, and EV Infrastructure integration: integration of EVs into the grid, enabling them to act as energy storage units that can supply electricity back to the grid, providing grid stability and flexibility, and facilitating the incorporation of RESs. DSOs and TSOs to facilitate the integration of distributed renewable energy and the integration of EV charging infrastructure	●
Energy Efficiency Directive	Art. 15 & 17	<p>EVs and Smart Charging: Smart charging systems to optimise grid usage.</p> <p>Promotes EVs as flexible energy assets that can adjust charging schedules or feed energy back into the grid. Member States to enable consumers and businesses to adjust their energy usage in response to market signals (e.g., price changes, renewable energy availability).</p>	●
	Art. 22 & 25	Innovation in energy efficiency technologies, including those for EV integration and energy management. Member States are called to develop markets for energy services, enabling private and public entities to provide solutions such as optimised energy use for EVs, energy storage management, and smart charging services.	●
Regulation (EU) 2023/1804 on Alternative Fuels Infrastructure (AFI)	Art. 3	CPs for light-duty EVs. Deployment must align with EV fleet growth in each Member State and include recharging points spaced no more than 60 km apart along the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T). Both normal-power and fast-charging options are required to cater to diverse user needs. Urban areas must also have sufficient infrastructure to meet residential and commercial demands. While private	●

		investment is prioritised, public support is encouraged in areas with insufficient market-driven solutions.	
	Art. 4	CPs for heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs). Recharging points must be spaced no more than 60 km apart on core TEN-T networks and 100 km on comprehensive networks, with high-power options for quick charging. Urban and overnight facilities are required to support logistics and long-haul travel, with progressive implementation from 2025 to full deployment by 2030. Collaboration with private stakeholders is encouraged to fund and expand infrastructure deployment.	●
	Art. 5	The Use case platform must provide the following: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ad Hoc Recharging and Payment Options: Payments must be possible via widely used instruments in the EU, A single payment terminal can serve multiple points in a pool. 2. Opt-Out from Automatic Authentication. 3. Pricing Transparency and Non-Discrimination (Price per kWh). All pricing details must be accessible prior to charging. 	●
	Art. 14 and 15	National policy frameworks & National reporting: Art. 14.2 (h) the deployment and operation of recharging points, including the geographical distribution of bidirectional recharging points, contribute to the flexibility of the energy system and to the penetration of renewable electricity into the electric system. The ODP presented in this UC provides a full alignment. Art.15.3 Member States must evaluate how the deployment and operation of recharging points can enhance EVs' contribution to the flexibility of the energy system, including the participation of EVs in the balancing markets, and the assessment of the inclusion of smart charging points (V2G). Art. 15.4 TSOs and DSOs must input on the potential contribution of bidirectional recharging to reducing user and system costs and increasing the renewable electricity share in the electricity system.	●

Legenda:

- Relevant, full compliance ●
- Compliant with potential risks ●
- Barrier to implementation ●

Conclusions

The platform operates in strict adherence to the GDPR, ensuring transparency, security, and fairness in handling personal data such as EV user locations, charging behaviours, and payment details. Core principles under Article 5—such as purpose limitation and data minimisation—guide the lawful and secure processing of personal data. For instance, charging behaviours and route preferences are processed exclusively for coordination and pricing optimisation purposes. Consent mechanisms compliant with Article 6 ensure explicit user agreement for data collection and profiling. Advanced cybersecurity measures, including encryption and access controls required under Article 32, safeguard user data against breaches, building trust among stakeholders.

The platform aligns with the Data Act (EU 2023/2854) by facilitating interoperable data access for stakeholders, such as EMSPs and logistics operators, under Article 3. It ensures that smaller players in the market have equal access to critical charging and operational data, preventing monopolistic practices and ensuring compliance with the fair contract requirements of Article 9. Additionally, as a neutral data intermediary under the Data Governance Act (DGA), the platform adheres to Article 9, enabling equitable data exchanges between DSOs, CPPs, and other entities. It also supports the innovative reuse of anonymised public sector data for optimising grid operations and dynamic pricing, as permitted under Article 14.

To reinforce operational integrity, the platform implements the robust cybersecurity frameworks mandated by the NIS 2 Directive (EU 2022/2555). Following Article 21, multi-factor authentication, encryption, and incident reporting mechanisms are embedded into its systems, protecting sensitive energy and user data from potential cyber threats. These measures position the platform as a trusted operator in the EU's critical energy infrastructure.

The ODP integrates high-risk AI applications in energy and EV charging, requiring strict compliance with the **European Artificial Intelligence Act**. Compliance with Articles 6, 9, 13, 14, and 51 ensures transparency, fairness, cybersecurity, and regulatory oversight. Implementing risk mitigation, human oversight, and cybersecurity frameworks will enable legal operation and market trust in AI-driven EV and energy systems.

In compliance with the Electricity Market Regulation (EU 2019/943), the platform integrates EVs as active participants in the energy market. By offering dynamic electricity pricing as outlined in Article 11, the platform empowers EV users to optimise charging costs, incentivising off-peak charging during renewable energy surpluses. This aligns consumer behaviour with grid demands, enhancing stability while maximising renewable energy utilisation. Aggregators, supported under Article 13, bundle flexibility resources, enabling EVs to provide balancing services, participate in demand response schemes, and supply stored energy back to the grid via vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology.

Smart and bi-directional charging, emphasised in Articles 15 and 17, is integral to the platform's functionality. These capabilities allow EVs to dynamically adjust charging schedules based on real-time price signals and renewable energy availability, reducing grid strain and optimising resource utilisation. To support the electrification of transport, the platform ensures the deployment of accessible charging infrastructure, in line with Articles 31 and 32, aligning with grid capabilities and consumer needs.

Through the Electricity Directive (EU 2019/944), the platform supports the seamless integration of electromobility. Article 33 ensures widespread deployment of private and public recharging points, while Article 36 mandates DSO collaboration to ensure seamless grid connections for charging infrastructure. By coordinating with DSOs and TSOs, the platform helps integrate renewable energy and avoids market distortions.

The platform meets the ambitious targets of the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (EU 2023/1804) by deploying charging solutions for light- and heavy-duty vehicles. Articles 3 and 4 define distance- and fleet-based targets for recharging infrastructure along the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T), ensuring accessibility and efficiency. The platform offers both normal-power and high-power recharging options, catering to diverse user needs. Urban and long-distance recharging needs are addressed with progressive timelines set for 2025 to 2030, promoting electrification across freight and personal transport sectors.

Pricing transparency, detailed in Article 5, ensures that EV users can easily compare costs, access ad hoc charging without contracts, and benefit from standardised payment options. The platform supports bidirectional recharging, enabling V2G services to stabilise the grid and enhance renewable energy penetration. Articles 14 and 15 further emphasise the importance of integrating charging infrastructure into national policy frameworks and assessing its contribution to grid flexibility and renewable energy adoption.

With respect to the regulatory analysis **at the national level**, the platform will be able to participate in the market as an aggregator following national legislation. The activity is possible and enshrined in EU regulation, but it is noteworthy that the figure of independent aggregators is still not a reality in all Member States. The UC reference countries, Austria, Slovenia, and Hungary, are totally aligned with the European regulations analysed above, and it is certain that there are no regulatory barriers for this UC ODP to operate as presented.

Hungary

Hungary's approach to EV charging station regulation combines strict data protection measures with provisions for energy market participation. The GDPR serves as the cornerstone for data handling, with Hungary's Act CXII of 2011 enhancing transparency and enforcing lawful data processing. This act imposes stricter obligations for obtaining

consent and emphasises user rights in AI-driven decisions. Additionally, the eIDAS Regulation, adopted through Government Decree 451/2016, ensures secure electronic transactions, supporting digital interoperability for charging platforms.

From an energy market perspective, the Act LXXXVI of 2007 on Electricity governs the operation of EV charging stations. These stations are recognised as eligible market participants if they meet grid access and licensing requirements. They may procure electricity directly from the wholesale market or generate their own through RESs, such as on-site solar panels. Furthermore, the act encourages collaboration with aggregators, allowing charging stations to participate in demand response and balancing markets. The Hungarian Energy and Public Utility Regulatory Authority (HEA) oversees these activities, ensuring compliance and promoting fair market practices.

Austria

Austria integrates its regulatory frameworks with EU directives to promote renewable energy and decentralised energy trading for EV charging stations. The GDPR, reinforced by the Datenschutzgesetz (DSG), mandates risk-based measures for handling sensitive data. Austria also incorporates the Data Act and Federal Telecommunications Act (TKG) to ensure interoperability and fairness in data contracts, facilitating seamless interactions between market participants.

The Renewable Energy Expansion Act (European Air Group (EAG) 2021) and the Electricity Industry and Organisation Act (EIWOG 2010) underpin Austria's regulatory approach to EV charging stations. These laws encourage the integration of renewable energy into charging infrastructure and support P2P initiatives, enabling private CPs to participate in decentralised energy trading. Additionally, the Smart Meter Regulation (IME-VO) facilitates real-time energy monitoring, ensuring transparent and dynamic pricing for P2P transactions. Together, these measures create a market environment that prioritises renewable energy use and consumer empowerment.

Slovenia

Slovenia's regulatory framework emphasises renewable energy integration and market participation for EV charging stations. Under the GDPR, Slovenia's ZVOP-1 outlines strict consent rules, transparency in data processing, and additional safeguards against automated decisions. The eIDAS Regulation, implemented as Zakon o elektronskem poslovanju, ensures secure and interoperable electronic transactions, which are vital for digital charging platforms.

The Slovenian Energy Act (EZ-1) implements EU energy directives at the national level, allowing EV charging stations to directly procure electricity from the wholesale market. Operators may enter into Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) or trade on Slovenia's electricity market platform, Borzen. The act also facilitates participation in flexibility and balancing markets, enabling charging stations to contribute stored or generated energy

to grid services. Compliance with grid connection regulations, overseen by the Slovenian Energy Agency, is mandatory. The Decree on RESs further supports EV charging stations by regulating renewable energy use and encouraging them to act as both energy generators and consumers.

3.2.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCII. The governance model analysis explores what a viable governance model could look like to allow different stakeholders to participate successfully in the ODP despite diverging interest and commitment levels, while ensuring ODP operation compliance in the existing regulatory environment.

UCII aims to improve efficiency, reduce congestion, and optimise traffic management by integrating EVs, ETs, RES, and the grid into an ODP, benefiting stakeholders through shared resources. A suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met.

Stakeholder analysis

A first step in the governance model analysis is to better understand how the different ODP services benefit the various stakeholders and what resources they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating.

The Table 12 below captures the relationship between the proposed ODP services and identified stakeholders.

The stakeholders considered in this analysis were:

- Electric Vehicle (EV)/Electric Truck (ET) Users
- EMSP: E-Mobility Service Provider
- CPP: Charging Point Provider
- Data Science Team
- TSO: Transmission Network Operators
- DSO: Distribution Network Operators
- Renewable Energy Providers
- External Data Providers
- Electric Truck (ET) Owner Companies
- ODP Operator

It is assumed that the ODP operator provides all services as part of the ODP. Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, while others may not directly participate but still benefit from them.

Table 12 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	End user	Beneficiaries
CP booking service	ODP operator	EV/ET users, ET owner companies	CPP, EMSP, RES provider, TSO, DSO
Pricing services	ODP operator	EV/ET users, ET owner companies, EMSP	CPP, RES provider, TSO, DSO
Charging coordination service	ODP operator	EV/ET users, ET owner companies, EMSP	RES providers, DSO, TSO, CPP, data science team
Flexibility services	ODP operator	RES providers, EV/ET users, ET owner companies, EMSP, CPP	TSO, DSO, EV/ET users
Routing service	ODP operator	EV/ET users, ET owner companies	EMSP, CPP, TSO, DSO, External data providers

Based on this initial analysis, the role that each stakeholder plays in the ODP can now be determined. Table 13 shows their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 13 Stakeholders' role in ODP

Stakeholder	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
Data science team	Beneficiary	Data analysis, optimisation	Development of valuable algorithms and models, contribution to cutting-edge e-mobility solution
TSO	End user of some of the ODP services	Grid data, tariff formation data	Improved grid stability, reduced grid congestion, enhanced forecasting of electricity demand
DSO	End user for some services; beneficiary	Local grid management	Better local grid stability and grid management, reduced voltage fluctuations
EMSP	End user for some services; beneficiary	Charging services, billing	Optimised charging network utilisation
CPP	End user for some services; beneficiary	Charging infrastructure and stations	Reduced operational costs, attract more customers, increased utilisation of charging infrastructure
Renewable Energy Providers	End user for some services; beneficiary	Generation facilities and output	Improved grid integration of RES, more predictable energy demand patterns

External data providers	Beneficiary	Data infrastructure, traffic/weather information, data distribution	Increased demand for their data services
ET owner companies	End user for some services; beneficiary	Fleet location data, operational data, and charging schedules	Reduced operating costs, improved fleet efficiency, reduced downtime
EV/ET users	End user of some services; beneficiary	Charging fees and sessions	Reduced charging cost, improved charging availability, and reduced waiting times

Finally, the Table 14 below examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 14 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
TSO/DSO	May have concerns about the impact of large-scale EV/ET charging on grid stability and about the platform's ability to accurately predict and manage demand.
Data science team	May have concerns regarding compliance with cross-border regulations and data privacy laws and about liability in case of system failures or security breaches.
EMSP	May be concerned about difficulties with integrating with various CPPs and charging infrastructure and concerns about grid stability.
CPP	May be concerned about the impact of widespread EV charging on the electricity grid.
Renewable Energy Providers	May have concerns about grid's ability to manage fluctuating renewable energy supply.
External data providers	May have concerns regarding compliance with cross-border regulations, data privacy laws and data interoperability.
ET owner companies	May have concerns regarding compliance with cross-border regulations, operational range, and integration with fleet management systems.
EV/ET users	May have concerns about charging infrastructure availability and accessibility, charging speed/convenience, and interoperability.

Ownership and legal form of ODP platform operator

The main stakeholders in the UC are utilities, CPOs, smart charging operators, and ET/EV fleet operators.

TSOs and DSOs can benefit from ODP participation by gaining operational data and load-balancing opportunities to increase the operational stability and efficiency of their infrastructure.

From the above analysis, the governance model would entail a private sector entity to operate the ODP, alternatively, a public SVP (special purpose vehicle) would be governed by the consortium. This entity should be based in Europe and aligned with European values and ensure that the interests of participating parties are fairly represented and balanced, and that value flows proportionally to the contributions provided by each of its members.

The entity's overall goal is to ensure that its members can improve their sustainability while benefiting from lower operational costs. If the entity is operated as a commercial for-profit organisation, it would retain some of the benefits and limit the overall value of participating in the ODP. Given the overall addressable market in Europe, this is only a niche business opportunity.

Therefore, we suggest the entity to be a not-for-profit organisation providing the ODP as a shared utility for its members. Any revenue generated by the entity will be used to sustain the ODP operation and its evolution. These revenues could be funded by membership fees or through transaction costs.

Governance of this not-for-profit entity could be realised via more traditional means, such as supervisory boards elected from the member base that would adequately represent the members' interests. These boards could provide necessary oversight and control to ensure member contributions and value flows are in accordance with established membership agreements.

Regulatory governance consideration

The UC operates in a strong regulatory environment, cutting across sectors and jurisdictions. Therefore, the governance of the ODP needs to guarantee regulatory compliance.

The analysis of the ODP services from a regulatory governance angle identifies the following key areas for regulation:

- Cross-Border Harmonisation: Align EV/ET charging standards, pricing, and energy sharing regulations for seamless border operations.
- Renewable Energy Integration: Incentivise RES integration into charging networks via subsidies and preferential grid connections.
- Infrastructure Investment: Promote public/private investment in charging infrastructure, especially in border regions, to ensure accessibility.
- Data Sovereignty & Privacy: Enforce GDPR compliance for data handling, particularly in cross-border data sharing.
- Dynamic Pricing: Standardise dynamic pricing models to balance grid load and optimise RES utilisation.

A possible way to make regulatory compliance easier is to set up an advisory board consisting of representatives of key regulators to aid the alignment with existing national and European regulations and directives. While not actively involved in the supervision of the ODP, they can ensure that supervisory boards are equipped with up-to-date knowledge concerning any applicable regulations.

An in-depth analysis of necessary regulatory challenges and compliance is provided in section 3.2.7.

3.3 Use case III: Digitalisation of Data Centres

3.3.1 Use case identification and scope

The Digitalisation of Data Centres for Energy Efficiency and Waste Heat Reuse UC aims to enhance the sustainability and operational efficiency of DCs by leveraging advanced digital technologies. As DCs are among the largest energy consumers, optimising their electricity usage and integrating waste heat recovery solutions is critical for cost reduction and environmental impact. This UC proposes an ODP that enables DCs to function as cross-sector prosumers, participating in the EU energy market while also providing grid flexibility services. Through real-time monitoring, AI-driven analytics, and demand-side flexibility mechanisms, DCs can optimise energy flows, improve cooling efficiency, and support renewable energy integration.

The platform offers two sets of services: DC-related services for monitoring, operation, and planning, and grid-related services for flexibility capacity estimation, computational load transfer, and ancillary service participation. By integrating forecasting models and automated control systems, the ODP ensures that DCs minimise energy waste, strategically shift computational loads across EU member states, and contribute to grid stability. Additionally, the platform aligns with EU sustainability directives by facilitating transparent energy reporting, CF tracking, and regulatory compliance monitoring.

3.3.2 Actors of the Use Case

The following Table 15 analyses the main actors and their actions in the UC.

Table 15 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case III

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Sensors	System	Sensors are electronic components that respond to physical or chemical stimuli, that is, they detect variations in the environment in which they are inserted.	The sensors collect the data within the DC and external conditions needed to create the forecasts. The sensor data is provided to the data storage services where it is passed for further processing by the ODP/DC manager.	ISO 17025, ISO 5725, IEC 60751, ANSI MC96.1, IEEE 1451, MQTT, CoAP, OPC UA, Zigbee (IEEE 802.15.4), LoRaWAN, Bluetooth, NB-IoT, LTE-M,

				ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27701, ETSI EN 303 645
Smart meters	System	An electronic device that records information—such as consumption of electric energy, voltage levels, current, and power factor—and communicates the information to the consumer and electricity suppliers	The smart meters receive signals about the electricity price, electrical signals and parameters levels in DC and communicate them to the data storage, operation/testing and ancillary services to enable fast decisions for flexibility utilisation and forecasting.	MID, EN 13757, IEC 62056, EN 50470, EN 300 220, ETSI EN 303 645
DSO	Role	DSOs are the operating managers of distribution networks. A DSO has to maintain, both short- and long-term, the capability of equipment, installations, and networks to supply electricity continuously and reliably while meeting the quality requirements in force.	DSO determines the required services for the ODP and uses the ODP to exploit different grid and flexibility services.	IEC 61970/61968 (CIM), IEC 61850
Retailer/ Aggregator/ Trader	Role	Bids into the market on behalf of all data centres managed by the association.	Uses the platform as a decision support tool to bid on electricity market/provide ancillary services. The platform calculates flexible DC loads (primary from the HVAC systems and backup storage) that can be bidded independently of the tariff service.	EU 2019/943, EU 2019/944
TSO	Role	An entity responsible for operating, ensuring the maintenance of and, if necessary, developing the transmission system in a given area and, where applicable, its interconnections with other systems, and for ensuring the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable demands for the transmission of electricity.	Defines the requirements and rules for data centres to provide ancillary services. They primary use the price tariff calculation service to design new price tariffs for DCs. Look at the flexibility forecasts from their regional data centres (supported by DC associations), schedule proposed by the AI algorithms for transferring loads and propose a bidding scheme to their regional data centres.	IEC 61970/61968 (CIM), IEC 61850
Data Centre Association		The owner of the platform serving as an	Coordinates communication, agreements and data exchange	

		intermediary between data centres, the platform and TSOs.	between the data centres and TSOs. Monitors the platform performance usage and ensures regulatory compliance.	
DC Manager, including Data Centre's Scada and operators	Role	Supervise the overall smooth and successful operation of the operational scenarios	Performs tests on different parts of the digital platform. Ensures reliable communication between the DSO/TSO, sensors, meters, and the DC. Ensures that the DC system provides ancillary services within the agreed terms.	GDPR, NIS Directive, Directive 2009/125/EC, EN 50600, ISO/IEC 50001

3.3.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of UCIII is presented in Figure 11 and the description of the UC scenarios in Table 16. Data is received from sensors and smart meters and is stored in the data storage or directly used by ODP services. The rules and regulations for providing flexibility and the flexibility capacity that the DC should be provided are agreed upon by DSO and/or TSO. The DC manager uses the ODP services for planning, operation, and grid ancillary services.

Figure 11 Diagram of Use Case III

Table 16 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case III

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.III.S1	Data recording and communication	The measurement time interval is elapsed, measurement request is sent by the DC manager/ODP.	The data monitoring service receives the data from different sensors and smart meters, visualizes them, and presents them to the DC managers and TSO. The data is processed in real-time to detect anomalies and generate alerts if thresholds are exceeded. This ensures continuous monitoring and quick response to any issues.	Sensors/ smart meters
BEG.III.S2	Planning	A new device is to be integrated into DC, new control logic is required or a new regulation is applied in the DC.	DC/DC association manager configures and runs the planning service using digital twin based simulation and forecasting tools to decide which technologies, their configuration, and operation strategy would best serve the purpose of DC renovation/upgrade with objectives of reducing costs and increasing sustainability of the integrated solution. This service calculates the societal and environmental benefit for each EU location from integration of different technologies (e.g., hydrogen systems, innovative server infrastructure, storage and controllers), load transfer between member states and DC supply to district heating.	DC manager
BEG.III.S3	Digital twin development	Based on the results of planning and operational tests, the DC manager decides on the final configuration of the integrated device/control/constraint system.	The data centre manager works with a team of engineers to describe a recent design for control logic/device/constraint and integrate it into a digital twin for the updated system. This digital twin is used to simulate the operational behavior of the data centre under various conditions to ensure reliability and efficiency before actual implementation.	DC manager
BEG.III.S4	Provision of operation and	The equipment is configured and installed based on the result of	The operation services receive the real-time data, forecasted parameters, and status of	DC manager

	hardware testing	planning and management decisions.	different devices (UPS, EV charger, RES, energy storage, etc.) and schedule the operation of devices considering technical and reliability constraints applied on the existing and newly integrated equipment. The developed digital twin is tested with new technologies, and the results are evaluated from technical and economic perspectives.	
BEG.III.S5	Grid ancillary services	A grid service required by DSO or TSO	Considering the DC needs and status of the devices, a methodology is used to forecast the flexibility capacity of the DCs managed by DC associations for providing grid services. The ODP/DC manager offers the flexibility capacity to the TSO or DSO through the platform considering the rules and regulations and provides flexibility when needed.	DC manager
BEG.III.S6	Computational load transfer	Data from TSO or DSO is received	TSO or DSO can calculate the required reduction in energy consumption of DC to stabilize the local grid. As one of the tools for reducing the non-renewable energy consumption and avoiding congestions, the possibility of moving computational load to other DCs is calculated by this service	DC manager
BEG.III.S7	Price tariff calculation	Upon the TSO request	This service collects data from DCs and their price-responsiveness behavior and proposes a dynamic grid tariff scheme to encourage DCs to reduce energy consumption in critical time intervals.	TSO, DC manager

3.3.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCIII are illustrated in Table 17:

Table 17 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case III

Challenges	Mitigation measures
High energy consumption: DCs require a significant amount of energy for Information Technology (IT) infrastructures and cooling systems	Implement AI-driven energy optimisation and efficient cooling technologies.
Smart grid integration: DCs must dynamically interact with smart grids for load balancing and flexibility	Develop interoperability standards and deploy automated demand-side response systems.
Implementation costs: Investing in digitalisation and energy optimisation technologies can be expensive.	Utilise financial incentives, public-private partnerships and a phase-by-phase deployment strategy.
Real-time monitoring difficulties: Limited visibility in energy usage prevents effective decision-making	Deploy IoT devices for real-time monitoring and predictive analytics.
Regulatory aspects: DCs must meet various energy efficiency and emissions reporting regulations	Automate compliance tracking and integrate CF monitoring systems.
Security and privacy: Handling large volumes of energy-related data introduces cybersecurity vulnerabilities	Implement encryption, role-based access controls, and GDPR-compliant data governance.

3.3.5 Modular architecture specification

Perception layer

The perception layer is responsible for collecting real-time data from various sensors and monitoring systems deployed within the DC infrastructure. These sensors track energy consumption, temperature fluctuations, cooling efficiency, and operational performance of IT equipment. Smart meters provide detailed energy usage statistics, while IoT-based thermal sensors monitor heat generation and dissipation across different components. Power Management Units (PMUs) track electrical loads to optimise energy distribution, ensuring efficiency and grid stability. Additionally, environmental sensors assess humidity levels and air quality to support dynamic cooling adjustments. This layer acts as the foundation for data-driven decision making by ensuring a continuous flow of accurate and timely information to the higher layers of the architecture.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer serves as the central hub for processing, normalising, and distributing data collected from the Perception Layer. It ensures seamless integration between heterogeneous data sources and the digital platform managing energy efficiency and waste heat reuse. Data ingestion mechanisms capture real-time energy metrics and operational parameters, structuring them for consistency. Middleware components facilitate interoperability by converting raw data into standardised formats that align with industry protocols and regulations.

This layer also implements advanced data filtering and validation techniques to remove noise and anomalies, ensuring that only high-quality data is passed on for analysis. Secure APIs enable communication between the platform and external stakeholders, such as grid operators and district heating providers, allowing for optimised load balancing and demand response coordination. Furthermore, data sovereignty mechanisms ensure compliance with GDPR and energy data governance policies, protecting sensitive operational information while enabling controlled data sharing among authorised entities. The inclusion of distributed ledger technologies (DLT), such as blockchain, could further enhance security and transparency by providing an immutable record of energy transactions, waste heat utilisation agreements, and compliance tracking.

Service layer

The Service Layer delivers the core functionalities necessary for monitoring, planning, optimising, and integrating DC operations with external energy networks.

The **Monitoring Service** provides real-time visualisation of data collected from various sensors and smart meters, allowing DC operators to assess energy consumption, cooling efficiency, and system performance. This service ensures that operators have a clear understanding of operational conditions, enabling them to take proactive measures to enhance efficiency and stability.

The **Planning Service** offers simulation and testing capabilities within the ODP. It allows DC managers to evaluate the integration of new technologies, such as renewable energy systems, advanced cooling techniques, or alternative backup solutions like hydrogen engines. By leveraging digital twins, this service tests different configurations under real-world conditions, ensuring that new technologies meet both technical and economic requirements before full deployment.

The **Operation Service** is responsible for scheduling and managing the real-time operation of DC components, such as uninterruptible power supplies (UPS), EV chargers, RESs, and cooling storage systems. This service considers forecasted energy demand, device status, and reliability constraints to optimise the activation and operation of various energy assets, ensuring seamless coordination and minimal energy waste.

The **Grid Flexibility Service** enables DCs to contribute to grid stability by forecasting available flexibility capacity and offering it to the Transmission System Operator (TSO) or DSO based on predefined regulatory frameworks. Using advanced analytics and real-time measurement data, this service ensures that DCs can provide demand-side flexibility while complying with national energy regulations.

The **Computational Load Transfer Among DCs Service** analyzes the grid conditions in different regions based on information received from TSOs and DSOs. It evaluates the computational capabilities of different DCs and suggests strategies for redistributing

workloads across multiple facilities to mitigate grid congestion. This service helps balance energy demand by shifting computational loads to areas with excess renewable generation or lower electricity costs, improving overall energy efficiency and grid resilience.

The **Electricity Price Tariff (Network Charges) Calculation Service** assists TSOs in determining dynamic electricity tariffs tailored to DCs. This service analyzes the price-responsiveness of DCs, using methodologies such as the Flexibility Function, to propose tariff adjustments that encourage optimal use of flexibility services. Additionally, tariff modifications can account for the financial implications of computational load transfers, ensuring that DCs are incentivised to participate in energy optimisation efforts.

Business layer

The Business Layer translates technical capabilities into actionable insights for decision-makers, energy managers, and regulatory authorities. Interactive dashboards provide a visual representation of KPIs, enabling stakeholders to monitor energy efficiency metrics, waste heat recovery levels, and financial returns on energy optimisation investments. These dashboards offer real-time and historical data insights, allowing for data-driven policy decisions and operational adjustments.

Automated reporting tools streamline regulatory compliance by generating standardised reports on energy usage, emissions tracking, and waste heat utilisation. These reports facilitate transparency in sustainability initiatives and ensure alignment with national and EU-level policies. A customer engagement interface allows businesses, municipalities, and energy operators to interact with the platform, request data access, and configure energy optimisation preferences. This interface supports collaboration between DCs and external energy consumers, enhancing the economic and environmental benefits of energy digitalisation.

Holistic view and interactions

Also, there are dependencies within the layered architecture, especially between the Service and Business layer. The Monitoring service continuously feeds energy efficiency and operational data information into the stakeholders' dashboards, ensuring that decision-makers have access to real-time insights. The Planning Service provides predictive analysis and scenario evaluation results to the Reporting and Compliance System, enabling the generation of transparent energy optimisation reports. The Grid Flexibility Service and Computational Load Transfer Service provide essential data to the Financial Settlement Module, ensuring that energy market participation, load balancing efforts, and operational costs are properly accounted for. These integrated interactions ensure seamless operation, regulatory compliance, and financial sustainability, enabling DCs to contribute effectively to energy efficiency goals.

A graphical representation of the abovementioned interactions is illustrated in Figure 12:

Figure 12 Holistic view and interactions between the layers of Use Case III

3.3.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 13:

Figure 13 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case III

3.3.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case III are illustrated in Table 18 below:

Table 18 Regulatory aspects of Use Case III

Regulation/standard	Article/section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
Data Governance Act (DGA) - Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 5 & 10	The DGA establishes a framework to facilitate data sharing across the EU. The ODP must comply with it, setting conditions for reusing protected data, ensuring compliance with confidentiality and IP rights when handling DCs' operational data. Additionally,	●

		DGA applies requiring neutrality and preventing conflicts of interest in data transactions.	
Data Act - Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 4 & 5	Ensures that DCs retain fair access to data generated by their infrastructure, facilitating energy optimisation and computational load balancing. Data Act mandates that data holders must provide access to third parties upon request, meaning that the ODP must have mechanisms to enable secure and transparent data sharing between DCs and TSOs.	●
Interoperable Europe Act - Regulation (EU) 2024/903	Art. 3	Mandates that all digital services in cross-border operations adhere to EU interoperability standards, ensuring harmonised data exchanges between DCs and stakeholders in different member states. International Energy Agency (IEA) obliges interoperability assessments before deploying new IT systems, meaning the ODP must be tested for cross-border compatibility.	●
GDPR - Regulation (EU) 2016/679	Art. 5 & 25	The GDPR applies requiring data minimisation and purpose limitation to prevent inadvertent processing of personal data. If personal data is involved, the processing must be lawful, requiring user consent or another legal basis.	●
Artificial Intelligence Act	Art. 6	Classification of AI systems as high-risk-based on their intended purpose and potential impact on safety or fundamental rights. The ODP must assess whether its AI components fall under this category, necessitating stringent compliance measures.	●
	Art. 8	Obligations of providers of high-risk AI systems: including risk management, data governance, technical documentation, and conformity assessments. The ODP's AI functionalities might be deemed high-risk in consequence, adherence to these obligations is mandatory.	●
Regulation 2019/943 (on the internal market for electricity)	Art. 3	Competitive, flexible, and consumer-centred markets. DCs participate as prosumers , optimising energy use based on market conditions.	●
	Art. 6	Market-based balancing services & non-discriminatory access. DCs can offer real-time flexibility to TSOs, bidding into balancing markets.	●
	Art. 17	Demand response participation, including via aggregators. DCs participate directly or through aggregators, selling flexibility services. DCs adjust energy use based on dynamic pricing signals, reducing peak demand pressure.	●
	Art. 19	Capacity mechanisms for security of supply. DCs can provide backup power, flexibility, and capacity reserve services. In this UC, hydrogen and battery storage enable DCs to replace diesel generators and stabilise the grid.	●
Electricity Directive 2019/944	Art. 11	Prosumers & Market Access: The ODP enables DCs to manage the generation, storage, and sale of their own electricity, helping to optimise energy use.	●
	Art. 15	Demand Response Participation. The ODP analyzes electricity prices & promotes the shifts of computational loads, providing information for DC to adjust power usage based on price signals, supporting grid stability.	●
	Art. 16	Aggregator-Based Flexibility Services. The ODP facilitates collective DC participation, allowing aggregators to manage bids.	●
	Art. 18	Smart Metering & Real-Time Monitoring. The ODP collects live data from smart meters, ensuring efficient grid interactions. The	●

		ODP helps DC to optimise energy use with real-time AI-based recommendations.	
Directive 2018/2001 - RED II	Art. 21	Self-consumption & surplus energy sale. The ODP tracks DC energy production and automates energy trading ensuring optimal self-use and surplus trading.	●
Directive 2020/1791 - Energy Efficiency Directive	Art. 8	Energy audits & efficiency management. The ODP automates energy audits and suggests energy efficiency improvement by analysing DCs' energy use and recommends efficiency strategies.	●
	Art. 11	Demand-side flexibility & efficiency. The ODP provides dynamic information for DCs to adjust energy consumption to optimise grid interaction. The ODP automates demand response participation, optimising load shifting and energy use.	●
Regulation 1227/2011 (REMIT)	Art. 3	Prohibition of Insider Trading: The ODP ensures real-time, non-selective disclosure of DC flexibility data to prevent insider trading	●
	Art. 4	Obligation to Publish Inside Information: The ODP automates transparency reporting and ensures simultaneous market access to key operational data	●

Legenda:

- Relevant, full compliance
- Compliant with potential risks
- Barrier to implementation

Conclusions

The ODP enables DCs to act as prosumers in the EU electricity market, providing flexibility services, demand response, and energy trading. By integrating RESs, optimising computational load management, and collaborating with TSOs and DSOs, the ODP enhances grid stability and operational efficiency. The platform supports decarbonisation, digitalisation, and energy efficiency, positioning DCs as key stakeholders in Europe's transition to a sustainable and competitive energy market.

For this regulatory analysis, the ODP has been considered as an information point platform for TSO/DSOs and other electricity market participants. The ODP acts, however, as an energy management support platform for DCs and Data Centres Associations.

The regulatory framework supporting this initiative spans multiple EU regulations. The ODP must comply with data governance and security regulations to ensure transparent and secure data exchange. **The Data Governance Act** (EU 2022/868) (Art. 5, 10) and the **Data Act** (EU 2023/2854) (Art. 4, 5) regulate data access, sharing mechanisms, and third-party interactions, ensuring that DCs have full control over their operational data. The **Interoperable Europe Act** (EU 2024/903) (Art. 3) enforces cross-border standardisation of data exchange, critical for enabling DC-to-TSO interactions across EU member states. Additionally, compliance with **GDPR**, EU 2016/679 (Art. 5, 25) ensures data security and privacy by design, preventing unauthorised use of DCs' operational data.

In the electricity market, the **Electricity Regulation** (EU 2019/943) and **Electricity Directive** (EU 2019/944) define the market-based participation of DCs as flexibility providers. The ODP facilitates competitive and consumer-centred market integration (Art. 3) by allowing DCs to adjust consumption based on real-time market signals and engage in balancing services (Art. 6). It also enables aggregators to pool DC flexibility and bid into the market (Art. 17) while supporting capacity mechanisms that help ensure grid stability and reliability (Art. 19). The Electricity Directive (EU 2019/944) further mandates DC access to smart metering data (Art. 18) and demand-side flexibility participation (Art. 15), both of which are core functionalities of the ODP.

The ODP also aligns with sustainability and energy efficiency regulations, ensuring that DCs contribute to the EU's decarbonisation and energy transition goals. The **Renewable Energy Directive** (RED II, EU 2018/2001) (Art. 21, 24) allows DCs to self-generate, store, and trade renewable energy within Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), a function the ODP supports by enabling real-time RES monitoring and surplus energy transactions. Additionally, compliance with the **Energy Efficiency Directive** (EED, EU 2023/1791) (Art. 8, 11) requires energy audits and demand-side efficiency improvements, which the ODP facilitates through AI-driven analytics and automated energy management strategies.

To ensure market integrity and compliance with transparency regulations, the ODP integrates **Regulation (EU) 1227/2011** (REMIT) requirements. This includes preventing insider trading by controlling access to real-time flexibility data and market-sensitive information (Art. 3), as well as ensuring non-discriminatory disclosure of market-relevant data (Art. 4). Additionally, the ODP aligns with the Electricity Balancing Guideline (EU 2017/2195) and Demand Connection Code (EU 2016/1388), defining technical standards for DCs offering flexibility services to TSOs.

The activity of this ODP is possible and enshrined in EU regulation, but it is noteworthy that the figure of independent aggregators is still not a reality in all Member States.

With respect to the regulatory analysis at **national level** of this UC reference countries - Denmark, Germany, Spain, and Sweden - the ODP presents full compliance in terms of data, as the Regulations analysed in this section apply directly to the Member States. It is interesting to mention though, that the General Data Protection regulations at national level have been fully analysed (Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de 5 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos Personales y garantía de los derechos digitales, Data Protection Act (2018:218), BDSG and Danish Data Protection Act) and that this ODP presents no regulatory barriers on this respect.

Otherwise, the functionalities of this ODP related to different energy services present no challenges in general, but as mentioned above, there are some market participants that are not a reality in all Member States. As an example, the figure of the independent aggregator, which has not been regulated in Spain, might encounter a regulatory barrier for DCs to participate in the Spanish electricity market along with this market participant.

In conclusion, the ODP aligns with EU regulatory frameworks and addresses national market conditions to enable DC participation in Spain, Denmark, and Germany. By ensuring compliance with data governance, market transparency, renewables integration, and efficiency mandates, the ODP provides a robust solution for DCs to contribute to grid stability, decarbonisation, and market competitiveness. Its adaptability to country-specific regulations ensures seamless market participation, making it a critical enabler for the sustainable digitalisation of Europe's energy market.

3.3.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCIII. The governance model analysis explores what a viable governance model could look like to allow different stakeholders to participate successfully in the ODP despite diverging interest and commitment levels, while ensuring ODP operation compliance in the existing regulatory environment.

The UCIII proposes several advanced digital services enabled by the ODP that rely on resources provided by different stakeholders and deliver specific benefits to them. A suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met.

Stakeholder analysis

A first step in the governance model analysis is to better understand how the different ODP services benefit the various stakeholders and what resources they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating.

The Table 19 below captures the relationship between the proposed ODP services and identified stakeholders. Stakeholders considered in this analysis include:

- DCs/DCAs: Data Centres or Data Centre Associations representing multiple DCs
- TSO: Transmission network operators
- ERA: Energy Retailer/Aggregators
- DHP: District Heating Providers
- DSO: Distribution network operators

It is assumed that the ODP operator provides all services as part of the ODP. Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, while others may not directly participate but still benefit from them.

Table 19 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	End user	Other beneficiaries
DC load prediction	ODP operator	TSO	ERA, DSO
On-site power generation and direct connection (import) to renewables	ODP operator	DCA, DC, ERA, TSO	DSO
Dynamic tariff calculation	ODP operator	TSO	DSO
Workload transfer between DCs – decision support	ODP operator	DCA, DC	
PtH Flexibility services	ODP operator	DCA, DC, DHP	ERA

Based on this initial analysis, the role of each stakeholder plays in the ODP can now be determined. Table 20 shows their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 20 Stakeholders' role in ODP

Stakeholder	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
DCs and DCAs	End user of some ODP services	Operational/ (work)load data	Cheaper energy, more sustainable footprint
TSO	End user of some of the ODP services	Grid data, tariff formation data	Avoidance of grid congestion, cost, and increase operational predictability
DHP	End user of PtH services	Heat pricing information	Cheaper/free heat
ERA	No direct involvement	N/A	More bidding opportunities
DSO	No direct involvement	N/A	Better operation oversight

Finally, Table 21 examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 21 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
DCAs	Should not have major reservations themselves, but instead work on resolving them for other stakeholders, in particular their member DCs. Emphasis needs to be given to balancing the influence of big DC providers with smaller entities, as well as old/existing and new/future members; incentivise DCs for sharing their data; agree with DSO on pilot testing conditions; and attract installation companies.
DCs	Reluctant to share operational data, installing sustainable infrastructure by themselves
TSO	May see a problem in handling uncertainty during the experimental phase
DHP	May not invest in low-temperature heating sources if they are not cheap
ERA	Working with relatively stable and large assets
DSO	May see a problem in handling uncertainty during the experimental phase

Ownership and legal form of ODP platform operator

The main stakeholders in the UC are European DCs and DCAs, who coordinate their data centre energy use and reuse through the ODP. Key drivers for their collaboration are lower operational costs and sustainability. By aggregating and better coordinating their energy demand across their data centres and cross-border, they can offer a key flexibility asset towards the energy market, which provides them with better bargaining power to lower their energy costs. They can also generate additional value with power-to-heat by cooperating with local district heating providers.

TSOs and DSOs can benefit from ODP participation by gaining operational data and load-balancing opportunities to increase the operational stability and efficiency of their infrastructure. These benefits can then be passed on as savings to the DCs and DCAs. ERA and DHP obtain more opportunities to access or exchange energy by participating in the ODP.

From the above analysis, the most likely governance model would entail setting up an independent private sector entity that is controlled by the DCs and DCAs to operate the ODP. This entity should be based in Europe and aligned with European values and ensure that the interests of participating DCs and DCAs are fairly represented and balanced and that value flows proportionally to the contributions provided by each of its members.

The entity's overall goal is to ensure that its members can improve their sustainability while benefiting from lower operational costs. If the entity operated as a commercial for-profit organisation, it would retain some of the benefits and limit the overall value towards participating DCs and DCAs. Given the overall addressable market in Europe, this is likely only a niche business opportunity.

Therefore, we suggest the entity be a not-for-profit organisation providing the ODP as a shared utility for its members. Any revenue generated by the entity will be used to sustain the ODP operation and its evolution. These revenues could be funded by membership fees or through transaction costs.

Governance of this not-for-profit entity could be realised via more traditional means, such as supervisory boards elected from the member base that would adequately represent the members' interests. These boards could provide necessary oversight and control to ensure member contributions and value flows are in accordance with established membership agreements.

Regulatory governance consideration

The UC operates in a strong regulatory environment cutting across sectors and territories. Therefore, the governance of the ODP needs to have compliance with relevant regulations at its core.

The analysis of the ODP services from the regulatory governance angle identifies the following areas for regulation as key concerns:

- **Cross-border data transfer between data centres.** ODP governance needs to ensure compliance with regulations such as GDPR and the Data Governance Act.
- **Cross-border energy demand shift.** ODP governance needs to ensure compliance with national regulatory authorities (NRAs) and the EU Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER).
- **Flexibility market participation.** ODP governance will depend on the nature of flexibility market (e.g., balancing, frequency, capacity, congestion, intraday) it aims to participate. Options for this could vary in different European countries. Participation will likely be through a grid operator (TSO/DSO) or an aggregator, which will enforce compliance with local regulatory requirements by contractual terms.

A possible way to make regulatory compliance easier is to setup an advisory board consisting of representatives of key regulators to aid the alignment with existing national and European regulations and directives. While not actively involved in the supervision of the ODP, they can ensure that supervisory boards are equipped with the up-to-date knowledge concerning any applicable regulations.

An in-depth analysis of necessary regulatory challenges and compliance is provided in Section 3.3.7.

3.4 Use case IV: Digital permits for drone-based inspections

3.4.1 Use case identification and scope

The Digital Permits for Drone-Based Inspections in Linear Infrastructures UC aims to streamline and automate the permit management process for drone operations in inspecting railways, power lines, and pipelines. Traditional permit approvals are slow, highly manual, and involve multiple regulatory bodies, leading to significant delays, especially in cross-border operations. This UC proposes an ODP that leverages blockchain technology, secure data sharing mechanisms, and compliance automation to ensure faster, more transparent, and secure permitting. By validating all legal and regulatory conditions in a single platform, the solution enhances safety, efficiency, and accessibility for drone-based inspections, reducing administrative burdens and ensuring regulatory alignment at the European, national, and regional levels.

The platform enables real-time coordination between air traffic control, environmental agencies, and infrastructure operators, ensuring that drone inspections are conducted legally and efficiently. By minimising human errors and automating compliance checks, the system accelerates the permit validation process, making drone-based inspections a viable, scalable, and safer alternative to traditional infrastructure monitoring.

Additionally, the interoperability of the platform across jurisdictions supports seamless cross-border drone operations, helping to improve infrastructure maintenance, road safety, and environmental protection while reducing operational costs and disruptions.

3.4.2 Actors of the Use Case

The following Table 22 analyses the main actors and their actions in the UC.

Table 22 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case IV

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Infrastructure manager (country A)	Role	National authority or the company responsible for maintaining cross-border linear infrastructure.	It makes the decision to carry out a drone-based inspection of a cross-border infrastructure. It generates the work order for a work operator. It generates the request with the drone operator and work order details (location, duration and specifications). It may receive requests to clarify some details or the final validation to carry out the inspection.	IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE 3801-2022
Traffic directorate	Role	National Authority responsible for road mobility	It receives requests from the infrastructure manager. It assesses the traffic impact of the inspection (if appropriate) and can generate an additional query for further details. It validates permission and prepares the operation to support the intervention.	IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE 3801-2022
Air Traffic Control Provider	Role	National Authority to regulate flights	It receives requests from the infrastructure manager. It evaluates the legal conditions of the request (licenses, restrictions...). It may generate additional queries for further details. It validates the intervention date and duration.	IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE 3801-2022
Other public authority	Role	Any other public authority responsible for getting permissions	It receives maintenance intervention requests. It evaluates compliance with National/Regional regulations. It may generate additional queries for clarification. It validates the intervention.	IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE 3801-2022
Infrastructure manager (country B)	Role	National authority or the company responsible for maintaining the linear	It replicates the request of Country A for National compliance of Country B.	IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE 3801-2022

		infrastructure beyond the cross-border		
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Referenced standards:

- IEEE 3205-2023 IEEE Standard for Blockchain Interoperability Data Authentication and Communication Protocol
- IEEE 3801-2022 IEEE Standard for Blockchain-based Electronic Contracts

3.4.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of UCIV is presented in Figure 14 and the description of the UC scenarios in Table 23.

Figure 14 Diagram of Use Case IV

Table 23 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case IV

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.IV.S1	Application request	The user generates a request for flight authorisation.	The application contains the flight details (drone, drone operator license, location, duration, estimated date...).	The infrastructure manager (country A)
BEG.IV.S2	Application validation	All the actors validate the flight application	All actors receive the application details and validate their specific legal and regulatory conditions.	Traffic Directorate Air Traffic Control Provider Other public authority Infrastructure manager (country B)
BEG.IV.S3	Application rejection	Some actors reject the application	Some actor detects that the application does not comply legal or regulatory conditions	Traffic Directorate Air Traffic Control Provider

		because the action is prohibited		Other public authority Infrastructure manager (country B)
BEG.IV.S4	Modification request	Some actors request additional information due to missing or unclear information or for non-compliance	Some actors detect that some information is missing or unclear or the application does not fulfil legal or regulatory conditions.	Traffic Directorate Air Traffic Control Provider Other public authority Infrastructure manager (country B)

3.4.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCIV are illustrated in Table 24:

Table 24 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case IV

Challenges	Mitigation measures
Regulatory fragmentation in drone operation across countries hinders cross-border inspections	Develop interoperable solutions aligned with EU standards and facilitate cross-border collaboration among regulatory bodies
Manual and slow permit review processes in daily inspections lead to operational delays in permit processing	Automate workflows using AI to expedite review and approval while providing real-time status updates to stakeholders
Complexity of multi-stakeholder coordination including regulatory authorities, infrastructure owners, and drone operators.	Use a unified platform with clearly defined roles, secure communication channels, and collaborative tools to streamline coordination.
Protecting sensitive data related to infrastructure and operations (data privacy)	Implement end-to-end encryption, role-based access controls, and GDPR-compliant data sharing policies
Cross-border data interoperability and interoperable data exchange across national boundaries.	Utilise data spaces like Gaia-X and standardised APIs to support seamless cross-border data integration

3.4.5 Modular architecture specification

Perception layer

The Perception Layer serves as the foundation for data acquisition, collecting real-time and static information essential for automating the permit management process. This layer integrates multiple sources, including **drones** equipped with sensors, **air traffic monitoring systems**, and **environmental data collection tools**. Drones collect **data on infrastructure conditions**, including high-resolution images and environmental parameters, while air traffic systems provide **situational awareness** by tracking current flight operations and restricted zones. Additionally, environmental data sources monitor the potential impact of drone operations on sensitive areas. The Perception Layer ensures secure and standardised communication through protocols such as HTTPS and MQTT, transmitting data to higher layers for validation and processing.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer acts as the core engine for processing, managing, and securely sharing data collected in the Perception Layer. This layer ensures the interoperability and consistency of data flows by employing data normalisation techniques and standardised data models. Key functionalities include:

Data Ingestion and Normalisation: Processes data from drones, air traffic systems, and environmental agencies, ensuring consistency and compatibility.

Messaging Broker: Supports real-time data streaming and communication between stakeholders, including regulatory bodies and infrastructure managers.

API Gateway: Facilitates secure access to services and external systems, enabling smooth interactions between national authorities and cross-border entities.

Data Sovereignty and Privacy Compliance: Implements encryption, access controls, and GDPR-compliant mechanisms to protect sensitive infrastructure and operational data.

The middleware also supports cross-border operations by integrating with data spaces like Gaia-X, promoting seamless data sharing among regulatory agencies and stakeholders.

Service layer

The Service Layer delivers the essential functionalities required for automating the permit lifecycle and supporting drone-based inspections. Core services include:

Decision support system (DSS): Provides advanced analytics and recommendations to stakeholders by leveraging data from permits, drone operations, and environmental assessments. This system aids regulatory authorities and infrastructure managers in making informed decisions about approvals, scheduling, and conflict resolution.

Work order management service: Automates the creation, tracking, and management of work orders related to drone operations. This service ensures that tasks, such as inspections or permit reviews, are assigned, monitored, and completed efficiently, improving operational oversight.

Permit management service: Automates the submission, validation, and approval of drone operation permits. This service interacts with stakeholders such as regulatory authorities, traffic directorates, and air traffic control providers to streamline workflows and reduce delays.

Authorisation service: Implements procedures to authenticate and authorise stakeholders involved in the permitting process. By ensuring role-based access control and eIDAS-compliant identity verification, this service guarantees secure interactions across the platform

Business layer

The Business Layer provides user-centric tools and insights to enhance stakeholder collaboration, transparency, and decision-making. Key components include:

Visualisation and stakeholder dashboards: Interactive dashboards that provide real-time insights into the status of permit applications, drone inspections, and compliance metrics. The dashboards are tailored for different user roles, including drone operators, infrastructure managers, and regulatory authorities.

Reporting and analytics tools: Generate detailed reports for regulatory compliance, operational efficiency, and environmental impact assessments. These tools help stakeholders evaluate the effectiveness of drone-based inspections and identify areas for improvement.

User interaction interface: A centralised platform for stakeholders to access services, manage workflows, and receive notifications about permit statuses. The interface simplifies interactions with the system, promoting higher adoption rates

Blockchain: Leverages blockchain technology to provide immutable records of permit transactions, enhancing trust and accountability among stakeholders. The audit trails enable stakeholders to verify the authenticity and status of permits.

Holistic view and interactions

These services interact in a structured workflow to ensure smooth permit approvals, optimised decision-making, and secure execution of drone-based inspections. The Permit Management Service acts as the entry point for processing permit applications and verifying regulatory compliance. Once a permit request is submitted, it is analysed by the DSS, which assesses operational feasibility, risk factors, and scheduling needs. The Work Order Management Service is then responsible for executing approved permits by generating work orders for inspection teams, ensuring operational tasks are clearly defined and tracked. Throughout this process, the Authorisation Service ensures that only authenticated and authorised stakeholders interact with the platform, securing data access and regulatory compliance.

The Permit Management Service connects directly to Stakeholder Dashboards, providing real-time permit status updates. The DSS feeds data into Reporting and Analytics Tools, enabling advanced insights for decision-making. The Work Order Management Service integrates with the User Interaction Interface, ensuring smooth task execution and real-time updates for end users. Lastly, the Authorisation Service ensures that access to the Blockchain is secure, maintaining an immutable and trustworthy record of permit transactions.

This structured integration between the Service and Business Layers ensures transparency, efficiency, and regulatory compliance while providing stakeholders with the necessary tools to manage drone-based inspections effectively.

A graphical representation of the abovementioned interactions is illustrated in Figure 15:

Figure 15 Holistic view and interactions between the layers of Use Case IV

3.4.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 16:

Figure 16 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case IV

3.4.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case IV are illustrated in Table 25 below:

Table 25 Regulatory aspects of Use Case IV

Regulation/standard	Article/section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
Data Governance Act (DGA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 5 & 11	The digital permit platform can benefit from public-sector data reuse to integrate air traffic and environmental regulations in flight approvals. Data intermediation services enable secure transactions between agencies involved in permit validation.	●

Data Act – Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 4 & 8	Ensures that drone-generated data (e.g., flight telemetry, infrastructure inspection data) is accessible under fair conditions. Operators can demand access to data from infrastructure managers, while data holders must ensure fair and non-discriminatory access. This is critical in cross-border operations where different regulations apply to data exchange.	●
Interoperable Europe Act – Regulation (EU) 2024/903	Art. 3 & 7	Cross-border drone inspections rely on interoperable data exchanges between national agencies (traffic control, infrastructure managers, environmental bodies). Art. 3 establishes an EU interoperability framework, requiring authorities to adopt common technical standards. Art. 7 creates an Interoperability Board to oversee such standards, directly impacting how the permit platform integrates with different national authorities.	●
GDPR – Regulation (EU) 2016/679	Art. 6 & 25	The GDPR applies because drones may collect personal data (e.g., images, location data). Compliance requires a legal basis for processing adherence to data minimisation and security. Data breaches must be reported under GDPR rules, and operators may need a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) before launching cross-border drone operations.	●
eIDAS – Regulation (EU) No 910/2014	Art. 6 & 24	The digital permit system must support electronic identification (eID) and trust services for cross-border drone operators. eIDAS Regulation ensures that national eIDs are mutually recognised, meaning a drone operator in Spain can apply for a permit in France using Spanish credentials and mandates that qualified trust service providers, ensuring that electronic signatures on flight permits are legally binding.	●
NIS 2 Directive – Directive (EU) 2022/2555	Art. 4 & 21	NIS 2 Directive mandates risk assessments for cybersecurity threats and requires the platform to implement incident response plans.	●
Digital Services Act (DSA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/2065	Art. 14 & 19	The ODP may qualify as an online intermediary under the DSA. Art. 14 requires algorithmic transparency, meaning automated permit approvals must be explainable.	●
Artificial Intelligence Act	Art 6-10	This ODP falls into the high-risk category due to its direct impact on public safety, privacy, and infrastructure. The ODP must ensure that Drone operators establish robust systems to identify, mitigate, and monitor risks associated with AI-powered functionalities, such as navigation systems or automated data analysis.	●
	Art 13,14 & 15	While the ODP automates permit validation and airspace management, human intervention should remain possible to override AI decisions during critical operations or emergencies. The AI algorithms used for flight operations or inspection analysis must be explainable to ensure that operators and regulatory bodies understand the decision-making processes.	●
Regulation 2019/947 on Unmanned Aircraft	Art.5	The ODP must automate the drone operator risk assessment (SORA) compliance, verifying operator qualifications, airspace restrictions, and safety measures in cross-border drone operations.	●

Systems (UAS) operations	Art. 11	Operators conducting drone flights outside the "open" category must obtain operational authorisation or hold a Light UAS Operator Certificate (LUC). The blockchain technology implemented in this ODP must be able to optimise LUC validation and regulatory approvals across different national authorities.	●
	Arts. 13 & 15	Member States must accept authorisations issued by other EU countries. Spain, Portugal, and France restrictions are standardised by the ODP ensuring a cross-border validation process, with mutual recognition of permits while respecting national regulations. The ODP permit system integrates with national aviation authorities and traffic management services to automate airspace approvals and ensure compliance with real-time geo-awareness alerts.	●
	Art. 18	The ODP integrates national registration databases, ensuring that only certified operators and compliant drones are permitted to conduct inspections.	●
Regulation (EU) 2019/945 on technical and operational requirements	Arts. 4 & 6	CE Marking, compliance and classification of UAS: the ODP validates that drones used in inspections comply with CE safety and technical requirements before issuing a permit.	●
	Arts. 13 & 14	Geo-Awareness & Remote Identification. Certified category: The ODP permit system integrates geo-fencing and remote ID validation, ensuring that drones do not enter restricted or unauthorised airspace during inspections. It also verifies drone certification levels and flags high-risk operations for additional approvals.	●
Regulation (EU) 376/2014 on Occurrence Reporting in Civil Aviation	Arts 4, 6 & 7	Requires drone operators to report safety incidents and share data across authorities. The ODP must integrate secure data sharing mechanisms to comply with safety reporting obligations	●
Regulation (EU) 2021/664 on U-Space Implementation	Arts. 3, 8, 9, 11 & 13	Defines a framework for the integration of UAS into European airspace. The ODP must align with U-Space services (e.g., e-identification, geo-awareness, flight authorisations) to ensure safe and coordinated drone operations when requested.	●

Conclusions

A central aspect of the regulatory framework is data governance and sharing, which is essential for drone operations that rely on access to public sector data, device-generated data, and secure data exchanges. The Data Governance Act (DGA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/868 establishes a legal structure for data intermediaries, promoting secure and transparent data sharing mechanisms. This is particularly relevant for drone operators who require access to datasets to enhance operational planning and execution. The Data Act – Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 complements these principles by mandating fair and non-discriminatory access to data, ensuring that data holders provide access under

equitable conditions. These frameworks enable improved data accessibility while fostering innovation in drone technology.

The Interoperable Europe Act – Regulation (EU) 2024/903 ensures seamless data exchange between public administrations and private entities. This regulation plays a crucial role in enabling real-time interoperability between drone operators and national aviation authorities, particularly in cross-border operations where regulatory harmonisation is necessary for effective coordination. The act mandates an interoperability assessment and the establishment of the European Interoperability Board, which oversees compliance and governance structures for enhanced cooperation.

Privacy and cybersecurity considerations are fundamental in drone-based inspections, as they often involve the collection and processing of personal data. The GDPR – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 sets out strict requirements regarding data protection, mandating lawful, fair, and transparent processing of personal data. Drone operators must adhere to key GDPR principles such as data minimisation, explicit consent for data collection, and implementation of appropriate security measures to protect collected data. The NIS 2 Directive – Directive (EU) 2022/2555 strengthens cybersecurity obligations by requiring risk management strategies, encryption, and incident response protocols for digital platforms that manage drone permits and related services. Similarly, the Digital Services Act (DSA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 enforces transparency and due diligence obligations for digital platforms, ensuring compliance with accountability and security standards in drone-related data transactions.

It is important to note that the Artificial Intelligence Act has a profound impact on the applications and functionalities of UCIV. By setting high standards for risk management, transparency, and safety, it ensures the responsible deployment of AI in drone operations. Although compliance poses technical and operational challenges, the AIA ultimately supports innovation and harmonisation across the EU, enabling safer, more efficient, and legally compliant drone operations for linear infrastructure inspections.

In addition to broader regulations on data governance and cybersecurity, drone-specific regulations directly govern the operation, certification, and airspace management of UAS. Regulation (EU) 2019/947 establishes operational requirements, including risk assessment obligations using the SORA methodology. Drone operators must submit risk evaluations, obtain operational authorisations, and ensure compliance with national aviation regulations. Furthermore, the regulation emphasises the recognition of cross-border authorisations, ensuring that permits issued in one EU country are valid across others while respecting national restrictions. The LUC streamlines compliance verification, allowing qualified operators to conduct drone flights with reduced administrative burdens.

In parallel, Regulation (EU) 2019/945 defines technical and operational requirements for drones, covering aspects such as CE marking, classification (C0-C6 categories), geo-

awareness, and remote identification. This ensures that drones used in EU airspace meet safety and technical specifications before deployment. The regulation also imposes strict certification requirements for drones classified under the "certified" category, which are subject to higher safety and cybersecurity standards due to their involvement in complex operations.

Safety and incident reporting are critical components of aviation oversight. Regulation (EU) 376/2014 on Occurrence Reporting in Civil Aviation mandates that drone operators, infrastructure managers, and regulatory bodies report safety-related incidents that may affect public safety or air traffic. Member states must store and analyse reported occurrences in a centralised repository and share relevant data among aviation authorities to improve safety coordination.

As digital transformation accelerates, eIDAS – Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 ensures secure electronic identification and trust services for drone operators. This regulation is vital for automating permit applications, electronic approvals, and cross-border recognition of electronic identities, simplifying administrative procedures for drone-related activities.

Finally, the U-Space Implementation Regulation (EU) 2021/664 establishes a structured approach to integrating drones into European airspace. It requires member states to designate U-Space zones, where drones must operate under digital and automated traffic management services. These services include electronic identification, geo-awareness, flight authorisations, and real-time traffic information to ensure safe and coordinated drone operations. The regulation mandates that operators request and receive automated flight authorisations before take-off, while also ensuring compliance with air traffic management protocols.

At the national level, this UC references countries, **Spain, Portugal, and France**, generally align with EU regulations on data governance, cybersecurity, and privacy. National aviation laws introduce specific operational constraints. The ODP's automated framework mitigates these challenges by streamlining multi-country permit validation, reducing approval times, and enabling seamless interoperability between national aviation authorities. As a result, UCIV enhances the efficiency, safety, and legal compliance of cross-border drone operations for linear infrastructure inspections.

At the **data governance level**, key EU regulations—Data Governance Act (DGA), Data Act, and Interoperable Europe Act—show no national deviations, ensuring seamless data sharing and interoperability. Similarly, GDPR has been transposed into national laws (Ley Orgánica 3/2018 in Spain, Lei n.º 58/2019 in Portugal, and LOI n° 2018-493 in France), maintaining privacy protections with slight national adaptations. Regulations like eIDAS, NIS 2 Directive, and Digital Services Act (DSA) are also uniformly implemented across these countries.

At the **drone-specific regulatory level**, national aviation laws introduce distinct operational restrictions. Spain follows AESA Regulations and Royal Decree 1036/2017, Portugal enforces Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil (ANAC) Regulations and Decree-Law No. 58/2018, while France complies with French Civil Aviation Authority Regulations and Arrêté du 3 décembre 2020. While Regulation (EU) 2019/947 mandates mutual recognition of permits, these national laws create additional compliance challenges.

These national differences present potential barriers to seamless cross-border drone operations. However, the ODP introduced in UCIV addresses these challenges by automating compliance validation across multiple jurisdictions. The ODP integrates national aviation regulations, ensuring that drone operators meet country-specific requirements while benefiting from the EU-wide regulatory framework. By standardising permit validation, enabling real-time U-Space air traffic integration, and facilitating secure cross-border data sharing, the platform enhances operational efficiency while ensuring compliance with privacy and security regulations.

3.4.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCIV. The governance model analysis considers what a viable setup could look like to allow the various stakeholders — ranging from infrastructure managers to national and regional authorities — to participate effectively in the ODP, despite differing mandates, regulatory responsibilities, and levels of engagement. At the same time, the model must ensure compliance with the complex and multi-layered regulatory landscape that governs drone operations, particularly in cross-border contexts.

UCIV proposes the deployment of advanced digital services enabled by the ODP to streamline and validate permits for drone-based inspections. These services rely on inputs from multiple stakeholders and are designed to deliver shared benefits such as reduced bureaucracy, enhanced inspection efficiency, and improved infrastructure maintenance. A suitable governance model must therefore balance stakeholder needs, facilitate cooperation and transparency, and ensure that the digital platform functions reliably, securely, and in alignment with relevant regulations across national borders.

Stakeholder analysis

A first step in the governance model analysis is to understand better how the different ODP services benefit the various stakeholders and what resources they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating.

The Table 26 below captures the relationship between the proposed ODP services and identified stakeholders. Stakeholders considered include the following:

- Infrastructure Managers (IM)
- Air Traffic Control Providers (ATC)
- Traffic Directorates (TD)
- Other Public Authorities (PA)
- Drone Operators (DO)
- Infrastructure Managers (Cross-border counterpart)
- ODP Operator

It is assumed that the ODP operator provides all services as part of the ODP. Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, while others may not directly participate but still benefit from them.

Table 26 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	End user	Beneficiaries
Digital Permit Management for Drone Operations	ODP operator	Infrastructure Managers (IM), Drone Operators (DO)	All public authorities, IMs, DOs
Real-Time Multi-Authority Coordination	ODP operator	Air Traffic Control (ATC), Traffic Directorate (TD), Other Public Authorities	IMs, DOs, National and cross-border agencies
Automated Legal and Regulatory Compliance Validation	ODP operator	ATC, TD, Other Public Authorities	IMs, Public Authorities
Cross-Border Inspection Workflow Integration	ODP operator	Infrastructure Managers (IM) from involved countries, Public Authorities	Cross-border stakeholders, drone service providers
Inspection Status Tracking and Notification System	ODP operator	All participating stakeholders	All participants (improved communication and reduced delays)
Blockchain-Based Audit Trail	ODP operator	Regulators, Infrastructure Managers, Public Authorities	Legal authorities, national regulators, audit bodies, IMs

Based on this initial analysis, the role of each stakeholder plays in the ODP can now be determined. Table 27 below shows their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 27 Stakeholders' role in ODP

Stakeholder	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
Infrastructure Manager (IM)	End user of ODP permit management and coordination services	Inspection request data (location, timing, scope), infrastructure access details	Faster permit approvals, improved maintenance efficiency, reduced inspection delays
Air Traffic Control Provider (ATC)	Validator of airspace compliance and drone flight permits	Legal flight conditions, restricted zones, pilot licenses	Centralised processing of flight requests, reduced manual workload, better flight tracking

Traffic Directorate (TD)	Validator of road safety impacts	Traffic flow data, event scheduling, safety protocols	Improved coordination with infrastructure works, fewer disruptions, safer operations
Other Public Authorities (PA)	Validator of legal/environmental/d efence compliance	National/regional regulation inputs, site-specific constraints	Transparent permit validation process, faster review cycles, enhanced regulatory assurance
Drone Operator (DO)	Executor of drone inspections	Drone ID, pilot certifications, flight plan details	Simplified and predictable permitting process, expanded business opportunities
ODP Operator	Platform provider and coordinator	Platform infrastructure, regulatory logic, user access controls	Trusted governance role, transparency, harmonisation of validation across all stakeholders

Finally, Table 28 below examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 28 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
ODP Operator	While expected to act as a neutral and trusted coordinator, the ODP Operator faces potential challenges in aligning with diverse national and EU regulatory frameworks. Ensuring that the platform remains compliant, standardised, and user-friendly across multiple jurisdictions is complex and may involve ongoing testing and coordination with national authorities. As such, there may be reservations about scalability, legal consistency, and the ability to adapt rapidly to evolving regulations.
Infrastructure Manager (IM)	May be concerned about data confidentiality and the responsiveness of multiple validation authorities in time-critical inspections.
Air Traffic Control Provider (ATC)	Requires assurance that the platform accurately reflects up-to-date flight regulations and licensing data. May require technical integration with existing systems.
Traffic Directorate (TD)	Could you hesitate if drone inspections conflict with traffic safety operations or if workflows are unclear. Needs coordination assurance.
Other Public Authorities (PA)	May need clarification on regulatory authority in cross-border inspections. May also require guarantees of data integrity and jurisdiction.
Drone Operator (DO)	Potential concerns about procedural complexity and permit delays if the system is not efficiently managed. Requires clear onboarding and support.

Ownership and legal form of ODP platform operator

The ODP supporting drone-based inspections is designed to operate under the direct management of a neutral, pan-European entity, such as Eurocontrol or a similar European-level aviation coordination body. This organisation is well-positioned to ensure cross-border regulatory alignment, uphold aviation safety standards, and maintain the interoperability of drone permit systems across EU member states. The platform operator will be responsible for maintaining the digital infrastructure, coordinating multi-

authority workflows, and ensuring the integration of national regulations and validation procedures into a unified digital process.

By placing the ODP under the oversight of a pan-European entity, the governance model enhances trust among national and regional stakeholders, including infrastructure managers, air traffic controllers, public authorities, and drone operators. This structure avoids the perception of national bias, encourages participation from all involved countries, and reinforces the platform's role as a standardised, interoperable service supporting cross-border drone operations.

Governance Model and Ownership

The most suitable model for operating the ODP is a publicly governed digital platform, managed by a neutral European entity. While this central operator holds responsibility for the platform's technical and operational management, collaborative governance mechanisms should be established to incorporate structured input from national air traffic control bodies, infrastructure authorities, and environmental or regulatory agencies. This ensures that stakeholder interests and regulatory variations are reflected within the platform's rules and workflows.

The primary objectives of the drone permit ODP include:

- Providing a standardised, secure, and transparent platform for drone permit validation across Europe.
- Ensuring compliance with EU and national aviation regulations, including those from EASA and other relevant bodies.
- Reducing bureaucratic delays in permit processing for infrastructure inspections, especially in cross-border contexts.
- Supporting blockchain-based traceability and legal validation of digital permits across multiple authorities.
- Enabling safe and efficient infrastructure maintenance with minimal disruptions and full legal coverage.

A nationally controlled or for-profit model would risk fragmentation, regulatory misalignment, and lack of trust, particularly in cross-border operations. By contrast, a pan-European entity-managed ODP ensures consistency, neutrality, and long-term alignment with EU policy goals, supporting digitalisation, interoperability, and infrastructure resilience across the EU.

Regulatory governance consideration

The UC operates within a highly regulated environment that spans national borders and involves multiple sectors — namely aviation, infrastructure maintenance, public safety, and environmental protection. As such, the governance of the ODP must place regulatory

compliance at the core of its design and operation, particularly due to the sensitive nature of airspace management, flight approvals, and public infrastructure oversight.

The analysis of the ODP services from a regulatory governance perspective identifies the following key areas requiring compliance:

- **Data Protection and Cross-Border Data Flows:** The ODP will process sensitive information, including flight plans, inspection scopes, infrastructure location data, and validation workflows involving multiple national entities. Therefore, it must fully comply with the GDPR and the Data Governance Act, ensuring secure data exchange, transparency, and user consent, particularly across jurisdictional boundaries.
- **Airspace and Drone Operation Compliance:** Given the involvement of air traffic authorities and national drone regulations, the ODP must align with policies established by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and national civil aviation bodies. This includes adherence to visual line-of-sight (VLOS) rules, no-fly zone protocols, and national security regulations, which may vary by country.
- **Cross-Border Regulatory Harmonisation:** The ODP must accommodate variations in drone permit procedures and legal frameworks across EU member states. In countries like Spain, where regional authorities may have independent regulatory power, this becomes even more complex. The ODP must allow for modular compliance logic, enabling different validation layers depending on jurisdiction, while preserving a unified, transparent process.
- **Infrastructure and Environmental Safeguards:** Drone-based inspections often involve flights near or over critical infrastructure, environmentally protected areas, or public spaces. Therefore, the ODP must integrate regulatory input from environmental agencies, public safety departments, and infrastructure authorities, ensuring that all necessary permissions are obtained before inspections proceed.

To ensure continuous alignment with evolving regulatory frameworks and build confidence among participating stakeholders, it is recommended to establish a **Regulatory Advisory Board** within the governance structure of the ODP. This advisory board should include:

- Representatives from EU-level aviation and data protection authorities (e.g., EASA, EDPS),
- National and regional authorities involved in air traffic control, environmental protection, and infrastructure regulation,

While not directly responsible for operational supervision, this board would support the ODP supervisory body by ensuring access to up-to-date legal interpretations and help harmonise the application of EU directives and national regulations.

3.5 Use case V: Smart port operations

3.5.1 Use case identification and scope

The Smart Port Operations UC aims to enhance efficiency, safety, and sustainability in port management through the integration of AI-driven cameras, drone systems, and digital platforms. By leveraging real-time monitoring and volumetric measurement technologies, this UC enables precise tracking of docks, cranes, ships, and stockpiles, ensuring optimal resource allocation and regulatory compliance. The FIWARE digital platform, as adopted by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), serves as the central hub for data integration, providing advanced analytics, visualisation, and decision-making tools to improve port operations.

The platform facilitates automation in scheduling, inventory management, and security monitoring, reducing manual inefficiencies while promoting environmentally sustainable practices. By creating a scalable and replicable model, the UC fosters cross-sector collaboration among port authorities, technology providers, and logistics stakeholders, paving the way for the digital transformation of port operations. The real-time insights generated through this framework not only enhance safety and operational efficiency but also support the long-term goal of smart, interconnected, and sustainable ports worldwide.

3.5.2 Actors of the Use Case

The actors involved in the conceptualisation of the ODP can be stakeholders, devices, or systems that trigger an action. The following Table 29 analyses the main actors and their actions in the UC.

Table 29 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case V

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Port Authority	Role	The governing body is responsible for the overall management, regulation, and administration of the port.	-Supplies input information about port regulations, schedules, and safety protocols. -Receives real-time operational data from AI cameras and drones. -Both supplies and receives information to ensure smooth and efficient port operations, overseeing all activities.	No
AI Camera System	System	An intelligent camera network was installed throughout the port to monitor operations and detect anomalies.	-Supplies real-time video and analytical data to the central digital platform. -Receives configuration updates and operational commands from the digital platform.	ISO 27001
Drone Fleet	System	A fleet of drones programmed to conduct volumetric	-Supply aerial data, including volumetric measurements of stockpiles, to the central platform.	EASA (EU) 2019/947.

		measurements and surveillance of the port.	-Receive flight plans, operational commands, and data processing instructions from the digital platform.	
Logistics Companies	Role	Companies responsible for transporting goods to and from the port, managing supply chains, and coordinating with port authorities.	-Supply input information about shipment schedules and logistics requirements. -Receive real-time updates on port operations, traffic conditions, and potential delays.	No
Ship Operators	Role	Entities responsible for managing ships docking at the port, including cargo handling and scheduling.	-Supplies input information regarding ship arrival and departure times, cargo details, and operational needs. -Receives real-time updates on docking schedules, available resources, and any potential operational issues.	No
Customs Authorities	Role	Government officials responsible for regulating and inspecting goods entering and leaving the port to ensure compliance with national laws.	-Supplies input information about customs regulations and requirements. -Receives real-time data on incoming and outgoing shipments to facilitate inspections and compliance checks.	National Regulations
Environmental Monitoring Systems	System	Systems installed to monitor environmental conditions, such as air and water quality, within the port.	-Supplies real-time environmental data to the digital platform. -Receives alerts and commands for data collection and reporting from the digital platform.	ISO 14001
Port Staff	Role	Employees working within the port, including dockworkers, crane operators, and administrative staff.	-Supplies input information on operational status, equipment conditions, and work schedules. -Receives real-time updates on operational tasks, safety protocols, and workflow changes.	No

3.5.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of the UCV is presented in Figure 17 and the description of the UC scenarios in Table 30:

Figure 17 Diagram of Use Case V

Table 30 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case V

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.V.S1	Real-Time Monitoring of Port Operation	Detection of unusual activity or operational anomalies by AI cameras.	AI cameras installed throughout the port continuously monitor activities such as docking, loading, and unloading ships. If the AI system detects unusual activity, such as unauthorised access to restricted areas or operational inefficiencies, it immediately sends an alert to the Port Authority through the FIWARE digital platform. The Port Authority reviews the alert, verifies the issue using the camera feed, and coordinates with the Security Personnel to address the anomaly. The security team takes necessary actions to resolve the issue and updates the Port Authority. The incident is logged in to the digital platform for future reference and analysis.	AI Camera System
BEG.V.S2	Volumetric Measurement of Stockpiles	Scheduled drone flight for daily volumetric measurement.	At a scheduled time, drones programmed to measure stockpile volumes take off and follow predefined routes around the port. They capture detailed aerial images and use software to calculate the volume of materials stored in the port. This data is transmitted to the FIWARE digital platform, where it is processed and analyzed. The Port Authority receives a detailed report on stockpile volumes, which is also accessible to Logistics	Drone Fleet

			Companies and Environmental Monitoring Systems for inventory management and environmental impact assessments. Any discrepancies or unusual findings are flagged for further investigation.	
BEG.V.S3	Coordination of Ship Docking	Arrival notification of an incoming ship.	When a ship is approaching the port, the Ship Operators notify the Port Authority of its estimated time of arrival and docking requirements. The Port Authority uses real-time data from AI cameras and the digital platform to assess the availability of docking spaces and allocate a suitable dock for the incoming ship. The information is relayed back to Ship Operators and the port workforce. Dockworkers prepare the allocated dock, and the ship docks smoothly. The process is monitored in real-time to ensure efficiency and safety. Any issues are immediately addressed by coordinating with the relevant actors.	Ship Operators
BEG.V.S4	Environmental Monitoring and Response	Detection of environmental threshold breaches by monitoring systems.	Environmental Monitoring Systems continuously collect data on air and water quality within the port. If any environmental parameter breaches the preset safety thresholds, the system sends an alert to the FIWARE digital platform. The Port Authority receives the alert and coordinates with Environmental Monitoring Systems and the port workforce to investigate the source of the pollution. Corrective actions are taken, such as adjusting operations or implementing mitigation measures. The response and actions taken are logged into the digital platform for regulatory reporting and future reference.	Environmental Monitoring Systems

3.5.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCV are illustrated in Table 31:

Table 31 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case V

Challenges	Mitigation measures
Integration of heterogeneous systems: Diverse systems and devices, such as AI cameras, drones, and legacy port systems, require seamless integration to enable smooth data exchange.	Use middleware with data normalisation capabilities and standardised data models to harmonise data formats and ensure interoperability.
Workforce training and adaptation: Upskilling port workers to effectively operate and maintain	Develop comprehensive training programs, hands-on workshops, and user-friendly interfaces to support workforce adaptation.

advanced technologies like drones and AI-driven systems.	
Real-time data processing and analysis: Processing large volumes of real-time data from multiple sources to make timely decisions.	Leverage edge computing for local data processing and cloud infrastructure for advanced analytics, ensuring efficient data handling.
Cross-border data exchange: Sharing operational data with international stakeholders while ensuring compliance with varying regulations and standards.	Use data spaces like Gaia-X to securely and standardise data sharing, ensuring compliance with local and EU regulations.
Cybersecurity risks: Ports are high-value targets for cyberattacks, risking disruption to operations and data breaches.	Deploy multi-layered cybersecurity measures, including firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and regular vulnerability assessments. Use blockchain for secure logging of critical events.
Data privacy and GDPR compliance: Handling large amounts of sensitive data from AI cameras, drones, and IoT devices while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.	Implement end-to-end encryption, anonymisation techniques, and robust access controls. Conduct regular GDPR audits to ensure adherence to privacy standards.
Scalability of infrastructure: Managing increasing volumes of data and operations as the port expands its activities and digital capabilities.	Use cloud-based solutions and modular architectures to scale infrastructure efficiently and support future growth

3.5.5 Modular architecture specification

Perception layer

The perception layer serves as the basis for data collection within the smart port ecosystem, integrating a diverse range of IoT devices and external systems to monitor and control physical activities across the port. Those systems and devices include:

AI cameras: These cameras are strategically deployed across the port to monitor docking operations, cargo handling, and security. They provide real-time video feeds and use AI to detect anomalies, such as equipment malfunctions or unauthorised access.

Drone fleet: Equipped with high-resolution cameras and sensors, drones are utilised for aerial inspections, volumetric stockpile measurements, and infrastructure monitoring. They perform scheduled or on-demand missions to provide detailed insights into operational and environmental conditions.

Environmental sensors: A network of IoT devices tracks air quality, water pollution, and noise levels, ensuring the port's compliance with environmental standards. These sensors provide continuous monitoring and automated alerts for threshold breaches.

Geolocation systems: These systems include Global Positioning System (GPS) for vehicle tracking and actuators for controlling port equipment, such as cranes and gates, enabling precise and automated operations.

This layer ensures seamless data acquisition, forming the backbone for real-time monitoring and decision-making within the port.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer serves as the central engine for managing data flow and ensuring seamless interoperability across the smart port ecosystem. It bridges the Perception Layer and the Application Layer, handling data ingestion, processing, and sharing while enforcing compliance with EU regulations. This layer integrates diverse data sources, including IoT devices, AI cameras, drones, and legacy port systems, ensuring they interact cohesively within a unified platform.

At its core, this layer facilitates the reliable ingestion of data from external systems and devices, supporting both standardised and proprietary communication protocols. Once ingested, the data is normalised into common models to ensure consistency across formats and sources, enabling uniform analysis and decision-making. The Messaging Broker component within this layer provides robust real-time data streaming capabilities, ensuring efficient and scalable communication between components.

To enable secure interaction with external systems, the API Gateway acts as the northbound interface, providing stakeholders with standardised access to the platform's functionalities. This gateway is integral to maintaining secure communication channels and enforcing role-based access control. Furthermore, the layer implements robust data sovereignty mechanisms, ensuring that stakeholders retain full control over their data while adhering to GDPR and other regulatory requirements. This functionality allows stakeholders to define and enforce data sharing policies confidently. A key component of this layer is the Data Space Adapter/Connector, which ensures interoperability with other data spaces, such as Gaia-X. This capability allows the platform to securely share and ingest data from external ecosystems, supporting cross-sector and cross-border collaboration.

Service layer

The Service (Application) Layer provides the core functionalities required to transform raw data from the lower layers into actionable insights and operational tools, ensuring the efficient and sustainable management of smart port operations. Each service within this layer is tailored to address specific aspects of port activities while integrating seamlessly with other services to create a cohesive and responsive platform. The key services include but not limited to:

Real-time monitoring service: The real-time monitoring service processes live data from AI cameras, drones, and IoT sensors deployed in the port. This service detects anomalies, such as equipment failures, unauthorised access, or environmental hazards, and provides operators with immediate alerts. By offering continuous oversight of port activities, the service enhances security and operational reliability, ensuring proactive response to potential issues.

Volumetric measurement service: This service utilises drone-captured imagery to calculate stockpile volumes for resources such as coal, gravel, or containers stored in the

port. Automating volumetric measurements eliminates manual errors, improves resource allocation, and ensures precise inventory tracking. The service integrates these insights into logistics and planning workflows to support operational efficiency.

Environmental compliance service: The environmental compliance service monitors air quality, water conditions, and noise levels using IoT sensors and analyzes the data against predefined environmental thresholds. If breaches occur, the service generates alerts and compliance reports to guide corrective actions. By ensuring adherence to environmental regulations, this service supports the port's sustainability goals and regulatory obligations.

Incident and security management service: Analyses data from AI cameras, drones, and sensors to detect security breaches, operational anomalies, or environmental threshold violations. They provide alerts and recommendations for incident response, ensuring timely action to maintain safety and compliance. Automated workflows ensure that security protocols and incident management steps are consistently followed.

Logistics coordination service: This service streamlines operations by integrating data from various sources to optimise cargo handling, dock scheduling, and resource utilisation. It enables port operators to coordinate activities in real-time, reducing delays and maximising throughput. By aligning logistics processes with dynamic data inputs, the service ensures a more synchronised and efficient port environment.

Decision support system: The DSS provides predictive analytics and visualisation tools to support strategic decision-making. It aggregates data from other services, analyzes trends, and generates actionable recommendations for optimising workflows, resource management, and safety protocols. With its advanced analytics capabilities, the DSS empowers stakeholders to make data-driven decisions, enhancing both short-term efficiency and long-term planning.

Automation and control platforms: These platforms enable remote monitoring and control of IoT devices and port equipment, such as cranes, gates, and conveyor belts. Operators can execute tasks like opening gates, repositioning equipment, or adjusting schedules through centralised interfaces. The automation capabilities reduce human intervention, enhance accuracy, and streamline port operations for maximum efficiency.

Business layer

The Business Layer directly links with stakeholders, translating the platform's outputs into meaningful insights, tools, and workflows. It supports decision-making and operational transparency.

Visualisation and KPI dashboards: Provides real-time and historical metrics on key performance indicators, such as cargo handling efficiency, environmental compliance, and equipment utilisation. Stakeholders can use these dashboards to monitor operations and make informed decisions.

Workflow management: Automates routine tasks, such as assigning dock schedules, responding to anomalies, and issuing maintenance requests, streamlining operations, and reducing manual overhead.

Reporting and compliance: Generates detailed reports for regulatory bodies, covering areas like environmental impact assessments, safety audits, and operational performance. These reports ensure transparency and support compliance with national and EU regulations.

User interaction service: Offers a user-friendly interface for port operators, logistics companies, and environmental agencies to access and exchange critical data, book resources, and receive alerts. This service ensures stakeholders have the tools they need to interact with the platform effectively.

User Profiling plays a crucial role in customising the platform's services for different stakeholders, including port authorities, logistics operators, and regulatory bodies. By analyzing user behaviour, preferences, and operational patterns, the system can provide personalised recommendations, optimise workflows, and enhance decision-making.

IAM ensures secure and controlled access to the platform, protecting sensitive logistics and environmental data. By integrating eIDAS-compliant authentication mechanisms and multi-factor authentication (MFA), IAM guarantees that only authorised users can interact with critical port operations data.

Blockchain for trust and transparency: Provides an immutable ledger for recording critical transactions, such as cargo movements, environmental compliance logs, and financial settlements. This builds trust among stakeholders and ensures traceability in all operations.

Holistic view and interactions

The architecture of UCV: Smart Port Operations is designed as an interconnected and dynamic system where each layer complements and supports the others to achieve seamless functionality. The Perception Layer collects real-time data from IoT devices, AI cameras, and drones, serving as the foundation for actionable insights. This data is then processed, normalised, and secured in the Middleware Layer, which acts as the central engine for data management and interoperability. The Application Layer leverages this harmonised data to provide critical services such as real-time monitoring, logistics coordination, and environmental compliance, ensuring operational efficiency and regulatory alignment. The outputs of these services feed into the Business Layer, which delivers intuitive dashboards, automated workflows, and compliance tools to stakeholders, facilitating informed decision-making and collaboration. Together, these layers form a cohesive ecosystem where data flows seamlessly from collection to actionable insights, enabling smart ports to operate efficiently, sustainably, and in compliance with regional and cross-border regulations.

A generic framework for the services and their possible interactions is illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Holistic view and interaction between the layers of Use Case V

3.5.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 19:

Figure 19 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case V

3.5.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case V are illustrated in Table 32 below:

Table 32 Regulatory aspects of Use Case V

Regulation/ standard	Article/ section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
Data Governance Act (DGA) - Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 5, 9 & 12	Ensures neutrality and transparency for entities facilitating data sharing, being relevant for secure and fair data transactions. Supports reuse of public sector data, particularly environmental and logistical datasets. FIWARE must act as a neutral intermediary.	●
Data Act - Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 4, 11 & 15	Establishes fair access to data, enabling collaboration among stakeholders, and imposes fair data sharing terms. Governs the conditions under which public bodies can access data in public interest, ensuring lawful access.	●
Interoperable Europe Act - Regulation (EU) 2024/903	Art. 7	Requires adherence to EU-wide interoperability standards, ensuring FIWARE systems align with such frameworks for scalability.	●
GDPR - Regulation (EU) 2016/679	Art. 6 & 25	Mandates lawful, fair, and transparent data processing. Requires safeguards for operational data that might include personal information. Requires embedding privacy and security measures during the design of AI cameras and drones for port monitoring.	●
Artificial Intelligence Act	Art. 6-10	High-Risk AI Systems. AI systems used in critical infrastructure, such as ports, fall under the high-risk category. The AI systems integrated into the ODP must undergo thorough risk assessments. ODP operators must document the functioning of AI systems to comply with transparency requirements. It must ensure that data used for drone route optimisation or environmental monitoring is accurate, representative, and free of discrimination.	
	Art. 13 & 14	The Act requires that users be informed about AI system capabilities and limitations, particularly when AI decisions significantly affect individuals or operations. The ODP must implement human-in-the-loop mechanisms to ensure that critical decisions (e.g., in cargo handling or drone navigation in high-risk zones) are reviewed or approved by human operators.	
EASA 2019/947	Art. 3, 5 & 12	Ports are considered as 'specific' category. Drones Operators must submit a risk assessment (often following SORA methodology). The port authority grants operational authorisation based on the risk assessment	●
eFTI 2020/1056	Art. 3 & 4	Establishes that the regulation applies to electronic freight transport information used for regulatory purposes. Drone operations contributing to freight data collection must align with these provisions and align with these standardised formats to enable seamless integration into eFTI systems	●
	Art. 8	Grants access to eFTI data only to authorised parties, ensuring data confidentiality and security. Drone operators and the ODP must implement access controls to protect sensitive freight data.	●

Regulation 2017/352	Art. 4	Allows port managing bodies to impose minimum requirements on service providers. Drone operators offering services through this UC ODP, like infrastructure inspections or cargo management. So these requirements must be met.	●
	Art. 6 & 8	Ensures fair, transparent, and non-discriminatory access to port services. Ports to impose public service obligations (PSOs) on providers, including drone operators ensure: Safety and security of operations, Environmental protection, such as pollution monitoring or emission control, continuity of service in critical areas of the port. The ODP must take into account these requirements when selecting drone operator companies.	●
	Art. 15	If drones are introduced as a new technology or service, port authorities must consult users (e.g., shipping companies or terminal operators) about the impact. The project must take into account these requirements when introducing this ODP into the Port.	●
Regulation (EU) 2019/1239: European Maritime Single Window Environment	Art. 3 & 5	Reporting formalities for ships arriving at, staying in, and departing from EU ports. Drone operations indirectly impact this scope when they contribute to data collection for reporting purposes. Drone operators and the ODP must ensure that their data management systems are compatible with this interface to avoid delays or errors.	●
	Art. 6	This ODP and the drone operators must coordinate with stakeholders to ensure proper integration of drone-collected data into the EMSWe.	●
	Art. 9	This ODP and drone operators must adhere to cybersecurity standards to protect sensitive data collected during operations and comply with the data-related regulations specified in the section above.	●

Legenda:

- Relevant, full compliance
- Compliant with potential risks
- Barrier to implementation

Conclusions

The integration of drones in port operations and their alignment with ODPs, is significantly influenced by various European regulations.

The Data Governance Act (EU 2022/868) ensures the secure and fair use of data, particularly in environments like ports where multiple stakeholders interact. Articles 5, 9, and 12 emphasise transparency and neutrality in data sharing, impacting platforms such as FIWARE, which facilitate data exchange. Similarly, the Data Act (EU 2023/2854) mandates fair access to data (Article 4) and sharing obligations (Article 11), requiring clear

agreements for the use of drone-generated data in port logistics. The Interoperable Europe Act (EU 2024/903) further enforces interoperability standards (Article 7) and shared infrastructure (Article 13), ensuring the seamless integration of digital platforms across ports.

From a privacy and security perspective, the GDPR, EU 2016/679 plays a crucial role, particularly concerning drones and AI-driven systems that collect personal or sensitive data. Articles 6 and 25 require lawfulness, transparency, and privacy-by-design principles in data processing, ensuring compliance with stringent data protection obligations. The Digital Services Act (EU 2022/2065) also introduces accountability measures for online platforms managing drone-collected data.

The **Artificial Intelligence Act** introduces rigorous standards for the use of AI in critical infrastructure, directly impacting ODPs managing drone operations in ports. Compliance with the Act's provisions ensures ethical, safe, and transparent AI use while fostering trust among stakeholders. AI systems used in critical infrastructure, such as ports, fall under the **high-risk** category due to their potential impact on safety and security. The Act emphasises the need for human oversight in high-risk AI systems to prevent harm or misuse and mandates the ODP to undergo thorough risk assessments to identify potential hazards, particularly in scenarios involving drones operating near sensitive port infrastructure. It also addresses operational transparency for Stakeholders using the ODP, such as port authorities or logistics operators, to be made aware of the capabilities and limitations of AI-driven tools integrated into the platform.

Regarding drone-specific regulations, EASA Regulation (EU 2019/947) categorises drone operations into risk-based groups, with port activities generally falling under the Specific Category, requiring a risk assessment and operational authorisation (Articles 3, 5, and 12). Additionally, Regulation (EU) 2017/352, governing port services, establishes minimum operational requirements for drone operators (Articles 4 and 6) and mandates fair access to port services while ensuring safety and environmental sustainability.

With increasing digitalisation in maritime logistics, regulations such as the European Maritime Single Window Environment (EMSWe) Regulation (EU 2019/1239) and the Electronic Freight Transport Information Regulation (EU 2020/1056) play a critical role. The EMSWe Regulation streamlines reporting formalities for ships, and drones contribute by enabling vessel inspections, emissions monitoring, and real-time logistical insights (Articles 3, 5, and 9). Similarly, the eFTI Regulation facilitates the electronic exchange of freight information, requiring drone-collected data to comply with standardised formats and cybersecurity measures (Articles 3, 4, and 8).

Despite the regulatory advancements, several challenges persist in integrating drones within port operations. These include technological interoperability, data ownership conflicts, and ensuring cybersecurity compliance. The alignment of drone operations with evolving EU frameworks, such as the European Mobility Data Space (EMDS) and

forthcoming AI regulations, will be pivotal in shaping future port logistics and surveillance capabilities.

In conclusion, while drones offer significant operational benefits in ports, compliance with multiple EU regulations remains a fundamental requirement. Stakeholders must navigate complex legislative landscapes to ensure that drone deployment aligns with safety, transparency, data protection, and interoperability standards, thereby fostering a secure and efficient port ecosystem.

In **Spain**, the reference country for this Use case, the integration of drone technology ports is governed by a combination of national legislation and alignment with EU regulations. The framework focuses on data governance, operational safety, and coordination with port authorities, ensuring both innovation and compliance in sensitive maritime environments.

Spain aligns with the Data Governance Act (DGA) through national legislation such as Ley 18/2022 de Creación y Crecimiento de Empresas and general data transparency laws. These laws facilitate the reuse of public sector data and ensure transparency in data exchanges, crucial for ODPs in port environments.

Regarding drone operations, Royal Decree 517/2024, published on June 4, 2024, establishes the primary legal framework for the civil use of UAS in Spain. This decree harmonises Spanish law with EASA Regulation (EU) 2019/947 and repeals previous regulations, such as Royal Decree 1036/2017 and Chapter XI of Royal Decree 1180/2018. The decree outlines specific requirements for drone operations in controlled spaces, including ports.

It is important to consider that the **Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (AESA)** is the principal regulatory body overseeing drone operations in Spain. AESA provides detailed guidelines for drone operators, particularly concerning operations in sensitive environments like ports and it will secure specific operational permissions, and the compliance with both national and local regulations.

3.5.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCV. The governance model analysis explores what a viable governance model could look like to allow different stakeholders to participate successfully in the ODP despite diverging interest and commitment levels, while ensuring ODP operation compliance in the existing regulatory environment.

The UCV proposes several advanced digital services enabled by the ODP that rely on resources provided by different stakeholders and deliver specific benefits to them. A suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately

provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met.

Stakeholder analysis

A first step in the governance model analysis is to understand better how the different ODP services benefit the various stakeholders and what resources they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating.

The Table 33 below captures the relationship between the proposed ODP services and identified stakeholders. Stakeholders considered in this analysis include:

- Port Authorities (PA)
- Logistics Companies (LC)
- Shipping Operators (SO)
- Customs Authorities (CA)
- Port Staff (PS)

It is assumed that the ODP operator provides all services as part of the ODP. Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, while others may not directly participate but still benefit from them.

Table 33 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	End user	Beneficiaries
Real-time resource allocation & scheduling	ODP operator	SO, CA	PA, PS
Enhanced security and compliance monitoring	ODP operator	PA, PS	LC
Optimisation of energy consumption and waste management	ODP operator	PA	SO
Facilitate inspections and compliance checks	ODP operator	CA	-

Based on this initial analysis, the role of each stakeholder in the ODP can now be determined. Table 34 below shows their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table, and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 34 Stakeholders' role in ODP

Stakeholder	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
PA	ODP provider	Real-time operational data from AI-driven cameras and drones & schedules.	Efficient port operation & overseeing all activities.
PS	End user of some ODP services	Operational status, equipment condition, and work schedules.	Real-time optimisation of operational tasks and workflows. Additional safety.

SO	End user of ODP real-time resource allocation & scheduling	Distribution of goods (arrival, departure)	Operational time savings, available resources, and schedules optimisation
CA	End user of ODP real-time resource allocation & scheduling	Regulation and requirements	Facilitate inspections and compliance checks
LC	End user of ODP integration into existing digital platforms	Shipment schedules	Real-time updates on traffic conditions and potential delays

Finally, Table 35 below examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 35 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
PA	Expected to have minimal reservations and resolve them for other stakeholders: provide conditions for pilot testing, attract installation companies, and provide a platform for sharing their data.
PS	Possible reluctance to share their operational data, privacy concerns.
SO	Minimal (already sharing the data with the PA).
LC	Minimal (already sharing the data with the PA).
CA	None.

Ownership and legal form of ODP platform operator

The ODP is directly managed by the Port Authority, ensuring alignment with port governance, security protocols, and operational strategies. Instead of an independent external provider, the platform remains under the direct oversight of the PA, which is responsible for maintaining the digital infrastructure, managing service delivery, and ensuring compliance with evolving EU regulatory requirements for port operations, safety, and environmental standards.

By keeping the ODP under Port Authority control, the governance model fosters trust among port stakeholders, including port staff, ship operators, logistics companies, and customs authorities, ensuring seamless integration and cooperation. This centralised management model enhances data security, operational transparency, and interoperability with the port's existing digital infrastructure.

Governance Model and Ownership

The most suitable model for operating the Smart Port ODP is a publicly governed, Port Authority-managed digital infrastructure, ensuring that the platform serves the interests of all port stakeholders. While the PA holds direct operational control, collaborative governance mechanisms may be established to incorporate input from logistics companies, ship operators, customs authorities, and port staff representatives, ensuring a balanced stakeholder ecosystem.

The primary objectives of the Smart Port ODP include:

- Providing a centralised, AI-powered digital infrastructure for real-time port monitoring and operational decision-making.
- Ensuring compliance with EU regulations on port safety, emissions tracking, and customs integration.
- Offering advanced AI-based monitoring services, including real-time surveillance via AI cameras and drones.
- Facilitating seamless data integration into the Port's digital platform, enabling comprehensive analysis and visualisation for efficient management.

A for-profit structure controlled by a private entity would add an unnecessary additional layer to complex port operations and likely increase costs and the security of port operations. Instead, a Port Authority-managed ODP ensures transparency, security, and adherence to regulatory frameworks, maximising value for all port stakeholders while aligning with public policy objectives.

Regulatory governance consideration

The UC operates in a strong regulatory environment cutting across sectors and territories. Therefore, the governance of the ODP needs to have compliance with relevant regulations at its core.

The analysis of the ODP services from regulatory governance angle identifies the following areas for regulation as key concerns:

- **Data Protection and Cross-Border Data Flows:** The ODP will handle sensitive port operations data, including real-time surveillance, logistics, and emissions monitoring. It must comply with the GDPR.
- **Port Safety and Environmental Compliance:** The platform must align with EU and international safety and environmental policies, including the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) and EU regulations on port security and emissions monitoring.

- **Customs and Trade Procedures:** Since the platform integrates real-time logistics and emissions tracking, it must comply with EU customs and trade regulations, including EFTI Regulation (Electronic Freight Transport Information).

A possible way to make regulatory compliance easier is to setup an advisory board consisting of representatives of key regulators to aid the alignment with existing national and European regulations and directives. While not actively involved in the supervision of the ODP, they can ensure that supervisory boards are equipped with the up-to-date knowledge concerning any applicable regulations.

3.6 Use case VI: Carbon footprint of port supply chain

3.6.1 Use case identification and scope

The CF of Port Supply Chain UC focuses on establishing a standardised, transparent, and verifiable methodology for tracking and managing carbon emissions in logistics, particularly within port operations. Given the critical role of ports as transport and energy hubs, this UC proposes an ODP that integrates real-time and historical data from diverse sources such as shipping emissions, fuel consumption, cargo tracking, and multimodal transportation data. The platform aims to bridge the gap in emissions tracking by automating data collection from ships, trucks, and port equipment, ensuring a comprehensive and reliable CF calculation.

Through cross-border data harmonisation, the platform facilitates seamless data exchange between stakeholders, ensuring compliance with EU environmental regulations such as GDPR and the IMO guidelines for emissions tracking. Additionally, route optimisation services support logistics operators in reducing emissions by selecting the most sustainable transport routes. By integrating blockchain technology, the ODP enhances data transparency, trust, and accountability among stakeholders, fostering collaboration and regulatory compliance. Ultimately, this UC supports the logistics sector's green transition, promoting sustainable business practices and contributing to the EU's long-term environmental goals.

3.6.2 Actors of the Use Case

The abovementioned logistics operations involve multiple actors and transportation modes, creating complexity in carbon accounting as proposed in Table 36. The ODP integrates data from various sources, including ships, trucks, and port equipment, ensuring real-time data acquisition and analysis.

Table 36 Main actors and actions involved in Use Case VI

Actor Name	Actor Type	Actor description	Actions	Standards
Manufacturer	Role	Generic manufacturer of goods that require maritime transport and logistic services	It registers the CF of its products at the final point of manufacture. Check out the Custom and Border Protection (CBP) to find the logistics operator with the best price/emissions ratio.	No
Consumer/Citizen	Role	Consumer of goods	Check the final CF of their products (e.g., QR code) on the platform.	No
Logistic Operator	Role	Support companies with transportation, storage, shipment, and distribution of goods	Access CBP to offer different transport mechanisms and routes. Access the GL to audit CF of maritime transport services. Check the historical CF of transport operations.	No
Maritime Transport Service	Role	Waterborne transport of goods (cargo) via waterways	Register the energy consumption (e.g., fuel) of transport operations (routes, duration, load...)	No
Port Authority	Role	Public manager of the port (operation and maintenance)	Access the CBP to know the CF impact of different transport operations to/from the port	No

3.6.3 Diagram of the Use Case and scenarios

The diagram of the UCVI is presented in Figure 20. Actors' scenarios' descriptions are presented in Table 37.

Figure 20 Diagram of Use Case VI

Table 37 Descriptive scenarios of Use Case VI

S.No	Scenario Name	Triggering Event	Scenario Description	Primary Actor
BEG.VI.S1	New route completed	Route completed: goods have arrived at the destination port	The transport service accesses the platform and registers the route updates, arriving time, and remaining fuel/energy. The platform updates the CF of transported goods and informs logistic operators and Port Authorities involved. The customer can track the CF of his order if the manufacturer (or seller) has provided him with the code.	Maritime Transport Service
BEG.VI.S2	Audit Port CF operations	The Port Authority audits the annual CF of transport operations	Download of annual CF indicators and savings (in case of smart services)	Port Authority

3.6.4 Challenges and mitigation measures

The challenges and mitigation measures of UCVI are illustrated in Table 38:

Table 38 Challenges and mitigation measures of Use Case VI

Challenges	Mitigation measures
Integration with existing legacy systems: Integrating the ODP with existing legacy systems poses a significant challenge, as these systems may use outdated data formats, proprietary protocols, and often lack the capabilities required for modern integration. These factors create barriers to seamless data exchange and platform adoption.	The ODP employs standardised open APIs and modular integration to enable seamless data exchange with legacy systems. Specifically, the use of edge gateways helps to bridge the gap between older infrastructure and the modern platform by translating proprietary data formats into standardised, interoperable formats. The edge gateways are capable of preprocessing data locally, which minimises the load on legacy systems while ensuring that only validated and standardised information is forwarded to the ODP.
CF calculation methods: The lack of standardised methodologies for calculating carbon emissions across different transportation modes (e.g., ships, trucks, port equipment) leads to data discrepancies and unreliable CF figures. These inconsistencies complicate decision-making for logistics operators and stakeholders across the supply chain.	The ODP enforces the use of standardised CF calculation methods compliant with IMO and EU guidelines. By integrating a CF Calculation Microservice, the platform ensures that emissions are calculated using uniform parameters across the logistics chain, regardless of the transportation mode. This results in consistent and comparable CF data, improving transparency and reliability for all stakeholders
Data privacy and regulatory issues: Ensuring privacy, GDPR compliance and safeguarding sensitive logistics data across borders is a significant challenge, especially	The ODP enforces strict Identity and IAM services, compliant with eIDAS standards, to secure user authentication and authorisation. Additionally, edge computing technologies are utilised to process sensitive data locally, reducing the

when dealing with real-time data exchanges and cross-border operations. Inadequate data security measures can lead to privacy breaches and non-compliance with EU regulations	need for transferring data across borders and ensuring compliance with GDPR regulations. This approach minimises the risk of data breaches while ensuring that only authorised users have access to critical CF data
Cross-border data exchange: Varying national regulations and legacy systems make cross-border data exchange difficult. This regulatory and technical fragmentation complicates real-time CF tracking, leading to delays and inefficiencies in managing logistics operations.	To address these challenges, the ODP leverages GAIA-X and eDelivery-compliant services to create a trusted framework for cross-border data exchange. GAIA-X ensures a standardised approach to data governance, providing unified policies that make cross-border sharing more consistent and trustworthy. Additionally, data sovereignty filters are applied to control the flow of data based on national regulations, ensuring that sensitive data is only shared in compliance with local laws.
Scalability and performance stability: As logistics operations grow in complexity, the platform must handle increasing data volumes and efficiently integrate innovative technologies and legacy systems. Scaling these systems without compromising performance and security can be a major challenge.	The ODP is designed with scalability in mind, enabling the system to dynamically scale as needed. Edge computing also helps distribute the processing load, ensuring that data is handled locally before being transmitted to the central ODP. This architecture enables seamless integration of legacy systems while maintaining high availability and performance
Stakeholder engagement and adoption: Encouraging adoption of the ODP by various stakeholders, including port authorities, logistics operators, and government agencies, presents a significant challenge, especially given the varying levels of technological maturity, resource availability, and perceived value among these stakeholders. Resistance to change and the upfront costs of transitioning from traditional systems to the ODP can also hinder widespread adoption.	The ODP aims to provide a user-friendly interface and various levels of technical support to ensure broad adoption. Stakeholder engagement initiatives, such as workshops, hands-on training sessions, and pilot programs, are planned to demonstrate the platform's value. Financial incentives or subsidies may also be offered to offset the costs of adoption for smaller logistics operators. Effective communication of the benefits, along with a phased onboarding process that allows stakeholders to gradually integrate the ODP into their operations without significant disruption, will help drive stakeholder buy-in and promote widespread adoption.

3.6.5 Modular architecture specification

Perception layer

The Perception layer in the current UC deals with real-time data collection from **IoT devices** deployed across the logistics chain. These devices include sensors on **ships, trucks, and port equipment** and collect a wide range of data that reflects the operational efficiency and environmental impact of logistics activities. For example, ship sensors monitor fuel consumption, GPS location, and engine performance, while truck sensors capture route data, cargo weight, and condition. In the port itself, sensors track energy usage. All this data is gathered using standardised communication protocols like MQTT and HTTPS, ensuring secure transmission across the network.

What's crucial here is that the devices use digital certificates to securely transmit their data, enhancing trust and preventing unauthorised access. These certificates help

maintain a chain of trust, ensuring that the data is accurate and authentic from the moment it is captured. Automated device registration and firmware monitoring ensure that devices remain secure, while operational flows based on sensor data allow real-time decision-making. This layer is instrumental in enabling accurate CF calculations, which are vital for reducing emissions and promoting sustainability in the logistics chain.

Middleware layer

The Middleware Layer serves as the core integration and processing hub, ensuring seamless interoperability between the Perception Layer and higher-level services. This layer is responsible for data ingestion, transformation, validation, and secure exchange, enabling efficient communication between various stakeholders, including port authorities, shipping companies, and regulatory bodies.

The Messaging Broker enables asynchronous data flow between components, allowing the system to handle large-scale, real-time emissions tracking efficiently. The API Gateway provides a secure interface for external integrations, enabling authorised stakeholders to access emissions data, generate reports, and receive optimisation insights. Additionally, data sovereignty mechanisms enforce GDPR and regulatory compliance by defining role-based access and secure cross-border data sharing policies. The Data Space Adapter further enables integration with external data spaces such as Gaia-X, fostering interoperability and cross-sector collaboration for a standardised approach to CF tracking. Ultimately, this layer acts as the backbone of the ODP, enabling reliable, secure, and scalable emissions monitoring and optimisation in port logistics.

Service layer

The Service Layer forms the core of the Operational Data Platform (ODP) by handling critical services such as data validation microservice, CF calculation microservice, cloud data lake, and route optimisation. These services are essential for ensuring the accuracy, security, and efficiency of the platform, which integrates data from multiple stakeholders in the logistics sector.

The **Data Validation Microservice** is responsible for ensuring the accuracy, integrity, and consistency of the data collected from IoT devices. In UCVI, the large volume of data gathered from different transportation modes makes data validation a crucial step in the process. The microservice performs real-time anomaly detection to identify discrepancies in the incoming data streams, such as sensor malfunctions or transmission errors. It uses standardised checksums and validation rules aligned with EU-wide BEGONIA schemas to verify the authenticity and compliance of the data before it is processed further. By validating data in real-time, this microservice ensures that only accurate and consistent data is used for CF calculations and route optimisation. It also enhances interoperability between stakeholders by adhering to a common data structure, which allows seamless data exchange between different logistics actors and systems.

The **CF Calculation Microservice** automates the process of calculating carbon emissions based on data collected from various transportation modes. This microservice integrates national and EU-level parameters into the calculation process, ensuring compliance with the latest regulatory frameworks and standards, such as the guidelines set by the IMO for shipping emissions. The CF Calculation Microservice processes data such as fuel consumption, cargo weight, vehicle type, and route information to determine the CF of each leg of a shipment's journey. For example, emissions from ships are calculated based on fuel usage and distance travelled, while trucks' emissions are based on fuel consumption, cargo load, and the efficiency of the route taken. This microservice provides dynamic, real-time reporting of emissions through API calls, allowing stakeholders to access up-to-date CF information. The availability of real-time data supports informed decision-making, enabling logistics operators to adjust their operations to reduce emissions and comply with environmental regulations. Additionally, the CF Calculation Microservice integrates with route optimisation services, using CF data to suggest sustainable and emissions-efficient routes for goods transport.

The **Route Optimisation Microservice** is a key component of the Application Layer, designed to optimise the transport routes for logistics operators, ensuring that the most carbon-efficient and cost-effective routes are selected for goods transport. This microservice utilises real-time data such as traffic conditions, fuel prices, and weather information, along with the CF data generated by the CF Calculation Microservice, to provide actionable recommendations. The route optimisation service also leverages port-specific factors, such as available bunkering facilities, refuelling stations, and port congestion. By considering these dynamic variables, the microservice generates optimal routes that reduce fuel consumption, minimise traffic delays, and ensure compliance with EU regulations on emissions. The integration of CF data into the route optimisation process ensures that logistics operators can make sustainable choices that not only meet their operational needs but also contribute to reducing overall emissions in the supply chain.

Finally, the **Cloud Data Lake** provides secure, scalable storage for all the data collected, processed, and analysed by the ODP. It is a multi-tenant object storage system deployed within the public cloud, allowing stakeholders across the logistics network to store and access vast volumes of sensor data, CF metrics, and route optimisation insights. The Cloud Data Lake is designed to support real-time data streaming. In the UC, the Cloud Data Lake plays a vital role in facilitating cross-border data operations, enabling seamless integration of data from ports, vehicles, and equipment across multiple EU jurisdictions. This ensures that logistics operators and port authorities can access both real-time and historical data, helping them analyze trends, optimise operations, and make evidence-based decisions to reduce emissions. The data lake is compliant with GAIA-X standards and the GDPR, ensuring that sensitive data is stored securely and handled in accordance with EU regulations. The combination of real-time data streaming and cloud storage

allows stakeholders to access up-to-date CF and route optimisation data while maintaining a long-term archive for analysis and reporting. This enables the logistics sector to monitor its progress toward sustainability goals, optimise resource allocation, and meet regulatory requirements for emissions reporting.

Also, in the service layer, **blockchain** is integrated to ensure data integrity, traceability, and trust across the ODP. By providing an immutable ledger for CF transactions and other key interactions, blockchain guarantees that stakeholders can verify data accuracy and compliance throughout the logistics chain. This secure record-keeping builds transparency, fostering confidence among cross-border stakeholders and supporting EU regulatory requirements.

Business layer

The business layer is responsible for managing business logic, reporting, and user interfaces, facilitating decision-making based on the data collected, processed, and analysed by the platform. Key services in the Business Layer include the blockchain network for data integrity, the User Interface (UI) for accessibility and usability, and the Reporting and Analytics Microservice for insights and regulatory compliance.

At the heart of the Business Layer is the blockchain network, which provides a distributed ledger for managing CF transaction event logging. Blockchain is used to ensure data integrity and traceability across the entire CF tracking process, making the CF data immutable, transparent, and auditable. This transparency is critical for building trust among stakeholders, including port authorities, transport operators, logistics companies, regulatory bodies, and even end consumers. In the UC, the blockchain network is employed to log all significant events related to the CF, such as emissions data collected at various stages of the logistics process, fuel consumption records, and route optimisation decisions. These records are timestamped and stored in an immutable format, ensuring that the data cannot be tampered with or altered after it is recorded.

The User Interface (UI) is designed to be user-friendly and accessible, offering a streamlined experience for both technical and non-technical users across the logistics sector. The UI provides stakeholders with real-time access to critical data, such as CF metrics, route optimisation insights, and compliance reports. The goal of the UI is to facilitate decision-making by presenting complex data in a way that is easily understandable and actionable. The UI is tailored to the needs of different user groups, such as logistics operators, port authorities, and regulatory bodies. For logistics operators, the UI offers personalised dashboards that display KPIs, including real-time carbon emissions, fuel consumption, and route efficiency. These dashboards allow operators to make quick, data-driven decisions to optimise their logistics operations and reduce emissions. For port authorities and regulatory bodies, the UI provides detailed compliance reports and long-term CF data, helping them monitor sustainability efforts and ensure that emissions targets are being met.

Also, reporting and analytics provide stakeholders with automated reporting capabilities and deep insights into the logistics operations. This microservice processes the data stored in the Cloud Data Lake and generates reports on critical metrics such as carbon emissions, operational efficiency, and compliance with environmental regulations. It enables logistics companies and authorities to generate both real-time and historical reports, supporting data-driven decision-making. This microservice integrates with the platform's secure APIs, ensuring that reports can be accessed by authorised users while maintaining data privacy and security. These reports are designed to meet the specific requirements of different stakeholders.

Holistic view and interactions

The ODP for UCVI is designed as a tightly integrated, multi-layered architecture that enables seamless data flow from raw collection to actionable insights, supporting CF tracking across the logistics sector. Each layer is interconnected to ensure efficiency, reliability, and transparency, working collectively to address the complexities of cross-border data exchange, compliance, and carbon emissions accountability in EU port operations.

The **Perception Layer** initiates this flow by gathering real-time data from IoT sensors deployed across ships, trucks, and port equipment. These sensors capture critical metrics, which are fundamental to calculating the CF of logistics activities. To streamline the data processing, the Perception Layer performs initial data collection and ensures secure transmission using standardised protocols, thereby setting a foundation of reliable, high-quality data.

The Middleware Layer functions as the platform's communication backbone, managing data exchange between layers and external systems with a focus on regulatory compliance and secure data handling. This layer routes data requests via secure APIs and enforces data sovereignty measures, ensuring that all transactions adhere to EU standards like GDPR and eIDAS. The Middleware Layer's integration with eDelivery-compliant services further facilitates trusted cross-border data sharing, supporting the flow of information across different national and organisational systems. This secure data exchange establishes a reliable channel for inter-layer and stakeholder communication, enabling cohesive data interaction throughout the platform.

Validated data from the Middleware Layer is then utilised by **the Application Layer**, which powers the ODP's core services, including CF calculation, real-time anomaly detection, route optimisation, and data validation. Leveraging standardised and preprocessed data from the Data Layer, the Application Layer executes accurate, consistent CF calculations, supporting precise reporting and actionable recommendations for reducing emissions. This layer also provides stakeholders with tools for real-time decision-making, aligning with sustainability goals through services like

adaptive route optimisation, which balances efficiency with reduced environmental impact.

Finally, **the Business Layer** translates these outputs into accessible, actionable insights for stakeholders. Utilising blockchain technology, the Business Layer provides an immutable ledger for all CF-related transactions, enhancing traceability, accountability, and trust among logistics operators, port authorities, and regulatory bodies. Through a user-friendly interface, stakeholders gain access to real-time data visualisations, detailed compliance reports, and predictive analytics, empowering them to make informed, data-driven decisions. This layer ensures that data insights are not only accessible but also presented transparently, fostering trust across cross-border collaborations.

In this integrated system, each layer is interdependent, contributing essential functionalities to create a unified, efficient, and transparent platform. By linking real-time data acquisition with secure data exchange, rigorous validation, and actionable reporting, the ODP promotes an interoperable logistics network aligned with the EU’s sustainability and regulatory standards. This interconnected approach enables seamless data flow from raw sensor data to strategic decision-making, supporting the creation of a robust, data-driven CF tracking system that enhances transparency, sustainability, and operational efficiency across EU logistics operations.

Figure 21 below illustrates some basic interactions between the two upper layers of the architecture.

Figure 21 Holistic view and interactions between the layers of Use Case VI

3.6.6 Schematics

The graphical representation of the proposed architecture layers is depicted in the following Figure 22:

Figure 22 Proposed layered architecture of Use Case VI

3.6.7 Policy and regulatory analysis

Specific details about the policy and regulatory analysis of Use Case VI are illustrated in Table 39 below:

Table 39 Regulatory aspects of Use Case VI

Regulation/ standard	Article/ section	Relevance for the UC and Notes	Impact evaluation
Data Governance Act (DGA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/868	Art. 5, 6 & 11	Framework for neutral and transparent data sharing across borders ensuring the platform acts as a fair data intermediary, and facilitating harmonised cross-border sharing of CF and logistics data.	●
Data Act – Regulation (EU) 2023/2854	Art. 4, 5, 6 & 11	Regulates access, sharing, and fairness in data usage, mandating access for platform users to essential logistics and emissions data, ensuring fair data sharing agreements, and safeguarding cross-sector data use without regulatory conflicts.	●
Interoperable Europe Act – Regulation (EU) 2024/903	Art. 3, 4, 6 & 8.	Ensures cross-border interoperability of digital platforms, aligning with EU-wide interoperability standards, applying the adoption of harmonised technical specifications, and with determined agreements between public and private stakeholders for seamless cooperation.	●
Digital Markets Act (DMA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/1925	Art. 5, 6 & 7	Promotes fair competition and interoperability, preventing dominant platforms from restricting access to logistics and emissions data, establishing interoperability with other systems, and enabling the platform to connect with related services.	●
Digital Services Act (DSA) – Regulation (EU) 2022/2065	Art. 8 & 23	Enhances transparency and accountability, requiring clear communication about CF calculations and data handling and obligating platforms to mitigate risks like misinformation or inaccurate data.	●
General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Regulation (EU) 2018/1725	Art. 5, 25 & 35	Protects personal data and privacy with lawful and transparent data processing, Embeds privacy safeguards in the platform’s design, and mandates robust cybersecurity to protect user data.	●
eIDAS – Regulation (EU) No 910/2014	Art. 6 & 12	Provides secure and trustworthy digital interactions. Supports the use of electronic signatures to validate carbon data, and ensures interoperability of trust services for cross-border transactions.	●
NIS 2 Directive – Directive (EU) 2022/2555	Art. 2, 3, 21 & 23	Strengthens cybersecurity for critical actors, identifying logistics operators and port authorities as essential entities, mandates robust cybersecurity risk management, and requires timely incident reporting.	●
Energy Efficiency Directive – (EU) 2023/955	Art. 11 & 22	Promotes sustainable logistics practices, encouraging route optimisation to reduce emissions, and supporting monitoring and reporting	●

		of energy use, directly aligning with sustainability goals.	
<i>New Network Code on Cybersecurity for the EU Electricity Sector - Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1366</i>	Art. 3, 5 & 8	Ensures cybersecurity of data exchanges, particularly if involving energy infrastructure.	●
<i>Directive 2014/61/EU on measures to reduce the cost of deploying high-speed electronic communications networks</i>	Art. 3	Facilitates cost-effective deployment of high-speed networks, essential for efficient data communication.	●
<i>IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from ships, May 2018</i>		Sets a target to reduce total annual greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from international shipping by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008 levels.	●
<i>Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI)</i>		Energy efficiency requirements for existing ships and new vessels.	●
<i>Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) Rating System</i>		Operational measure to rate ships based on their carbon intensity, encouraging vessels to continuously improve their energy efficiency.	●
<i>Regulation (EU) 2020/1056 - eFTI</i>	Art. 5,6, 7,8 &9	Framework for efficient, secure, and standardised use of electronic freight transport information across the EU.	●
<i>Directive 2003/87/EC & Directive 2023/959 - Emission Trading System (ETS) Directive</i>	Art. 1, Art. 14 and Annex IV	The inclusion of maritime transport in the ETS underscores the EU's commitment to reducing the CF of this sector and promoting sustainable shipping practices.	●
<i>Regulation (EU) 2017/352 for Ports services</i>	Art. 7 & Art 13.	Environmental standards for port services providers. Charges based on environmental performance.	●
<i>Commission Recommendation 2021/2279 - Environmental footprint methods</i>		Accounting for emissions and energy use during the transport of goods as part of a product's overall environmental footprint. The choice of transport mode can significantly alter the Life Cycle and CF results of goods.	●

Legenda:

- Relevant, full compliance
- Compliant with potential risks
- Barrier to implementation

Conclusions

The logistics and maritime industries are increasingly regulated by European and international policies to ensure data transparency, interoperability, cybersecurity, and environmental sustainability. This section synthesises the relevant legislation and its impact on logistics platform designed for data sharing, CF calculation, and optimised freight operations.

The Data Governance Act (DGA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/868) establishes transparency and fairness in data sharing ecosystems, emphasising cross-border interoperability and secure data reuse. Key provisions include conditions for data intermediaries (Art. 5), fair fee structures (Art. 6), and cross-border sharing (Art. 11). Similarly, the Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854) mandates fair data access for users (Art. 4) and technical protections against unauthorised use (Art. 11). The Interoperable Europe Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/903) reinforces data exchange standards (Art. 3 & 6), facilitating seamless integration across digital platforms.

The Digital Markets Act (DMA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/1925) and Digital Services Act (DSA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065) prevent gatekeeping behaviours and ensure accountability in data usage, with obligations for transparency (Art. 8, DSA) and interoperability (Art. 7, DMA). These acts complement eFTI Regulation (EU) 2020/1056, which promotes secure and interoperable digital freight documentation systems.

The platform aligns with the Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2023/955 and IMO frameworks like the EEXI and EEDI (Energy Efficiency Design Index), supporting carbon-efficient operations and the transition to sustainable shipping practices. The EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) expands to cover maritime emissions, incentivising decarbonisation efforts. Moreover, compliance with the Environmental Footprint methods (EU 2021/2279) ensures robust life cycle assessments of transport modes and emissions.

To meet the NIS 2 Directive (EU) 2022/2555 and GDPR standards, the platform integrates advanced cybersecurity and privacy measures, ensuring lawful and secure data processing (Art. 25, GDPR) and risk management (Art. 21, NIS 2). Blockchain technology underpins data traceability and confidentiality, meeting the requirements of eFTI Articles 6-9.

Aligned with Regulation (EU) 2017/352, the platform incentivises energy-efficient vessels through transparent infrastructure charging, while leveraging real-time tracking tools to monitor compliance with the IMO's marine pollution convention.

This comprehensive regulatory alignment ensures the platform's operational efficiency, promotes sustainable practices, and builds trust among stakeholders while fostering a data-driven logistics ecosystem in line with EU and global policies.

3.6.8 Governance aspects

This section explores a potential governance model for an ODP that enables UCVI. The governance model analysis explores what a viable governance model could look like to allow different stakeholders to participate successfully in the ODP despite diverging interest and commitment levels, while ensuring ODP operation compliance in the existing regulatory environment.

The UCVI proposes several advanced digital services enabled by the ODP that rely on resources provided by different stakeholders and deliver specific benefits to them. A suitable governance model must ensure the stakeholders' various (potentially conflicting) needs and expectations are met and that promised services/resources are adequately provided and delivered. It also needs to ensure trust between participants and that the expected outcomes of the ODP are successfully met.

Stakeholder analysis

A first step in the governance model analysis is to understand better how the different ODP services benefit the various stakeholders and what resources they rely upon. We can then better understand what roles the different stakeholders play when participating in the ODP and what concerns might prevent them from participating.

The Table 40 below captures the relationship between the proposed ODP services and identified stakeholders. The stakeholders considered in this analysis include:

- External ODP Provider
- Port Authorities & Operators (PA)
- Logistics & Freight Companies (LO) –
- Shipping & Transport Operators –
- Customs & Trade Authorities –
- Manufacturers & Exporters (Manf)

It is assumed that the ODP operator provides all services as part of the ODP. Some stakeholders are directly involved as end users of the services, while others may not directly participate but still benefit from them.

Table 40 Relationship between ODP services and stakeholders

ODP Service	Provider	End user	Beneficiaries
Reduce CF in logistic operations	ODP operator	PA, MTS, LO	Manf.
Label to track the CF of the product	ODP operator	Cons.	Manf.
Real-time verification of CF calculation	ODP operator	PA, MTS, LO	
Competitiveness between different transport services	ODP operator	MTS	LO
Optimisation of transport route by reducing fuel consumption	ODP operator	MTS	

Based on this initial analysis, the role of each stakeholder in the ODP can now be determined. Table 41 shows their role in the ODP, what resources they would need to bring to the table and what benefits they may obtain from participation.

Table 41 Stakeholders' role in the ODP

Stakeholder	Role in ODP	Resource input	Benefits
External ODP Provider	ODP operator. Develops, manages, and maintains the platform as a neutral service provider.	Platform infrastructure, digital services, maintenance	Revenue from service provision, strengthened industry trust, scalable model
Port Authorities (PA)	Strategic partners and end users of the ODP	Operations data from port environments	Improved sustainability, competitiveness, compliance support, and funding access
Multimodal Transport Services (MTS)	End user of some ODP services	Energy consumption data from transport operations	Cheaper energy use, optimised emissions footprint, improved service efficiency
Logistics Operators (LO)	End user of some ODP services	Shipment, storage, and distribution data	Fuel and operational savings, better emissions reporting
Manufacturers (Manf)	Indirect beneficiaries, no direct platform use	Product CF data	Informed selection of greener logistics services

Finally, the Table 42 examines the reservations or concerns of different stakeholders towards participating in an ODP. A suitable governance approach should be able to address these adequately.

Table 42 Reservations of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Reservations
External ODP Provider	Needs strong stakeholder buy-in and long-term service agreements to ensure platform viability. Must guarantee data security, interoperability, and transparent governance to gain trust.
Port Authorities (PA)	May hesitate due to loss of ownership/control over the platform. Concerned about alignment with their infrastructure and regulatory obligations. Require guarantees on data sovereignty and service continuity.
Multimodal Transport Services (MTS)	Concerns about sharing operational data with a third-party entity. May fear exposure of sensitive logistics information. Assurance of data privacy, fair access, and competitive neutrality are an issue as well.
Logistics Operators (LO)	Similar to MTS: hesitant to share operational data, especially with external entities. Require incentives and proof of benefit before active participation.
Manufacturers (Manf.)	Minimal concerns. Expect accuracy and reliability of data received from the platform.

Ownership and legal form of ODP platform operator

The ODP for CF tracking, fuel optimisation, and multimodal logistics efficiency is a critical enabler of sustainable logistics. While PAs remain central actors in implementing and

benefiting from the platform, the ODP is no longer directly operated or owned by individual PAs.

Instead, the platform is managed by an external, neutral ODP provider, established specifically to ensure transparency, neutrality, and interoperability across multiple ports and logistics stakeholders. This external entity is responsible for maintaining the digital infrastructure, managing service delivery, and aligning evolving EU regulatory requirements.

By entrusting the ODP to an independent provider, the governance model encourages participation from multiple ports, including those who may otherwise hesitate to adopt a platform owned by a competing authority. This neutral positioning enhances trust and facilitates broader adoption, leading to greater standardisation and cross-border collaboration in the green transition of logistics.

Governance Model and Ownership

The most suitable model for operating the ODP is a **non-profit, independent legal entity** (e.g., association, cooperative, or foundation) composed of relevant stakeholders across the logistics ecosystem, including Port Authorities, transport operators, and possibly public sector actors. The platform could also be operated by a **private company** under strict governance agreements and stakeholder oversight to maintain neutrality.

This approach ensures that:

- The platform's development and operation serve the **collective interest** of all participants.
- Port Authorities, logistics companies, and manufacturers are treated as **equal partners and clients**, not subordinates to a single port or dominant actor.
- **Conflicts of interest are minimised**, encouraging wider adoption and cooperation.

The entity's **primary objectives** are to:

- Provide a **neutral, trustworthy digital infrastructure** for sustainable logistics.
- Facilitate compliance with **EU decarbonisation and digitalisation targets** (CBAM, ETS, FuelEU Maritime, EFTI).
- Offer **value-added services** (e.g., emissions reporting, route optimisation, CF labeling) to improve competitiveness across the supply chain.
- Enable **data standardisation and interoperability** across multiple ports and logistics hubs.

A for-profit structure, especially one controlled by a single stakeholder, would risk limiting the perceived neutrality and trust required for broad participation. In contrast, a not-for-profit governance model ensures that the platform operates as a shared digital utility,

maximising value creation for the entire logistics ecosystem while aligning with environmental and public policy objectives.

Regulatory governance consideration

This UC operates within a highly regulated space that intersects **transport logistics, environmental policy, and digital data governance**. As such, the governance of the ODP must ensure **full compliance with relevant EU and national regulations**, particularly those related to carbon emissions reporting, data exchange, and cross-border operations in the logistics sector.

With the platform now managed by an **external, neutral provider**, regulatory alignment becomes even more critical to ensure **institutional trust** and **legal certainty** for all stakeholders, especially Port Authorities, logistics operators, and customs/trade authorities.

The analysis of the ODP services from the regulatory governance angle identifies the following areas for regulation as key concerns:

Data Protection and Cross-Border Data Flows: The ODP will handle sensitive logistics, emissions, and operational data from multiple jurisdictions. It must fully comply with:

- The GDPR – ensuring lawful processing, consent management, and user rights.
- The Data Governance Act – facilitating secure and standardised cross-border data access and sharing between actors, including public and private entities.

Carbon Emissions Reporting & Regulatory Instruments: The platform must align with key EU decarbonisation policies that affect transport and trade logistics, including:

- CBAM (Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism): Ensures proper emissions tracking for imported/exported goods.
- EU ETS (Emissions Trading System): May require traceability of carbon-intensive transport operations linked to traded goods.
- FuelEU Maritime: Affects shipping emissions and reporting requirements in port operations.
- EFTI Regulation (Electronic Freight Transport Information): Governs the digital exchange of freight transport documentation, ensuring interoperability and compliance during inspections or customs processes.

Customs and Trade Procedures: Since the platform supports carbon tracking at the product or shipment level, it must respect the procedural and digital integration rules set by customs and trade authorities. This includes:

- Integration with single window systems for customs,
- Compliance with EU trade facilitation measures,

- And recognition of digital documents in official inspections and verifications.

To ensure long-term regulatory alignment and institutional trust, the ODP governance model should include a **Regulatory Advisory Board** composed of representatives from EU regulatory bodies (e.g., DG MOVE, DG CLIMA, DG TAXUD), national authorities in customs, transport, and data protection, as well as relevant standardisation organisations. Although this board would serve in a non-supervisory role, it would play a key role in advising the ODP operator and supervisory board on legal compliance, emerging regulatory changes, and implementation of best practices. Its involvement would help the platform stay up to date with evolving EU legislation, particularly in areas such as data protection, emissions tracking, and electronic freight documentation, while supporting consistent application of standards across multiple ports and countries.

Embedding such a regulatory governance mechanism into the ODP's structure will strengthen the platform's legitimacy, increase stakeholder confidence, and facilitate broader adoption across the logistics ecosystem. By ensuring that legal compliance is proactively addressed, the ODP reduces risks for its users, especially Port Authorities and logistics operators, who must navigate strict environmental and trade regulations. Moreover, the presence of a trusted, expert advisory board reinforces the platform's **neutrality and credibility**, positioning it as a reliable tool for emissions transparency, trade facilitation, and sustainable transport decision-making in alignment with EU decarbonisation goals.

4. Conclusions

Deliverable 3.2 has allowed the project team to collect and analyse technical, regulatory/policy, and governance data for the pertinent UCs of Begonia. The results reported here, which make use of the material collected in previous deliverables as well as fresh analysis and interaction with UC owners and (often through them) key stakeholders, will form the basis for proceeding with the selection of Begonia's final three UCs, which will be treated as implementation templates for ODPs. In particular, the Governance considerations for ODPs, which are treated in D3.2 for each specific UC, will allow us to expand on the way forward for the final three UCs, in terms of key stakeholder interactions and potential implementation scenarios.

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